

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

Be.CULTOUR:

“Beyond CULTural TOURism: human-centred innovations for sustainable and circular cultural tourism”

HORIZON 2020

This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101004627

Call: H2020-SC6-TRANSFORMATIONS-2020 – Type of action: IA (Innovation action)

Deliverable D5.11

Business model and business plans of innovative solutions for sustainable cultural tourism

Due date:	31/01/2024
Submission date:	31/01/2024
Deliverable leader:	HAUTE ECOLE ICHEC - ECAM – ISFSC (ICHEC)
Type:	Report
Author list:	dr. Ruba Saleh, Philippe Drouillon (ICHEC)

Disclaimer

The contents of this deliverable are the sole responsibility of one or more Parties of Be.CULTOUR consortium and can under no circumstances be regarded as reflecting the position of the Agency REA and European Commission under the European Union’s Horizon 2020.

Dissemination Level

-
- | | |
|-------------------------------------|---|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> | PU: Public |
| <input type="checkbox"/> | CO: Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Commission Services) |
-

Abstract

Be.CULTOUR acceleration program kicked-off on 25 October 2022 with the participation of Be.CULTOUR's 19 innovative circular cultural tourism solutions. Three acceleration sessions took place between October and December 2022. A fourth acceleration session will take place in January 2023 and a final pitching session took place between end of January and beginning of March 2023 in Be.CULTOUR's for each of the six Pilot Heritage Sites, namely: Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy; The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain; Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus; Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden; Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia & The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area.

As a result, the 19 innovative circular cultural tourism teams developed their business models (BM) and business plans (BP).

Partners involved in the document

Participant No	Participant organisation name	Short Name	Check if involved
1 Coordinator	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE, Institute of Heritage Science	CNR	
1.1	University of Naples Federico II – DiARC (Linked Third Party)	UNINA	
2	European Regions Research and Innovation Network	ERRIN	
3	ICLEI Europe – Local governments for Sustainability	ICLEI	
4	Iniziativa Cube S.r.l.	INI	
5	Uppsala University	UU	
6	Haute Ecole ICHEC - ECAM - ISFSC	ICHEC	X
7	Open University of the Netherlands	OUNL	
8	APT Basilicata	APT-BAS	
9	Diputación Provincial de Teruel	PGT	
10	Larnaca and Famagusta Districts Development Agency	ANETEL	
11	Laona Foundation	LAONA	
12	Västra Götaland region	VGR	
13	Stalna Konferencija Gradova I Opstina	SCTM	
14	Agentia Pentru Dezvoltare Regionala Nord-Est	NERDA	
15	Verde e Moldova	VEM	

Table of contents

1. DESCRIPTION OF THE PROJECT	7
1.1 Be.CULTOUR specific objectives	8
2. INTRODUCTION	10
2.1 Document structure	10
3 BE.CULTOUR ACCELERATION TRAINING	11
3.1 Session one: Project structuring	11
3.2 Session two: Pretotyping and Marketing Strategy	13
3.3 Session three: Financial Plan, Societal impact & Roadmapping	15
3.4 Session four: Viability and pitching	17
4. BUSINESS MODEL AND BUSINESS PLANS	46
4.1 Business model	46
4.2 Business plan	66
ACRONYMS	175

Figures Summary

Figure 1 – Miro Board frames session 1	13
Figure 2 - Miro Board frames session 2	15
Figure 3 - Miro Board frames session 3	16
Figure 4 - Ingredients of a successful pitch	18
Figure 5 - Ulrika Lindh and Björn Ohlén, Be.CULTOUR partners from Västra Götaland Region giving a welcome speech and explaining Be.CULTOUR local participatory process	20
Figure 6 - Forsvik CHAICE pitch	21
Figure 7 - Prova-Bo long-term rentals pitch	21
Figure 8 - Create, Design & Engage pitch	22
Figure 9 - Forsvik's factory	23
Figure 10 - Forsvik's factory	23
Figure 11 - Keynote by Monice Staudinger, programme Leader, Nordvästra Skaraborg	24
Figure 12 - Forsvik CHAICE pitch in Forsvik	24
Figure 13 - Rydal museum	25
Figure 14 - Rydal museum	26
Figure 15 - Björn Ohlén, Be.CULTOUR partners from Västra Götaland Region presented Be.CULTOUR action plan for Rydal	26
Figure 16 - Philippe Drouillon illustrating the innovation process	27
Figure 17 - Prova-Bo long-term rentals pitch in Rydal	27
Figure 18 - Create, Design & Engage pitch in Rydal	28
Figure 19 - Be.CULTOUR partners and innovators group picture in Rydal	28
Figure 20 - The cultural park of Rio Martin	30
Figure 21 - The cultural park of Rio Martin	30
Figure 22 - Eco glamping under the stars pitch	31
Figure 23 - Aridscape pitch	31
Figure 24 - La chica cabeza de bosque pitch	32
Figure 25 - Philippe Drouillon explaining how to set up an entrepreneurial dynamic for good at territorial level	32
Figure 26 - The three innovative teams answer questions	33
Figure 27 – Speed-dating session	33
Figure 28 - Digital Nomads Platform pitch	35
Figure 29 - ECoolTour pitch	35
Figure 30 - Stephen's route site update pitch	36
Figure 31 - The Bison Land's Heritage pitch	36
Figure 32 - FRUŠKING 8X4X4 pitch	37
Figure 33 - Cultural overload Irig pitch	38
Figure 34 - BAČ BY TOUCH pitch	38
Figure 35 - The three innovative teams answer questions	39
Figure 36 - Fly On Tour Immersivo pitch	40
Figure 37 - Cammino Lucano in Vulture pitch	41
Figure 38 - Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live	41
Figure 39 - dr. Eudokia Balamou, Be.CULTOUR partner from Anetel presenting Be.CULTOUR local action plan	44
Figure 40 - Sensory Bee Nature Trail pitch	44
Figure 41 - Needle festivals pitch	45
Figure 42 - Kalosorisete pitch	45
Figure 43 – The societal impact canvas	46

Tables Summary

Table 1 – Teams Miro Borads

12

1. Description of the Project

Be.CULTOUR stands for “Beyond CULTural TOURism: heritage innovation networks as drivers of Europeanisation towards a human-centred and circular tourism economy”. It expresses the goal to move beyond tourism through a longer-term *human-centred* development perspective, enhancing cultural heritage and landscape values.

Cultural tourism entails opportunities but also risks. Tourism as a whole can be a highly volatile economic sector. If not managed properly, cultural tourism can also easily turn into a “value extractive” industry, generating negative environmental, social and cultural impacts on local communities and ecosystems. This project will **develop specific strategies to promote an understanding** of cultural tourism, which moves away from a “stop-and-go” consumer-oriented approach towards one that puts humans and circular economy models at its centre, paying attention to nature, communities and cultural diversity. “Place”, intended as the *genius loci*, the ancient spirit of the site expressing its “intrinsic value” and “people” as co-creators of its uniqueness, culture, art, tradition, folklore, productivity, spirituality, as well as its “time space routine”, are the focus of Be.CULTOUR, which aims at realizing a longer-term development project for the pilot areas involved.

The overarching goal of Be.CULTOUR is to **co-create and test sustainable human-centred innovations for circular cultural tourism through collaborative innovation networks/methodologies and improved investments strategies**. Targeting deprived remote, peripheral or deindustrialized areas and cultural landscapes as well as over-exploited areas, local **Heritage innovation networks** will co-develop a long-term heritage-led development project in the areas involved enhancing **inclusive economic growth, communities’ wellbeing and resilience, nature regeneration** as well as **effective cooperation** at cross-border, regional and local level.

Wide and diversified partnerships of stakeholders from **18 EU and non-EU regions** of Northern-Central and Southern Europe, the Balkans, the Eastern neighbourhood and the Mediterranean will be the driving force of the project. A **community of 300 innovators** (which includes regional authorities and municipalities, clusters and associations, museums and tourist boards, entrepreneurs, chambers of commerce, citizens, researchers, practitioners as well as project partners) in **6 pilot regions** will **co-create innovative place-based solutions for human-centred development through sustainable and circular cultural tourism**.

Collaborative “Heritage innovation networks” will be established in **6 European deprived remote, peripheral and deindustrialised areas and cultural landscapes** identified as “pilot innovation ecosystems”: committed to the project’s objectives, they have defined clear cultural tourism-

related challenges requiring innovation that will serve as the basis for the collaboration with the **16 additional “mirror innovation ecosystems”**. Mutual learning and up-scaling of business solutions will be the objectives of the collaboration between pilot and mirror ecosystems, building the sustainability of the project's results beyond its lifetime.

By adopting a human-centred quadruple/quintuple helix approach to co-design, **Be.CULTOUR will result in 6 community-led Action Plans, 18 innovative human-centred solutions and 6 close-to-market prototypes** of new cultural tourism integrated services and products: these will directly contribute to **inclusive economic growth, communities’ wellbeing and resilience, and nature regeneration** in pilot and mirror regions, **stimulating effective cooperation** at a cross-border, regional and local level. The core partners of the Consortium will progressively build Be.CULTOUR sustainability by broadening the interregional collaboration while anchoring it to relevant EU initiatives in the academic, business and institutional realms.

1.1 Be.CULTOUR specific objectives

The scopes of the Be.CULTOUR project will be achieved through a set of specific, measurable, achievable, realistic and time-constrained (SMART) specific objectives:

Objective 1 – To assess the impacts and market potential of sustainable and circular cultural tourism at national, regional and local level through multidimensional quantitative and qualitative indicators, innovative statistical methods and advanced smart data management systems;

Objective 2 – To build a Community of Practice of 6 pilot regional ecosystems and a Community of Interest with 16 “mirror ecosystems” in EU and non-EU countries actively engaged in knowledge-sharing and exploitation of Be.CULTOUR’s approach, methodology, tools, and innovative solutions for sustainable and circular cultural tourism;

Objective 3 – To co-develop 6 Action Plans for sustainable and circular cultural tourism by establishing collaborative “Heritage innovation networks” in 6 pilot regions in Northern-Central and Southern Europe, the Balkans, the Eastern neighbourhood and the Mediterranean;

Objective 4 – To co-develop, prototype and test human-centred and place-specific product, process and service innovations for sustainable and circular cultural tourism in pilot heritage sites;

Objective 5 – To provide policy recommendations for more effective use of European Structural Investment Funds (ESIFs) and other EU funds to support cultural tourism innovation ecosystems in pilot and mirror regions, and develop a proposal of evolution of ESIFs through synergies with other public funds;

Objective 6 – To contribute to deepen cultural Europeanisation through information and educational activities focused on the European history, identity and culture expressed in tangible and intangible cultural heritage and cultural landscapes, developing European Cultural Routes and European Heritage Labels in pilot heritage sites.

All partners have wide experience in developing and testing the Be.CULTOUR proposed approach, methodology and tools, ensuring the effective and time-constrained achievement of all the above-mentioned specific goals.

2. Introduction

The main award of Be.CULTOUR hackathon consisted of a 4-month acceleration period offered by ICHEC Brussels Management School. During the first acceleration session, each of the 19 innovative teams discussed the team's pulse and availability; fine-tuned the innovative solution features and components, identified the riskiest assumptions, and selected the ones to be tested, set up a solution roadmap based on a set of "value streams", got acquainted with the content of a "Business" plan. During the second acceleration session, each team discussed the team's pulse and availability; started providing a retrospective on what has been achieved, designed prototypes, set up a marketing strategy and finally planned its 2nd iteration. During the third acceleration session, each team discussed the team's pulse and availability; provided a retrospective on what has been achieved, defined the financial model, identified, and evaluated societal impacts, prepared the Business Plan and planned the 3rd iteration.

Throughout the three sessions, each team worked collaboratively in a breakout room on its Miro board. After each session, the 19 teams were assigned a homework to complete before the next session. The fourth acceleration session was divided in two parts. Part I focused on answering questions, fine-tuning financial figures and pitch creation. While part II was centred on cross-fertilisation and peer to peer exchange through dry runs. Finally, the pitching sessions took place in-situ in four pilot heritage sites and on Zoom for the remaining two.

2.1 Document structure

The document is structured as follows:

Section 1 describes the project and its objectives

Section 2 provides an introduction

Section 3 introduces presents Be.CULTOUR acceleration training

Section 4 presents the business models and plans

3 Be.CULTOUR acceleration training

3.1 Session one: Project structuring

Session 1: Project structuring, 25 October 2022 from 09:00-12:00

This first session was attended by 58 participants as follows:

-48 innovators

1 participant per team (Cammino Lucano in Vulture, La chica cabeza de bosque, Forsviks CHAICE, BAČ BY TOUCH, Stephen's route site update) (4)

2 participants per team (Fly On Tour Immersivo, Eco glamping under the stars, Needle Festivals, Digital Nomads Platform) (8)

3 participants per team (Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live, AridScape The wide as heritage, Create, Design & Engage, Cultural overload - Irig road) (12)

4 participants per team (Sensory Bee Nature Trail, Kalosorisete, Prova-Bo long-term rentals, FRUŠKING 8x4x4, ECoolTour, The Bison Land's Heritage) (24)

-3 facilitators from ICHEC and 7 Be.CULTOUR partners

This session had the following objectives:

-Fine-tune the innovative solution features and components: What the users/clients will see, touch, hear concretely!

-Identify the riskiest assumptions and select the ones to be tested after session 1

-Set up a solution roadmap based on a set of "value streams"

-Get acquainted with the content of a "Business" plan

-Plan the first iteration to be executed

Implementation:

All the sessions adopted the hackathon methodology. Therefore, concepts were introduced in plenary and then each team co-worked in its own breakout room. During this session the 19 teams were introduced to their homework which was due before session two (15/11/2022). They were also advised to discuss together and then divide the homework between yourselves. It was recommended to set an internal deadline for the completion of each task. Finally, it was explained that by completing these tasks, they can advance as a team in the reflection, common understanding and development of their project.

During the first session, every team worked on its Miro board (see table 1). The first task was to complete frame 7¹: Team Zone and discuss the team pulse and availability. The second was to discuss and work on frame 4: User customer journey map, test assumptions & assumption test planning. Finally, teams co-designed frame 5: Project roadmap.

Session 1 homework:

The homework consisted of:

- Working on the team’s action plan
- Achieving the 1st iteration
- Testing selected riskiest assumptions
- Updating their solution according to lessons learned from the different tests

Be.CULTOUR 2022 - Hackathon/Acceleration - MIRO Links		
Team	Project	MIRO link
1	Cammino Lucano in Vulture	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIF8zo=?share_link_id=930602021345
2	Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaICvmU=?share_link_id=370087428072
3	Fly On Tour Immersivo	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaICvAE=?share_link_id=296924049260
4	Eco glamping under the stars	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIDG38=?share_link_id=722939586970
5	AridScape The wide as heritage	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIDGRk=?share_link_id=644610833169
6	La chica cabeza de bosque	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIANa8=?share_link_id=928902835823
7	Sensory Bee Nature Trail	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIAKES=?share_link_id=770437234366
8	Needle Festivals	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIA-VQ=?share_link_id=276561392659
9	Kalosorisete	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIAqRA=?share_link_id=500522024177
10	Forsviks CHAICE	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIAr8o=?share_link_id=271333721703
11	Prova-Bo long-term rentals	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBV-l=?share_link_id=492362258417
12	Create, Design & Engage	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBVY4=?share_link_id=993418438767
13	FRUŠKING 8x4x4	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBlro=?share_link_id=201686343569
14	Cultural overload - Irig road	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBlWI=?share_link_id=257908424650
15	BAČ BY TOUCH	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBcPY=?share_link_id=433643644559
16	Digital Nomads Platform	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBCSU=?share_link_id=366115127794
17	ECoolTour	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBymU=?share_link_id=547475920430
18	Stephen's route site update	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBt4l=?share_link_id=896098901715
19	The Bison Land’s Heritage	https://miro.com/app/board/uXjVPaIBtaw=?share_link_id=366965678570

Table 1 – Teams Miro Borads

¹ Frames are accessible on the Miro Boards of the teams. The links are provided in table 1.

Figure 1 – Miro Board frames session 1

3.2 Session two: Prototyping and Marketing Strategy

Session 2: Prototyping and Marketing Strategy, 15 November 2022 from 09:00-12:00

This second session was attended by 47 participants as follows:

-41 innovators

0 participant per team (La chica cabeza de bosque)

1 participant per team (Cammino Lucano in Vulture, Eco glamping under the stars, Forsviks CHAICE, Stephen's route site update, ECoolTour) (5)

2 participants per team (AridScape The wide as heritage, Needle Festivals, Prova-Bo long-term rentals, BAČ BY TOUCH) (8)

3 participants per team (Create, Design & Engage, Kalosorisete, Fly On Tour Immersivo, FRUŠKING 8x4x4, Digital Nomads Platform, The Bison Land's Heritage, Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live, Cultural overload - Irig road) (24)

4 participants per team (Sensory Bee Nature Trail) (4)

-3 facilitators from ICHEC and 3 Be.CULTOUR partners

This session had the following objectives:

- Provide a retrospective on what has been achieved at the end of iteration 1 vs what was planned
- Design prototypes (eg : landing page, storyboard)
- Set up a marketing strategy based on AARRR² marketing strategy
- Plan the 2nd iteration to be executed

Implementation:

The session's key concepts were introduced in plenary and then each team co-worked in its own breakout room. The 19 teams were also introduced to their homework which was due before session three (13/12/2022). During this second acceleration session, teams started by completing the Team Zone and discussing between themselves the team pulse and availability. Then they moved to Prototyping: worked on their landing page, and its related user/customer journey storyboard and a mini value proposition. Finally, teams co-designed their project's marketing strategy.

Session 2 homework:

The homework consisted of:

- Achieving the 2nd iteration
- Testing prototypes and additional riskiest assumptions toward specific target customers / users
- Fine tuning the Marketing Strategy and complete the marketing plan
- Updating the solution according to lessons learned from the different tests

² AARRR stands for acquisition, activation, retention, referral and revenue.

Figure 2 – Miro Board frames session 2

3.3 Session three: Financial Plan, Societal impact & Roadmapping

Session 3 - Financial Plan, Societal impact & Roadmapping, 13 December 2022 from 09:00-12:00

This second session was attended by 38 participants as follows:

-31 innovators

0 participant per team (AridScape The wide as heritage, Needle Festivals, La chica cabeza de bosque, BAČ BY TOUCH)

1 participant per team (Cammino Lucano in Vulture, Eco glamping under the stars, Forsviks CHAICE, Cultural overload - Irig road, Stephen's route site update) (5)

2 participants per team (Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live, Fly On Tour Immersivo, Digital Nomads Platform, ECoolTour, The Bison Land's Heritage) (10)

3 participants per team (Prova-Bo long-term rentals, Create, Design & Engage, Kalosorisete, FRUŠKING 8x4x4) (12)

4 participants per team (Sensory Bee Nature Trail) (4)

-3 facilitators from ICHEC and 4 Be.CULTOUR partners

This session had the following objectives:

- Provide a retrospective on what has been achieved at the end of iteration 2 vs what was planned
- Define the financial model: types of fundings, monetization / hybrid business models
- Identify and evaluate societal impacts - Theory of Change
- Prepare the Business Plan
- Plan the 3rd iteration to be executed

Implementation:

During the third acceleration session, teams started by completing the Team Zone and discussing between themselves the team pulse and availability. They then worked on fine-tuning their business model by discussing their: revenue streams, funding models, cost structure, investments and budget forecasts. Finally, they worked on their societal impacts, how to assess their impact and on roadmapping.

Session 3 homework

- Achieving the 3rd iteration
- Strengthening the financial model
- Fine tuning the societal impact assessment
- Fine tuning the solution roadmap

Figure 3 – Miro Board frames session 3

3.4 Session four: Viability and pitching

Session 4 – Part I: Fine-tuning financial figures and pitch creation, Monday 16 January 2023 from 13:30-15:00 (CET)

This second session was attended by 44 participants as follows:

-37 innovators

0 participant per team (Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live, Fly On Tour Immersivo, La chica cabeza de bosque, Needle Festivals, Digital Nomads Platform, Stephen's route site update)

1 participant per team (Cammino Lucano in Vulture, Eco glamping under the stars, AridScape The wide as heritage, Forsviks CHAICE, ECoolTour) (5)

2 participants per team (The Bison Land's Heritage, Cultural overload - Irig road) (4)

3 participants per team (Prova-Bo long-term rentals, Create, Design & Engage, Kalosorisete, FRUŠKING 8x4x4) (12)

4 participants per team (Sensory Bee Nature Trail, BAČ BY TOUCH) (16)

-3 facilitators from ICHEC and 4 Be.CULTOUR partners

This session had the following objectives:

- Provide retrospective on what has been achieved at the end of iteration 3 vs what was planned
- Fine-tune the financial figures
- Pitch creation

Implementation

During part I of the fourth acceleration session, ICHEC team answered questions related to financials, and discussed with the teams the main ingredients of a successful pitch. The teams were provided before the session with a Business Plan which was explained lengthily during the session. The teams were also coached on how to pitch their solutions.

Session 4 homework

- Preparing the final pitch (the business plan)

Figure 4 – Ingredients of a successful pitch

Session 4 – Part II: Pitch challenge through dry runs

For this second part of session four, it was important to cross-fertilise and get feedback also from peers and not only from coaches. For this reason, three dry-runs took place during which 6 teams pitched and shared comments and suggestions for improvement for the final pitching session.

Dry-run 1: Thursday 19 January 2023 13:30-15:00 CET (on-line)

PHS: Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden

(Forsviks CHAICE, Prova-Bo long-term rentals, Create, Design & Engage)

&

PHS: Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus

(Sensory Bee Nature Trail, Needle Festivals, Kalosorisete)

Dry-run 2: Friday 27 January 2023 14:30-16:00 CET (on-line)

PHS: Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy

(Cammino Lucano in Vulture, Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live, Fly On Tour Immersivo)

&

PHS: The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain

(Eco glamping under the stars, AridScape The wide as heritage, La chica cabeza de bosque)

Dry-run 3: Tuesday 31 January 2023 14:00-15:50 (CET) (on-line)

PHS: Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
(FRUŠKING 8x4x4, Cultural overload - Irig road, BAČ BY TOUCH)

&

PHS: The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border
area

(Digital Nomads Platform, ECoolTour Stephen's route site update, The Bison Land's Heritage)

Final pitching sessions program

Pilot Heritage Site: Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden

Tuesday 24 and Wednesday 25 January 2023

Day 1

The first in-situ pitching session took place on 24 January 2023 at the venue of Västra Götaland Region in, Gothenburg, Sweden. Ulrika Lindh and Björn Ohlén, Be.CULTOUR partners from Västra Götaland Region kicked off the pitching session by giving a welcome speech and explaining Be.CULTOUR local participatory process and the co-designed action plan by local stakeholders.

dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR project, Be.CULTOUR hackathon and acceleration training. While Philippe Drouillon illustrated the innovation process and methodology by providing concrete examples from acceleration hubs he animates in Belgium, France and Luxembourg.

The three Swedish teams pitched their Innovative circular cultural tourism solutions to a variety of stakeholders from the regional and local level coming from academia, public and private sector, impact investors and local media. Key people who could provide/share financial, physical and/or human resources for the successful implementation of their projects.

Figure 5 – Ulrika Lindh and Björn Ohlén, Be.CULTOUR partners from Västra Götaland Region giving a welcome speech and explaining Be.CULTOUR local participatory process

Forsvik CHAICE³ (Forsvik Cultural Heritage, Arts and Innovation Centre): aims to create a creative and cultural meeting place in Forsvik. A pitch presented by Kolja Schallenberg, Viktor Daggberg, Linnea Lindgren and Malin Alm Berglund.

Figure 6 – Forsvik CHAICE pitch

Prova-Bo long-term rentals (Test Living): intends to test a living way in the countryside while dedicating empty houses and apartments to good adaptive reuse. A pitch presented by Lovisa Kumlien, Elisabet Arns and Lena Göthe.

Figure 7 – Prova-Bo long-term rentals pitch

³ www.visitforsvik.com

Create, Design & Engage: two twin towns, Rydal and Saltaire (Be.CULTOUR Mirror Region Saltaire inspired from UK) with similar textile heritage are together creating the conditions for new creative and artistic development in their respective places. A pitch presented by Christina Shearer, Peter Albinsson, Rolf Danielsson and Julia Calver.

Figure 8 – Create, Design & Engage pitch

Finally, Christer Gustafsson, Be.CULTOUR partner from Uppsala universitet, delivered an inspiring speech about SMART specialisation and the regional development strategy.

In order to inform and trigger the local ecosystem support, two additional sessions took place. In the afternoon the second session took place in Forsvik and the third session took place the next day in Rydal. The second session started with a beautiful tour of Forsvik, one of the country's first and most well-preserved industrial heritage environments. The main features of the area were a saw, a hammer, and a mill, all driven by the power of water. By the end of the 17th century, the possibility of using the bar stool hammer was utilized. In the middle of the 19th century a mechanical workshop was established and became Skaraborg's first engineering industry. Complementary buildings with features such as clay media, metal foundry and wood grinding and paper pulp manufacturing were also added by hand. What is special to Forsvik was the history of women. Who had positions as owners, users and managers of farms, goods and workshops and good education. In 1886, Forsvik's built a railroad which was used to transport goods from Forsvik to the boats in Göta Canal. The track was used until the 1940s. Parts of the old track have been

rebuilt today. In 2008, 470 meters of the transport railway between the Göta Canal and Strömbron (bridge) were rebuilt at Forskvik's factory. The reconstruction was funded by the European Union Rural Development Program, Forsviks Association, Sponsors, Karlsborg Tourism AB, Västarvet and Göta Kanal.

Figure 9 – Forskvik's factory

Figure 10 – Forskvik's factory

After the tour, Ulrika Lindh, Be.CULTOUR partner from Västra Götaland Region kicked-off the session in Forsvik by welcoming the stakeholders and explaining Be.CULTOUR action plan for Forsvik. dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR project and Be.CULTOUR hackathon and acceleration training. Philippe Drouillon illustrated the innovation process and methodology by

providing concrete examples from acceleration hubs he animates in Belgium, France and Luxembourg. Followed by an inspiring keynote by Monica Staudinger, programme Leader, Nordvästra Skaraborg.

Afterwards, the four Be.CULTOUR innovators from Forsvik Kolja Schallenberg, Victor Daggberg, Linnear Lindgren and Malin Alm Berglund delivered their 10-minutes pitch. Their Innovative circular cultural tourism solution CHAICE (Forsvik Cultural Heritage, Arts and Innovation Centre) was presented to the local ecosystem. Finally, Christer Gustafsson, Uppsala universitet, delivered an inspiring speech about SMART specialisation and the regional development strategy.

Figure 11 – keynote by Monica Staudinger, programme Leader, Nordvästra Skaraborg

Figure 12– Forsvik CHAICE pitch in Forsvik

Day 2

On 25 January 2023, the third and last Be.CULTOUR accelerator pitching session in Sweden took place at Rydal museum⁴. The oldest preserved spinnery in Sweden. The textile factory from 1853, the inn and the renovated workers' housing are the most striking features.

The session started with Be.CULTOUR partner from Västra Götaland Region welcoming the stakeholders. Next, dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR project and Be.CULTOUR hackathon and acceleration training and Philippe Drouillon illustrated the innovation process and methodology by providing concrete examples from acceleration hubs he animates in Belgium, France and Luxembourg. Bjorn Ohlen, Be.CULTOUR partner from Västra Götaland Region presented the action plan for Rydal which was co-designed under the framework of Be.CULTOUR.

The two innovative Be.CULTOUR teams from Rydal delivered their 10-minutes pitches. Lovisa Kumlien, Elisabet Arns and Lena Göthe pitched their Prova-Bo long-term rentals (Test Living) solution and Christina Shearer, Peter Albinsson, Rolf Danielsson and Julia Calver pitched their Create, Design & Engage solution to the local ecosystem. The audience raised very concrete and relevant questions and engaged in a productive discussion with the two groups.

Figure 13–Rydal museum

⁴ <https://www.vastsverige.com/en/mark/produkter/rydals-museum/?site=153435>

Figure 14–Rydal museum

Figure 15– Bjorn Ohlen, Be.CULTOUR partner from Västra Götaland Region presented Be.CULTOUR action plan for Rydal

Figure 16– Philippe Drouillon illustrating the innovation process

Figure 17– Prova-Bo long-term rentals pitch in Rydal

Figure 18– Create, Design & Engage pitch in Rydal

Figure 19– Be.CULTOUR partners and innovators group picture in Rydal

Pilot Heritage Site: The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain

Thursday 02 February 2023

The second pitching session in situ took place at the venue of the cultural park of Rio Martin, in Teruel province, Aragon region, in Spain. Three teams pitched their Innovative circular cultural tourism solutions to a number of local stakeholders.

Joaquin Noe, Deputy of the Territorial Development Area and Delegate for European Programmes of the Provincial Council of Teruel delivered an institutional welcome. Be.CULTOUR project partner, Laura Gascon Herrero, Senior Project Manager at the Provincial Government of Teruel kicked off the session by explaining the local action plan developed under the framework of Be.CULTOUR. Afterwards dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR project and Be.CULTOUR hackathon and acceleration training.

The three innovative teams inspired the local stakeholders with their circular cultural tourism solutions aimed at the sustainable and human-centred development of their rural territory and communities. Eco glamping under the stars: aims at inviting tourists to drive through Aragon region, stay and enjoy the local products, the landscape and stars. It aims also to provide an alternative offer and connect the territory by turning limitations into opportunities. A pitch presented by Alberto Ipas. Aridscape intends to connect knowledge & talents with locations and resources. It aims to train, preserve and promote the vernacular cultural heritage. A pitch presented by Ismael Pizarro Munoz and Paz Gonzalez Marinas. La chica cabeza de bosque intends to highlight the positive elements of Teruel such as the cultural, social, and ethnographic components. It aims to enrich the cultural heritage and biodiversity of Teruel by making use of resources like water, land, vegetation, and locations. A pitch presented by Sara Bosque Camacho, Ederne Caballero Zaldivar.

Philippe Drouillon gave an inspirational talk about rural innovation with concrete examples from acceleration hubs he animates and contributes to in France. Finally, a speed dating session took place during which the innovators pitched their projects to the local actors of the territory of the Cultural Park of Rio Martín.

Figure 20– The cultural park of Rio Martín

Figure 21– The cultural park of Rio Martín

Figure 22– Eco glamping under the stars pitch

Figure 23– Aridscape pitch

Figure 24– La chica cabeza de bosque pitch

Figure 25– Philippe Drouillon explaining how to set up an entrepreneurial dynamic for good at territorial level

Figure 26– The three innovative teams answer questions

Figure 27– Speed-dating session

Pilot Heritage Site: The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area. Wednesday 15 February 2023, 09:00-12:00 (on-line).

Because of the war in Ukraine, the third pitching session took place on Zoom. Be.CULTOUR project partner from Romania, Roxana Slemco and from Moldova Anatolie Risina kicked off the session by explaining the local action plan developed under the framework of Be.CULTOUR. Carmen Chasovschi introduced Be.CULTOUR local participatory methodology and Alexandra Albu moderated the session. dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR project, the hackathon and acceleration training.

The four innovative teams pitched their Innovative circular cultural tourism solutions to a number of local stakeholders.

Digital Nomads Platform aims to become a one-stop-shop solution for highly skilled digital workers, to choose the north-eastern region as a work – live – explore destination for up to 6 months. The platform explores individual needs and skill set and match each profile with a recommended journey. The pitch presented by Anca Zota (Romanian team).

EcoolTour is a revolutionary algorithm that generates custom routes for travellers visiting the Republic of Moldova. It makes the planning process easier for travellers by taking into account their preferences and needs. A pitch presented by Constantin Miron (Moldovan team).

Stephen's route site update is a web platform which presents a unique opportunity for history and culture lovers' tourists who want to follow the Stephan's route and be the creators of their own route. It connects tourist attractions within the route through information panels with direct access to the digital platform through a QR code. A pitch presented by Valentin Ceban (Moldovan team).

The Bison Land’s Heritage is a unique learning experience which aims to reveal the subtle connection among the spiritual, cultural and natural aspects of local heritage. The project offers also a treasure hunt app and provides an educational “environment” for schools, families and companies and a connection with the local communities. A pitch presented by Viorela Chiper (Romanian team).

dr. Ruba Saleh and Roxana Slemco delivered the conclusions and talked Be.CULTOUR innovators through the next steps and implementation phase.

Figure 28– Digital Nomads Platform pitch

Figure 29– ECoolTour pitch

Figure 30– Stephen's route site update pitch

Figure 31– The Bison Land's Heritage pitch

**Pilot Heritage Site: Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia
Wednesday 22 February 2023, Novi Sad**

The fourth pitching session took place at Svilara, Novi Sad, in Serbia. The session kicked-off with welcoming remarks by Mr. Nenad Ivošević, Provincial Secretary for Commerce and Tourism and Ms. Danijela Vanušić, Assistant Minister, Ministry of Culture. dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR project and Be.CULTOUR hackathon & acceleration training. Nikola Tarbuk, Secretary General, of Be.CULTOUR partner Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities delivered a welcome speech. Philippe Drouillon, delivered an inspirational talk about how to set up an entrepreneurial dynamic for good at the territorial level and Koen Demarsin, shared a practical experience of cultural mapping at a regional level.

The three scalable innovative circular cultural tourism solutions from this Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site pitched their solutions.

FRUŠKING 8X4X4 a special tourism game which starts with (8x4x4) cards which have a QR code at the back. Each card hides a special story, tour and a wine. The pitch was presented by Avakum Kvas.

Cultural overload Irig aims at developing a mixed reality application which is providing tourists with immersive experience. The application informs and guide tourists through natural, cultural, and gastronomical heritage of Irig. It also structures and unify local tourist attractions. Thus, it serves as a tool to mobilize, connect, educate, and empower local entrepreneurs and institutions to provide an extraordinary service and get feedback for the future tourism strategy. The pitch was presented by Ana Aleksic.

BAČ BY TOUCH aims to offer an interactive environment which contains virtual and sensorial experience, promotion of cultural heritage, local entrepreneurship, rural tourism, and nature preservation. The virtual environment offers an experience of medieval life at the Bac Fortress. It also compasses 3D dynamic audio and characters which will answer questions about the Bac area. The pitch was presented by Zorica Subotic and Milan Koncar.

Finally, Igor Pucarević, Be.CULTOUR National Project Coordinator, at Standing Conference of Towns and Municipalities (SCTM), Serbia, explained Be.CULTOUR local action plan.

Figure 32– FRUŠKING 8X4X4 pitch

Figure 33– Cultural overload Irig pitch

Figure 34– BAČ BY TOUCH pitch

Figure 35– The three innovative teams answer questions

Last session: Vulture-Alto Bradano area, Basilicata Region, Italy

Tuesday 28 February 2023, 09:00-12:00 (on-line)

The fifth pitching session took place on Zoom. Be.CULTOUR project partner, Antonio Nicoletti kicked off the session by explaining the local action plan developed under the framework of Be.CULTOUR Basilicata region. dr. Antonia Gravagnuolo Be.CULTOUR project coordinator presented the project and its participatory methodology. dr. Ruba Saleh presented Be.CULTOUR hackathon & acceleration training. Two teams pitched their Innovative circular cultural tourism solutions to a number of local stakeholders.

Fly On Tour Immersivo is passion for flying, for authentic knowledge of places, for the exploration of inaccessible areas, for accessible tourism. The use of visors and FPV (First Person View) technology allows you to watch and experience unfamiliar or morphologically impossible locations or simply enjoy a panoramic view with professionally piloted drones. Its mission is to break down architectural barriers, giving people the opportunity to visit inaccessible places. This pitch was presented by Francesco Calderoni.

Cammino Lucano in Vulture offers a "slow" travel that allows people to get to know Basilicata from unexpected points of view that cannot be perceived by hit-and-run tourism that transform the journey into an unforgettable experience. The project aims at creating cultural paths capable of providing experiences connected to the intimate and deep stretches of Lucania through the Municipalities of: Melfi, Rapolla, Barile, Ginestra, Ripacandida, Rionero in Vulture, the lakes of Monticchio, Atella and San Fele. This video pitch was presented by Michele Santangelo.

The third group didn't attend the pitching session. the project Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live aims to activate cultural exchanges for students from all around EU and from different knowledge fields to design solutions for the urban regeneration & sustainable development of Vulture, focusing in particular on cultural tourism. By becoming temporary local residents, students contribute to the territory and participate in events and activities organised in partnership with local associations.

Figure 36– Fly On Tour Immersivo pitch

Figure 37– Cammino Lucano in Vulture pitch

OUR SOLUTION

Our solution aims to **activate cultural exchanges** for students from all around EU and from different knowledge fields.

- Students will design solutions for the urban regeneration and the sustainable development of Vulture, focusing in particular on cultural tourism
- Partnerships with University of Basilicata, local municipalities and entrepreneurs
- Not just tourist, students are (temporary) residents
- Events and activities will be part of the experience in partnership with local associations

FIRST MAIN PROJECT

IDENTIFICATION OF A SPECIFIC PLACE/RURAL BUILDING TO REGENERATE/RE-ACTIVATE AS MAIN HUB OF THE PROJECT

- First main project
- A place for people to meet and/or to work
- Conventions and local businesses
- Physical core of the project
- A place where cultural activities can be designed and take place
- Sustainable reuse of waste and local materials

Figure 38– Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live

Pilot Heritage Site: Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus

Thursday 02 March 2023

Be.CULTOUR study visit in the rural landscape of Larnaca started with a first stop at the UNESCO World Heritage neolithic settlement Choirokoitia. A very well-preserved stone and earthen architecture village which dates back to the 7th millennium. The next stop was at the museum of basketry in Choirokoitia which was restored and refurbished by the brilliant entrepreneur Petros Nicolaou. At the fully fledged decorated museum with local handicrafts, we participated in a halloumi making workshop run by Petros himself who is a talented craftsman as well and who produces three different types of baskets from local materials namely: straw, water reed and bamboo. Petros workshops are always full of people because of his human-centred approach and his passion and commitment to Cypriot intangible heritage. Our third stop was the Municipality of Lefkara which has been awarded the status of one of the 'Best Tourism Villages' by the World Tourism Organisation (WTO) thanks to a combination of exemplary sustainable tourism practises and its traditional character of well-preserved customs, handicrafts, architecture, and local gastronomy. Here we had the opportunity to learn about the history and challenges of Lefkara lace which was inscribed in 2009 on UNESCO's Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity and Lefkara Silversmithing. We also visited the entrepreneur Aphrodite Nikolaou who invented Lefkara lace biscuits and visited the Holy Cross Church.

The sixth and last pitching session took place at the Environmental Information Center of Rural Larnaca, Skarinou in the heart of Be.CULTOUR Pilot Heritage Site: Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus. The session kicked-off with welcoming remarks by Be.CULTOUR partner, dr. Eudokia Balamou, Operations manager, Anetel. dr. Balamou presented Be.CULTOUR local action plan. Her presentation was followed by a presentation by dr. Ruba Saleh about Be.CULTOUR project hackathon and acceleration training. The three Cypriot teams inspired the stakeholders with their innovative circular cultural tourism solutions.

Sensory Bee Nature Trail aims to revive & revitalize the unique medieval picturesque village of Vavla in threat of depopulation. Its goals are to preserve its cultural & natural heritage, the stories and legends associated with it & bee keeping history in the area, through enhancing community interaction of Honey Villages, through smart specialization, & provide knowledge, joy and happiness to children based on sustainable development aligned with EU 2030 goals & Green Deal. This pitch was presented by Yioula Papakyriacou.

Needle Festivals is a year-round festival with the mission to discover and explore Cypriot identity through cultural, entrepreneurial and sports activities. While embracing the rural landscape, the festivals will disrupt the status quo as social opportunity spaces for participants, to explore and elaborate on Cypriot identity: how it appears in daily life, sound, taste, and aesthetic through sensorial experiences and emerging relationships. This pitch was presented by Georgios Antoniou.

Kalosorisete (joy of life) aims to provide a user-friendly technology, where Cypriots and people visiting rural Larnaca in Cyprus to experience the authentic way of life and live authentic Cypriot experiences. Through a website and an application people can book through the website local experiences such as pasta making or chair making workshop. The actual product / service will be the experience as practiced by locals from generation to generation. On the back end of the website/application the vendors will be able to manage their bookings, their workshops and on later stage they will be able to upload products on the application's marketplace. This pitch was presented by Maris Kapari and Stelios Kaparis.

Figure 39– dr. Eudokia Balamou, Be.CULTOUR partner from Anetel presenting Be.CULTOUR local action plan

Figure 40– Sensory Bee Nature Trail pitch

Figure 41– Needle festivals pitch

Figure 42– Kalosorisete pitch

4. Business model and business plans

4.1 Business model

As explained in D3.6 the Societal Impact Canvas (Figure 43) was adopted for the innovative solutions. It is an evolution of the classical Business Model and Lean Canvases and embeds the societal impact dimension from different perspectives:

- “**Raison d’être**” aka purpose positioning humans and sustainability at the heart of the solution;
- “**Value Propositions**” that cover not only the functional dimension but also focus on environmental (circular) and social (people) dimensions;
- Societal impacts** where environmental and social positive impacts are demonstrated;
- Reallocation of potential profits and surpluses** as lever of further positive impacts;
- Governance** as a way to embrace key stakeholders’ perspectives and to keep human centrality in the development of the solution.

The use of the societal impact canvas helped the participants to visualise the 4 pillars of a successful solution: desirability, feasibility, viability, and impact.

Figure 43– The societal impact canvas

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project : **Cammino Lucano in Vulture** Date : **2023** Version : **F**

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star? What's our Maslow's Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our passion, our drivers? Build a new way of pilgrimage in Vulture - Alto Bradano while valuing and promoting an itinerary to visit the territory		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries' needs? Our Cammino Lucano in Vulture helps tourists who want to immerse themselves in nature by offering a structured route among the most interesting cultural sites in the Vulture territory, instead of not having precise indications on the itinerary by proposing Naturalistic way - Spiritual path - Wine and food tradition - Local community engagement - Astronomical connections		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakes of the Doughnut Model can we connect my project to? SDGs 2,3,4, 8, 9, 10,11,12, 13,15	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why they connect from us? success? What do they expect from us?		PROBLEMS (micro & macro) Today, what are the challenges, problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities? Limited cultural touristic offer, trouble in creating network in the territory, little awareness of the potential of the territory		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customer developed, established and maintained? Which channels are used to: • get in touch with them? • reach our segments? • make our solution available? Website, tour operators, specialised magazines and social media	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (source and/or mandatory) required to achieve the solution (Physical; intellectual; human; financial) and run underlying key activities? Experts in naturalistic, religious, astronomical, gastronomic and experiential matters insourced in website, content creation and specific designer, SMM, outsourced		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems? Pilgrimage, excursions, restaurants		TARGET SEGMENTS (customers / users / beneficiaries) To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters? Trekking enthusiasts experiential tourists Religious tourists astronomy enthusiasts food and wine tourists	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: salary team, external consulting fees, web and content developers fees.		SOCIETAL IMPACTS What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? Social impacts: inclusion engagement for local population with tourist Environmental impacts: environmental education Economical impacts: increased revenue for local shops Risk of adverse impacts: massive tourism, exploitation of the territory		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the existing financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price? Revenue streams: advertising, crowdfunding, freemium.	
GOVERNANCE Which principles and signposts that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution? Non-profit association		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why? The size of our potential target segments is quite small because we are working in niche market. The itinerary will economically supported by public funds and contributions by the users and the shops on the path.			

DESIRABILITY
 FEASIBILITY
 VIABILITY
 SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
BUSINESS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION
CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project : Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live... Date : 2023 Version : F.....

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star & What's our Massive Transformation Purpose (MTP) & What is the expected impact & How is it connected to our passion, our drivers & Circular and sustainable development of rural areas.		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives) & How each of them uniquely answers to customer / users / beneficiaries' needs & Our project helps students live a learning by doing experience and a strong connection with the local community aimed at developing local projects focused on sustainable development and tourism		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenges does our project address & Which SDGs & Which stakes of the Doughnut Model can we connect my project to & SDGs 1, 3,7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13,15, 16	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners & At which level (macro & micro) & What do they bring that is unique & Why do they contribute to our success & What do they expect from us & Municipalities, region, University, Association of exchange programs for students.		PROBLEMS (macro & micro) Today, what are the challenges, problems faced by users, beneficiaries, to their needs, size opportunities & Depopulation and lack of connection, infrastructures, accommodations & innovation.		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed, established and maintained? & With which channels & How do we reach our segments & How do we make our solution available & University exchange programmes, tour operators	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (source and/or mandatory) required to achieve the solution (physical, intellectual, financial, human, social) and run underlying key activities & We are a team of experts & we work in the field of consultancies for local authorities & enterprises in order to obtain funds to develop their projects.		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems & Erasmus programme		TARGET SEGMENTS (customers / users / beneficiaries) To whom does our solution create value & What are our customers / users segments & Who are our early adopters & University exchange students and tourists	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution & Costs: bills, events, management of the hub, materials and tools useful for the activities.		SOCIETAL IMPACTS (+ -) What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives & Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts & Constant presence of new residents (students and tourists), reuse of abandoned buildings & enhancement of the local economy both for businesses & services		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for & At what price & Revenue streams: rent of co-working space, events, meetings and public and private grants.	
GOVERNANCE & SERVICES Which principles and signposts that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective & How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution & Non-profit association		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution & What are they allocated for & Why & Improving the regenerated hub, creating job opportunities for women and young people thanks to the profits from co-working spaces, renting multifunctional rooms			

■ DESIRABILITY
■ FEASIBILITY
■ VIABILITY
■ SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
INTEGRATED MANAGEMENT SCHOOL
START LAB
ICHEC
ICHEC
FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project : Fly On Tour Immersivo

Date : 2023

Version : F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission/ Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our position, our drivers?</p> <p>To make unaccessible / undiscovered places in Gravina, in South Italy accessible to everyone</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, social and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our FLY - ON Immersive tours for all helps disabled people and people with reduced mobility to receive as much information as possible for an "accessible holiday". Our FLY - ON Immersive tours for everyone helps young people to get to know and be active protagonists of an alternative cultural offer through a unique storytelling ("collection of stories in flight") unlike the tourist guide who tells you aseptic and through FPV (Visors) & Drones technologies FLY- ON allows to visit in real time unaccessible places</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect my project to?</p> <p>SDGs 4, 5, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? Do they do anything that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Local authorities, partners & suppliers for zero waste of drone's material</p>		<p>PROBLEMS Painful & mixed</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges, problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, relate to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Morphology, lack of infrastructure, lack of time, depopulation</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed, established and maintained? Which channels are used to spread our solution across? How do we reach our segments? How do we make our solution available?</p> <p>Local guides, Tour operators, Local authorities.</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (tangible and/or intangible) required to achieve the solution (Physical, Intellectual, Human, Social) and run underlying key activities?</p> <p>The team is composed by the founders who manage & maintain the equipment, manage public relation</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems?</p> <p>Local guides with no possibility of visiting unaccessible areas, online websites.</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS (customers / users / beneficiaries)</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / user segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>-Young people (18-35) -Educational institutions (public and private) -People with intellectual disabilities & foreign also visitors</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: Equipment (drones), Internal costs (pilot & co-pilot), Outsourced costs: marketing, communication, implementation management & facilitator</p>		<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>How is the solution materialized? How does it conceivably look like? What are its main features / components?</p> <p>Immersive tours for all in inaccessible places</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: Product / subscription / robin hood model</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, how are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Private SME</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS ***</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>More inclusive model & support for people with intellectual disabilities. Spread the vision in more communities from South to North Italy, eventually in other European countries.</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are the objectives for it? Why? Evaluate the possibility of educating young people in the area on environmental issues, with outdoor classes. Creating new avenues for culture in the territory, through tradition & local narration (storytelling). Creating an increasingly collaborative educational model between students & teachers.</p>	

■ DESIRABILITY
■ FEASIBILITY
■ VIABILITY
■ SOCIETAL IMPACT

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project Eco glamping under the stars Date: 2023 Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission/Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our position, our drivers? Offer new & original activities in relation with nature & use our cultural & touristic heritage in an ECO way.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, social and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers/users/beneficiaries needs?</p> <p>Our project helps ecotourists discover the beauty of our territory while enjoying a unique silent & eco-friendly environment. Unlike other accommodations, we offer the possibility to meet & exchange with other guests & with the local community through local products & ad-hoc experiences.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which pillars of the Doughnut Model can we connect to our project to?</p> <p>SDGs 1, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>The Silent Routes, Arño Spa, Martín River Cultural Park, Motorland Aragón, El Cilear Monastery, Montañabian Astronomical Observatory, Dinópolis, La Qjineg</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users/beneficiaries/clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Isolated territory with few touristic offer. Lack of original & attractive touristic offer</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers/users/segments? Who are our early adopters? Which channels are used to reach our segments? How do we make our solution known? How do we make our solution available?</p> <p>Tourist offices Tourist guides Local authorities Social media</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (people and/or equipment) needed to provide the solution? Which individual, human, financial and/or underlying key activities?</p> <p>Three local entrepreneurs & one tourism consultant</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers/users/beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems? There are other initiatives in the territory that obtained European funds & they are working fairly well</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers/users/segments? Who are our early adopters? Which channels are used to reach our segments? How do we make our solution known? How do we make our solution available?</p> <p>-New ecotourists interested in astrotourism - Tourists who want a different offer a new experience - Motorbike riders - BTT tourists - Dinópolis park visitors - Industrial tourism visitors - Couples in love - Rio Martín Cultural Park visitors</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: equipments, infrastructure, staff, running costs. A public & private investment for the infrastructure and cabin domes.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Create connections with & between local entrepreneurs & producers, supplying local food to be cooked around the fire (organic & local)</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring/repeating schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: accommodation, Food & Beverage, activities</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Limited liability company</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p> <p>Train the local workers</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p>	

DESIRABILITY
FEASIBILITY

VIABILITY
SOCIAL IMPACT

ICHEC
INSTITUCIÓ INTERMUNICIPAL

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION
CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Paisajeencontrado (AridScape) Date: 2023 Version: F

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission/Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our passion, our dreams? Valorize villages traditional materials and techniques for enhancing urban landscape & tourism		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the Unique Value Propositions (UVPs), functional, societal and/or environmental (para-social)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries needs? Our project helps European students & graduates looking for good quality practical knowledge & experiences learn hands-on techniques in heritage restoration & landscaping while getting a viable option to live in the territory. Through our website & app they can find a room for rent in a local house. Unlike other training modules where you cannot live in the territory & interact with the community.		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which states of the Doughnut Model can we connect the project to? SDGs 1, 3, 4, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 15, 16	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us? Universities, local authorities, Local community		PROBLEMS (current & future) Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities? Loss of rural heritage, depopulation, loss of heritage value by locals, shortage of rental housing, degradation of industrial heritage		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers established or consolidated? Which channels are used to: • get in touch with them? • reach our segments? • make our solution irreplaceable? Local authorities, Universities, Website, Social media, App	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (people, capital, equipment) required to provide our proposition? (Physical, intellectual, human, financial) and how are they organized, structured and run underlying key activities? Traditional techniques & material expert builder, architect expert in architectural heritage Preservation, tourism professional, agriculture engineer & landscaper architect		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems? Students/Archaeologist stay at a residence at the archaeology park No solutions for landscape & industrial heritage loss		TARGET SEGMENTS (criticisms / users / beneficiaries) To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters? -Local population -Local businesses -Public administrations that are carrying rural regeneration policies -Students willing to acquire practical knowledge	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: equipments and goods, staff, fixed and variable costs, external services		SOCIETAL IMPACTS *** What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? Recovery of traditional sustainable construction. Coexistence between local community & international students. capacity building. Using local materials. Inter-generational connections.		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for & at what price? Revenue streams: workshops, students traineeship fee, rents, projects.	
GOVERNANCE Which principles and approaches that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution? Non for profit organisation		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits / surplus generated by the solution? What are they allocated for & why? Non profit		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION	

DESIRABILITY
 VIABILITY
 FEASIBILITY
 SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
 BUSINESS IMPROVEMENT SCHOOL

START LAB
 ICHEC

ICHEC
 FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: La chica cabeza de bosque

Date: 2023

Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission? Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our passion, our drivers?</p> <p>Our purpose is to generate benefits & enriching tourism experiences in our rural environment in Teruel, Aragón.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives? How each of them uniquely answers to customers' / users' / beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our workshops addressing young, elderly people, & families help these segments improve their mental health through a process of mindfulness, biodiversity & art therapy that result in sensorial experiences. Unlike other immersive experiences, we believe that biodiversity is the key to achieving the future challenges & our cultural heritage is an essential tool.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect the project to?</p> <p>SDGs 2, 3, 5, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 15, 16</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Local associations, local administration, centre for environmental studies, centre of innovation & rural bioeconomy in Teruel.</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Biodiversity & traditional knowledge loss, depopulation, mental health problems</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers established? Which channels are used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> get in touch with them? reach our solutions to them? make our solution available? <p>Local authorities Local media Website Social media</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (people, capital, equipment) required to provide our solution? What are the underlying key activities?</p> <p>A group of complementary profiles: experts in textile crafts, mental health, sustainability, rural development</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems?</p> <p>Lack of intergenerational activities, lack of mindfulness integration in families, lack of interesting workshops</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>Fase1: Aragón population: 1,320 million people (78% under65 years old) Fase2: Valencia population: 4,975 million people (80% under65 years old) + Cataluña: 7,566 million people (81% under65 years old)</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: equipments and goods, staff, fixed and variable costs</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economic and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Recovery of traditional knowledge linked to the natural environment, circularity of local materials, economic development of the area, improving mental health.</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: Experiences workshops, Kit DIY, redesigned second hand clothing, Hand-sewing & dyed clothing</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and agreements that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Ecofeminist cooperative. We need to collaborate as in nature happens that's why our point of view is global & collaborative.</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p> <p>Profit will be invested in making ethnobotany & horticultural therapy accessible to people to enhance territorial value, growth & development</p>			

■ DESIRABILITY
■ FEASIBILITY
■ VIABILITY
■ SOCIETAL IMPACT

FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Sensory Bee Nature Trail

Date: 2023

Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Absolute Transformation Purpose (ATP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our mission, our drivers?</p> <p>Revive & revitalize a unique medieval picturesque village in threat of depopulation</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, social, and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers' / users' / beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our solution provides to families with children, activities all year round for fun & knowledge about the bees & the environment. Thanks to the hive-themed playgrounds & information points. Unlike festivals this experience is available all year on. It also caters for special interest groups with relaxation & privacy features thanks to the various relaxation & meditation points with sound systems & themed relaxing spots with water points. Unlike the other trails is the only themed & innovative in Cyprus.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which 100s? Which pillars of the Doughnut Model can we channel my project to?</p> <p>SDGs 2, 3, 4, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 15</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Vaia Restaurants, Vaia Agriturismo establishments, Vaia community council, Christoula Winery, Vaia schools, Englyfos & Bee Nature Center, Agos Mikas Monastery, church of love, Local Meats Companies, Principian Association of Beekeepers, local artists</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Low tourism flow to the Vaia village, lack of environmental awareness, lack of cooperation</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers being developed, maintained or improved? Which channels are used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • get in touch with them? • reach our segments? • make our solution credible? <p>Larnaka region board, Larnaka & Famagusta development Agency, Deputy Ministry of Tourism, Vaia community council</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (people, capital, technology) required to provide our solution? What are the individual, human, financial, and non-underlying key activities?</p> <p>Team of experts, initial financing, trail maintenance</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems?</p> <p>Bee knowledge trail</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>Families with children, schools, special interest tourism</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: equipments and goods, fixed & variable costs, external services</p>		<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>How is the solution materialized? How does it conceptually look like? What are its main features / components?</p> <p>Creation of a sensory nature trail</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: open days (main stakeholders) Rotarians (Environmental events)</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and agreements that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Non-profit organization</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>The trail designed for families, schools & children with special needs in a deprived area with limited activities for children will increase the flow of tourism, job creation & preserve the culture, history & biodiversity of the routes, by integrating technology and solar energy into a historical site.</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p> <p>Non-profit: revenues for the business of the area</p>	

DESIRABILITY
FEASIBILITY

VIABILITY
SOCIAL IMPACT

ICHEC
INTEGRATED IMPACT TOOL

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION
CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project : Needle Festivals

Date : 2023

Version : F

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star ? What's our Inspiring Transformation Purpose (ITP) ? What is the expected impact ? How is it connected to our passion, our drivers ? Weaving the cultural present to our past in order to shape our future		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives) ? How each of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries needs ? Our solution is to take on the task of constructing a residence of creation. This physical space will be kind & inclusive both to the user & the environment where through the realm of creative arts crucial questions regarding our ethos & cyprriot character can be addressed. Our festival will act as a Hub employing artists of all kind including underrepresented backgrounds & allow them to present their work to locals & visitors thus acting as a Global Ambassador of Cypriot Arts.		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenges does our project address ? Which SDGs ? Which aspects of the Doughnut Model can we connect to our project to ? SDGs 2, 3, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 15	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners ? At which level of the value chain do they connect ? What do they bring that is unique ? Why do they contribute to our success ? What do they expect from us ? Local artists, cultural community groups, local authorities, universities, local business, minorities, local communities, tourism boards		PROBLEMS (users & needs) Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, online to their needs, with opportunities ? Lack of Cypriot collective identity, limited access to cultural activities, lack of opportunity to showcase artists talents, lack of appreciation of contemporary culture, no platform for like minded people to interact.		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / communities developed, maintained, enhanced or disrupted, which channels are used to ? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> get in touch with them ? reach our solution through ? reach our segments ? make our solution available ? Local Community centers, Tourism boards, local authorities, Artistic scene, Social media	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (people and/or solution) required to deliver our solution (product and/or service) ? What are the individual, human, financial and/or underlying key activities ? The team needs to involve additional experts in communications & marketing, architectural design & digital technologies.		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries deliver to their needs/problems ? Traditional festivals		TARGET SEGMENTS To whom does our solution create value ? What are our customers / users segments ? Who are our early adopters ? Curious young Cypriots, Foreign culture enthusiasts, niche tourists, sustainability enthusiasts	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution ? Costs: equipments and goods, staff, fixed and variable costs, external services		SOLUTION How is the solution materialized ? How does it conceptually look like ? Interactive cultural journey composed by exhibiting platform, immersive experiences and food stalls.		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution ? What are the recurring financing schemes ? What are customers ready to pay for ? At what price ? Revenue streams: tickets, memberships, merchandise, services, renting the creative centres	
GOVERNANCE Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective ? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution ? Non-profit organization		SOCIETAL IMPACTS * ** What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution ? From social, economical and environmental perspectives ? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts ? Empowering local communities & establishing social bonds & a resilient cultural system. Regenerative design by enhancing biodiversity & minimize the carbon footprint, sustainable employment opportunities.		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution ? What are they allocated for ? Why ? Non-profit	

DISAPABILITY
FEASIBILITY

VIABILITY
SOCETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
INTEGRATED COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT CENTRE

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION
CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Kalosorisete (joy of culture) Date: 2023 Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding health that it without our Inclusive Transformation Purpose (ITP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our vision, our drivers?</p> <p>We want to be the facilitators that bridge rural culture (tangible & intangible) & make it accessible to anyone who wishes to discover & experience it.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives? How each of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries needs?</p> <p>Our solution offers a user-friendly rural culture platform. Unlike websites that require tedious & time-consuming online/offline research, we offer a one-stop-shop where you can explore environment-friendly & traditional tangible & intangible heritage experiences & enjoy authentic cultural experiences by connecting you directly to local producers & tourism experience providers.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which aspects of the Doughnut Model can we connect to our project to?</p> <p>SDGs 1-16</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Local rural communities, local authorities, local producers</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>What are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>A gap between consumers, travellers, culturally conscious individuals & providers of tourism services / products in rural area.</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / partners / communities developed, which channels are used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> get in touch with them? make our solution known? reach our segments? make our solution available? 	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (finance and/or technology) required to launch, sustain, scale and run underlying key activities?</p> <p>Technology & onboarding of local service providers / producers in-house. The experiences will be "outsourced" to local service providers/producers.</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems?</p> <p>Website with cultural heritage assets.</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>Families, companies, individual travelers</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: scalable technology & staff cost.</p>		<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>How is the solution materialized? How does it conceptually look like?</p> <p>What are its main features / components?</p> <p>A website and application that bridges the gap between locating authenticity and exploring it</p>		<p>Website, Social media, Traditional media</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Limited liability company</p>		<p>SOCIAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Empowering women & young people to establish their own businesses & create their own streams of income, economic growth of local communities.</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the accounting financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: commission & fee based.</p>	
<p>DESIRABILITY</p> <p>FEASIBILITY</p>		<p>VIABILITY</p> <p>SOCIETAL IMPACT</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p>	

ICHEC INCLUSIVE INNOVATION ECOSYSTEMS

START LAB ICHEC

ICHEC FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Forsviks CHAICE

Date: 2023

Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our passion, our drivers?</p> <p>Create a place where people can grow!</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, social and/or environmental perspectives)? How much of them uniquely answer to customers' users' / beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our open-minded hub for material and immaterial innovations develops Forsvik into a community that lives, not only through tourists & the touristic season, but also through the local residents & visitors and thereby creates the possibility for the village to live for a longer period thanks to a supportive space for trying out creative ideas, developing the existing space, providing rooms to entrepreneurs & locals & developing transformative tourism.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughtnut Model can we connect my project to?</p> <p>SDGs 1-3, 5, 7, 8-13, 15-16</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? All which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Independent entrepreneurs, municipality & Västra Götalands regionen,</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Lack of creative working & leisure space</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed, which channels are used to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • get in touch with them? • make our solution known? • reach our segments? • make our solution available? <p>Local authorities Local entrepreneurs Social media Word of mouth</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (people and/or technology) required to launch, sustain, scale and run underlying key activities?</p> <p>Established entrepreneurs in the area Blacksmith, Theatre's, craftsmanships events, association</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems?</p> <p>None</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>Crafters Locals Visitors & Tourists Cultural Heritage lovers</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: staff, fixed and variable costs, external services</p>		<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>How is the solution materialised? How does it concretely look like? What are its main features / components?</p> <p>Forsviks Cultural Heritage, Arts & Innovation Centre (CHAICE)</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: renting, pay for use, products</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and agreements guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Non-profit organization</p>		<p>SOCIAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Strengthens local community, influx of entrepreneurs, more sustainable tourism</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p> <p>Non-profit</p>	

■ DESIRABILITY
■ FEASIBILITY
■ VIABILITY
■ SOCIETAL IMPACT

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Prova-Bo long-term rentals Date: 2023 Version: F

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the specified Impact? How is it connected to our position, our drivers? Making it easier to move to the countryside		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How much of them uniquely answer to customers/users/beneficiaries' needs? Our digital platform provides tenants with an easy & safe to rent out experience with legal support. Thanks to our legal & administrative services: provision of materials, information, roadmaps, legal documents/contracts & architectural services: mapping/inventory of spaces for housing & common usage - we help local owners contribute to the local development of their territory with what they have.		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect to our project? SDGs 1-4 & 7-16	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us? House owners Local associations Local authorities		PROBLEMS (needs & needs) Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities? Few options of private rentals are available. Depopulation		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users/beneficiaries/customers developed, which channels are used to? • get in touch with them • reach our segments • make our solution trouble-free Possible new residents House owners Local community	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (people and/or material) required to create value? What are the key activities/underlying key activities? Architectural services in-house, legal & administrative services to be outsourced.		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers/users/beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems? Airbnb focuses on short-term rentals & tourism where money does not go the locals		TARGET SEGMENTS To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers/users/segments? Who are our early adopters? Possible new residents House owners Local community	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: material creation, technical support, legal support, admin costs, staff costs, marketing		SOLUTION How is the solution mobilized? How does it conceptually look like? What are its main features/components? A digital platform giving smaller communities the possibility to welcome new people for short rentals to discover their fantastic place and community.		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring/repeating schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price? Revenue streams: rents, advertisements on the platform.	
GOVERNANCE Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution? Non-profit organization		SOCIAL IMPACTS *** What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and an environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? Social connection, a sense of meaning & belonging that brings mental health. While being close to nature brings the same effect plus physical health.		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits/surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why? Non-profit	

DESIRABILITY
 FEASIBILITY
 VIABILITY
 SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
 MODEL IMPACT CENTER BOULOGNE

 START LAB
 ICHEC

 ICHEC
 FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project : Create, Design & Engage

Date : 2023

Version : F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? Which is our Mission Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our position, our drivers?</p> <p>Development of textile artist exchanges & collaboration, providing inspiring residencies & opportunities to extend routes to market; makers space & digital platform.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our human centered sustainable solution helps textile artists to network & realize their artistry in order to collaborate through digital channels & personal meetings in an inspiring place where history & heritage has a big impact while introducing & making available space & digital tools. Our solution provides also existing audiences/networks the experience of high quality & authentic art in unique spaces through meeting the artists, exploring & participating in creative techniques & brings together past histories & futures in the industrial & rural landscapes of Saltaire & Rydal.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect to our project? To?</p> <p>SDGs 1-5, 8-12</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Municipal museums, International Weaving Center, study association, members of sustainable tourism industry, Trustees, with expertise in cultural policy & education, PR, business innovation, Bradford 2025.</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges, problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Both organizations must apply to a range of project funding pots and & easily to travel between Saltaire & Rydal.</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed? Which channels are used to?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> get in touch with them? reach our segments? make our solution available? <p>Through the network of partners</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (finance and/or non-financial) required to launch and sustain our proposed initiative? Human: financial and non underlying key activities?</p> <p>Project management, digital platform, evaluation, travel/communications to facilitate the partnership</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems?</p> <p>No existing solutions</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Artists in the first instance from UK & Sweden -School education centers -local community our existing audiences and local community networks from both countries 	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: Participation Fees, event travel, concessions, content creation, staff, fixed costs.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS ***</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Reflecting on cultural identity, awareness of natural materials & old technologies, innovative practice & reduced environmental engagement processes, increased in employment/ contracts for freelance artists & arts professionals.</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: grants, ticketing, courses, products, marketing, membership fees.</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Uk/Sweden International partnership</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p> <p>Network development & exchanges</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p>	

DESIRABILITY VIABILITY
FEASIBILITY SOCIAL IMPACT

ICHEC
BUSINESS MANAGEMENT TOOLKIT

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: FRUŠKING 8x4x4

Date: 2023

Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission/ Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our passion, our dreams? The development of cultural tourism in a pioneering & creative approach in choosing the way a tourist travels, explores & organizes their time.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers' / users' / beneficiaries' needs? The solution helps municipalities to solve the problem of concentration in one site and lack of communication & synergistic action towards joint potentials by unifying the whole region using one touristic program which includes cultural institutions, accommodation owners, restaurant owners, wine producers, local produce makers & other interested stakeholders. It also gives tourists unconventional tourist experience & a possibility to create their journey on their own unlike tourist agencies which offer package limited to certain places and pre-selected content.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which states of the Design/ Model can we extract/ try project to?</p> <p>SDGs 1-5 & 8-12</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us? The 3 municipalities, the Fruška Gora National Park, private accommodation owners, restaurant owners, monasteries/wineeries.</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities? Lack of cooperation in the field of cultural tourism or any other field between Irič, Sremski Karlovci & Bač pilot heritage site</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers established? Which channels are used to get in touch with them? reach our segments? make our solution available?</p> <p>Tourism agencies Local authorities Website App Social media</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (people and/or expertise) required to provide our solution? How do we run (organizational, financial, and human resources) and run underlying key activities? The team is composed of artists, creative people, tourist experts, cultural & natural heritage experts, wine producers & others.</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems? Tourist agencies give arrangements with predefined schedules & content</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>(customers / users / beneficiaries)</p> <p>Local & international tourists</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: HR, office expenses, construction works, application creation & development, design & creation of the boxes & the publications, video materials, marketing.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economic and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? The local population will have regular customers for their products. Holiday homes which are used only occasionally, will be reused. Traditional crafts will be revived, there will be an increasing demand for local guides and bike and repair service shops opened. Solution will decrease thanks to the on foot or by bike travelling.</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? Revenue streams: cross-selling, activity-based revenues.</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and aspects that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Non-profit association</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why? Non-profit</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? Revenue streams: cross-selling, activity-based revenues.</p>	

DESIRABILITY
FEASIBILITY

VIABILITY
SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
BUSINESS IMPROVEMENT TOOL

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION
CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Cultural overload - Irig road Date: 2023 Version: F

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star? What's our Qualitative Transformation Purpose (QTP)? What is the expected Impact? How is it connected to our vision, our mission, our values? Unifying tourist & cultural offer in one platform		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the Unique Value Propositions from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives? How much of them uniquely answers to customers / users / beneficiaries needs? Our solution helps tourists explore our destinations by offering routes, information & interesting spots. It also helps residents & cultural associations preserve, collect & better understand their cultural heritage by collecting information, digitizing & storing it in one place & presenting it. Our solution enables hotels, operators, hospitality workers to prolong stay of their guests & make their experience memorable thanks to the user-friendly online application. It also offers companies who look for team building with CSR activities games & activities not available in the area. Finally, it permits policy makers to set up optimal tourist strategy & reallocate limited resources by giving information on most & least popular attractions within current situation where decisions are made based on assumptions & subjective feelings.		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenge does our project address? Which SDGs? Which does the Doughnut Model can we connect my project to? SDGs 1-6 & 8-12 & 14-16	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners? At which level are we collaborating? How are they connected to the problem? How do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us? Hotels, operators, hospitality workers, Policy makers, Cultural associations, companies		PROBLEMS (users & market) Today, what are the challenges, problems faced by users, beneficiaries, stakeholders? How do they contribute to their needs, with opportunities? Lack of integrated tourism offer product		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed, established and maintained? Which channels are used to: • make our solution known? • reach our segments? • make our solution available? Local authorities Local suppliers Website App Social media	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (source and/or monetary) required to achieve the solution (physical, intellectual, human, financial) and the underlying key activities? A team of four experts already working in the hospitality sector & need to involve IT specialists.		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems? Knowledge scattered in several websites		TARGET SEGMENTS (customers / users / beneficiaries) To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users segments? Who are our early adopters? Tourists Residents Companies Hotels	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: staff, fixed and variable costs, external services.		SOLUTION How is the solution materialized? How does it concretely look like? What are its main features / components? A platform of sustainable ecosystems of Irig which connects restaurants, cultural institutions, nature/ecology, & local produce.		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price? Revenue streams: advertising, commissions & subscriptions.	
GOVERNANCE Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, engagement with the collective environment within the collective environment? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution? Limited liability company		SOCIETAL IMPACTS *** What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? Providing work & training to local residents as producers of goods and providers of services. Involvement of ethnic minorities. Promoting nature, healthy lifestyle, healthy local food.		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?	

■ DESIRABILITY
■ FEASIBILITY
■ VIABILITY
■ SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC INTELLECTUAL PROPERTY
START LAB ICHEC
ICHEC FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: BAČ BY TOUCH

Date: 2023

Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What is our Mission? Transformation Purpose (MPT)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our position, our clients?</p> <p>Provide information about the everyday life in medieval times at Bač Fortress.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers' / users' / beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our solution offers past insight & ecological education for tourists, and it teaches students about critical thinking in regard to tourism. It allows tourists to experience many situations they would encounter in medieval life, and which gives them a better outlook about the whole area, & how important it is for it to be preserved and what it used to represent & appreciate the modern times more & ease-of-access thanks to a 3D dynamic audio, characters that will be responsive to a set of questions about the Bač area in the form of multiple-choice dialogue.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect to this project to?</p> <p>SDGs 2-5 & 8-11</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>National & local authorities, hotels, restaurants, tourist organizations, agricultural school, municipal museum, local factory, cultural heritage institutions, etc. houses, NGOs.</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges, pain-points faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Concentration in one site & synergistic action towards joint potentials</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers / users' segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>Digital tourists Digital nomads Village enthusiasts</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the official resources (people, capital, material) required to implement the solution? (Individual, human, financial, and non-financial resources)</p> <p>The development of the website, administration, touch-screen display setup & creation of digital content is insured. The development of Android application will be outsourced.</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems?</p> <p>Concentration in one site & lack of communication & synergistic action towards joint potentials</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: service, ticketing, advertisement</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: staff, fixed and variable costs, external services.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economic and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Inclusion of vulnerable groups, experience tailored for people with reduced sight & reduced mobility. Parts of the display will be from recycled materials, & the website will feature ecologically conscious behavior in addition to job creation.</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and aspects that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Limited liability company</p>		<p>GOVERNANCE</p>		<p>ICHECK FORMATION CONTINUE</p>	

DESIRABILITY
FEASIBILITY

VIABILITY
SOCIAL IMPACT

ICHECK
BUSINESS IMPLEMENTATION TOOLS

START LAB
ICHECK

ICHECK
FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project : Digital Nomads Platform

Date : 2023

Version : F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star ? What's, our Massive Transformation Purpose (MTP) ? What is the expected impact ? How is it connected to our passion, our drivers ?</p> <p>Sustain the process of relocation of digital nomads in Iași & allow them to experience our region according to their lifestyle.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives) ? How each of them uniquely answer to customers / users / beneficiaries needs ?</p> <p>Our collaborative, dynamic platform & forum help digital nomads choose the city of Iași, Romania as a remote work destination. This platform ensures customized access to services & packages, with differentiated and unique offer ranging from basic needs to aspirational ones, matching profiles nomad to destination /experiences. It encourages nomads / remoters / expats to contribute to the well-being of the target communities, learn from its existing innovations & storytell. Unlike passive websites.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address ? Which SDGs ? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect my project to ?</p> <p>SDGs 2-9 & 11-14 & 16</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners ? At which level of the value chain do they connect ? What do they bring that is unique ? Why do they contribute to our success ? What do they expect from us ?</p> <p>Iași City Hall, Iași Destination Management Organization, multinational companies based in Iași, coworking spaces, innovation groups, universities, local associations</p>		<p>PROBLEMS (micro & macro)</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges, problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities ?</p> <p>The Region of Iași has low tourism development, although it has a great potential.</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed, which channels are used to : <ul style="list-style-type: none"> get in touch with them ? make our solution known ? reach our segments ? make our solution available ? </p> <p>Local authorities, Destination Management Organizations, Multinational companies based in Iași Travel agencies Website Social media</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (people, capital, technology) required to create the solution (physical, intellectual, human, financial) and run underlying key activities ?</p> <p>The association will implement & ensure & collaboration. We are travel advisor, IT specialist, destination specialist, communication advisor.</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs, / problems ?</p> <p>Different platforms for nomads / remoters / expats that usually offer information on destination, legislation, accommodation, insured events.</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS (customers / users / beneficiaries)</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value ? What are our customers / users segments ? Who are our early adopters ?</p> <p>Digital nomads (including remoters, expats) and their families</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution ?</p> <p>Costs: staff, fixed and variable costs, external services (site maintenance & hosting).</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS * + *</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution ? From social, economical and environmental perspectives ? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts ?</p> <p>Job creation, better inclusion of expats & immigrants; capitalization of local communities, initiatives, know-how transfer & personal development</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution ? What are the recurring financing schemes ? What are customers ready to pay for & At what price ?</p> <p>Revenue streams: premium users, advertising, commissions, crowdfunding</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and signposts that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective, How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution ?</p> <p>Iași Digital Innovation Hub Association</p>		<p>What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution ? What are they allocated for ? Why ?</p> <p>Non-profit</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p>	

DESIRABILITY
VIABILITY
FEASIBILITY

SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
BUSINESS IMPACTMENT SCHOOL

START LAB
ICHEC

ICHEC
FORMATION CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: **ECoolTour**

Date: **2023**

Version: **F**

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the specified impact? How is it connected to our passion, our drivers? Develop a self-learning AI, which creates patterns & improves them, to be able to adapt a touristic location for a specific user's needs.</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the Unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How much of them uniquely address to customers/users/beneficiaries' needs? ECoolTour helps foreign tourists & other customers create their own route adjusted to their needs on Stephen the Great route in order to reduce the time of modeling the route without intermediaries; center all payments in a single method & create your own journey. This innovative easy-to-use platform generates specific touristic experience based on the preferences of the users. Unlike other aggregation engines, which do not propose desired package solutions, paid by a single check, without generating complementary offer of cultural & natural resources.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we identified in my project? </p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us? Local authorities, Museums, tourist information centers, Travel agencies, Hotels, Heritage sites</p>		<p>PROBLEMS</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, online to their needs, seize opportunities? Under-developed Stephen the Great Route</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are we interacting with users/beneficiaries/customers destinations? Which channels are used to get in touch with them? reach our segments? make our solution available? Local authorities, Tourist information centers, Travel agencies, Mass media, Website, Social media</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (space and/or mandatory) required to launch and run the business? Intellectual, human, financial and run underlying key activities? Experts in tourism & digitalization, but every single user that contributes to the growth of the database, becomes a team member.</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers/users/beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems? Already packaged offer</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers/users segments? Who are our early adopters? International tourists, Students that study outside of Republic of Moldova, Diaspora, Young families</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: staff, fixed and variable costs, external services.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL IMPACTS</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? Job creation, reduce the pressure of intense tourist circuit & revitalization of local products & know-how</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price? Revenue streams: payment for use; in-app services; percentage from in-app sells, subscription; crowdfunding & donations.</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and aspects that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution? Non-profit organization</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUS ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits/surplus generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why? Non-profit</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUS ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits/surplus generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why? Non-profit</p>	

DESIRABILITY
FEASIBILITY

Viability
SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
START LAB
ICHEC
ICHEC
FORMATION
CONTINUE

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: Stephen's route site update

Date: 2023

Version: F

<p>PURPOSE</p> <p>What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission Transformation Purpose (MTP)? What is the intended impact? How is it connected to our position, our drivers?</p> <p>Tourism & heritage protection & development through cross-border partnership</p>		<p>VALUE PROPOSITIONS</p> <p>What are the unique Value Propositions (from functional, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How much of them uniquely answers to customers/users/beneficiaries' needs?</p> <p>Our solution helps tourists who want to participate in a cross-border route to learn about the history of Stephen the Great's personality & create their own digital route by providing necessary information, QRCode panels & a booking application. It also helps touristic attractions on the route who want to be part of a common route to benefit from promotion & upgrade of services by offering them promotional materials, including them in promotional activities, & placing them on platforms (dedicated web site, brochure, identity t-shirts, informational panels, etc.) both from Moldova & Romania.</p>		<p>SOCIETAL CHALLENGES</p> <p>Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect to our project to?</p> <p>SDGs 1, 10, 11 & 12</p>	
<p>KEY PARTNERS</p> <p>Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us?</p> <p>Ministry of Tourism, touristic attractions included in the route, local authorities</p>		<p>PROBLEMS (needs & needs)</p> <p>Today, what are the challenges/problems faced by users, beneficiaries, clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities?</p> <p>Lack of proper road infrastructure, undeveloped touristic attractions, undeveloped services, lack of labor force & promotion</p>		<p>CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL.</p> <p>How are relationships with users/beneficiaries/customers developed, which channels are used to?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> get in touch with them reach our segments make our solution available <p>Tour operators Local public authorities Cultural institutions (museums, fortresses, etc.) Tourist information centers HORECA & wineries representatives Profile associations Guides Website Social media</p>	
<p>RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES</p> <p>What are the critical resources (finance and/or non-finance) required to launch, sustain, scale, improve, industrialize, transfer, (re-)start and run underlying key activities?</p> <p>A team of communication, design promotional materials, grants/fundraising experts</p>		<p>SOLUTION</p> <p>How is the solution mobilized? How does it conceptually look like?</p> <p>What are its main features/components?</p> <p>A digital platform that connects tourist attractions from two countries with a common heritage</p>		<p>TARGET SEGMENTS (Customers/users/beneficiaries)</p> <p>To whom does our solution create value? What are our customers/users/segments? Who are our early adopters?</p> <p>Families Tourists Seniors Students</p>	
<p>COST STRUCTURE</p> <p>What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution?</p> <p>Costs: Staff, fixed and variable costs, external services (website maintenance, hosting & update, promotional materials and services).</p>		<p>EXISTING SOLUTIONS</p> <p>Today, how do customers/users/beneficiaries answer to their needs/problems?</p> <p>Self-search of needed information from various platforms & tools</p>		<p>REVENUE STREAMS</p> <p>What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring/reaching schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price?</p> <p>Revenue streams: Copyright royalties, governmental funding & subsidies</p>	
<p>GOVERNANCE</p> <p>Which principles and approach that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment, within the collective? How are stakeholders integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution?</p> <p>Non-profit organisation</p>		<p>SOCIAL IMPACTS ***</p> <p>What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and an environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts?</p> <p>Develop the rural area, build competences in the tourism sector, create jobs, diversify the touristic product & promote cross-border collaboration</p>		<p>PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION</p> <p>What are the allocation principles for profits/surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why?</p> <p>Non-profit</p>	

■ DESIRABILITY
■ FEASIBILITY
■ VIABILITY
■ SOCIETAL IMPACT

SOCIETAL IMPACT CANVAS

Project: The Bison Land's Heritage

Date: 2023

Version: F

PURPOSE What is our guiding North Star? What's our Mission/ Transformation Purpose (MPT)? What is the expected impact? How is it connected to our position, our drivers? Offer a unique experience for the tourists of the Bison Land, trying to combine in a holistic way certain natural, cultural & spiritual features of the area.		VALUE PROPOSITIONS What are the Unique Value Propositions (from business, societal and/or environmental perspectives)? How each of them uniquely answers to customers' / users' / beneficiaries' needs? Our solution enables families with children to explore & connect with the cultural, spiritual, natural heritage by finding specific activities for children & testing traditional products. It incentivizes school children improve their knowledge about nature & the environment by participating in thematic experiences according to their field of interest. It also helps companies discover alternative experiences to learn about culinary traditions & have a better knowledge of the area by discovering interesting thematic routes, participating in gastronomic presentation & stimulating an active lifestyle. Unlike choosing from classic tourism or shortening the stay period.		SOCIETAL CHALLENGES Which societal challenges does our project address? Which SDGs? Which stakeholders of the Doughnut Model can we connect? My project is to: SDGs 1-4 & 8-13	
KEY PARTNERS Who are our main partners? At which level of the value chain do they connect? What do they bring that is unique? Why do they contribute to our success? What do they expect from us? Guest houses, local producers, local craftsmen, tourist guides, local authorities		PROBLEMS (Context & internal) Today, what are the challenges? What are the main problems? Clients to meet their objectives, answer to their needs, seize opportunities? Bad touristic infrastructure, no traditional food in restaurants, lack of information, crowded periods during summer & religious feasts, no alternatives to "classic" walking in the forest.		CHANNELS & CUSTOMER REL. How are relationships with users / beneficiaries / customers developed, which channels are required to reach our segments? • get in touch with them? • make our solution known? • reach our segments? • make our solution available? Local authorities Guesthouse owners Our website Websites of our partners	
RESOURCES & ACTIVITIES What are the critical resources (finance and/or mandatory) required to launch and run the project? In which way are they used? What are the underlying key activities? Design & interpretation of the pathways, local events organization.		EXISTING SOLUTIONS Today, how do customers / users / beneficiaries answer to their needs / problems? Classic walking in the forest & zoo		TARGET SEGMENTS (customers / users / beneficiaries) To which does our solution create value? What are our segments? / our segments? Who are our early adopters? Families with kids Companies Schoolchildren groups	
COST STRUCTURE What are the main fixed and variable costs of our solution? Costs: Staff, fixed and variable costs, external services (pathways network, ecotourist infrastructure, &, treasure hunt application).		SOLUTION How is the solution materialized? How does it conceptually look like? What are its main features / components? A network of holistic interpreted pathways & treasure hunt application which will allow an educational environment & feedback		REVENUE STREAMS What are the main revenue streams generated by our solution? What are the recurring financing schemes? What are customers ready to pay for? At what price? Revenue streams: ticketing, advertising, in-app services.	
GOVERNANCE Which principles and approaches that guide decision making, responsibilities / power sharing & distribution, empowerment within the collective? Have one stakeholder integrated in the governance, the implementation and the evolution of the solution? Non-profit organization		SOCIETAL IMPACTS *** What are the negative and positive impacts of our solution? From social, economical and environmental perspectives? Which indicators do we use to evaluate these impacts? Reduction of tourism pressure in crowded areas & reinvigorate the local economy.		PROFITS & SURPLUSES ALLOCATION What are the allocation principles for profits / surpluses generated by the solution? What are they allocated for? Why? Non-profit	

DESIRABILITY
 FEASIBILITY
 VIABILITY
 SOCIETAL IMPACT

ICHEC
 (BISON LAND'S HERITAGE)

START LAB
 ICHEC

ICHEC
 FORMATION
 CONTINUE

4.2 Business plan

During part I of the fourth acceleration session, the 19 teams were introduced to Be.CULTOUR Business Plan, and they all received a template to use during the dry-run and the final pitch. The template included the 9 vital features for a successful pitch, namely:

1. Executive Summary
2. Your North Star / Massive Transformative Purpose
3. Needs addressed
4. Offer and unique value propositions
5. Operating model
6. Financial model
7. Organization : Team & governance
8. Societal impacts
9. How do you « make » your future ?

Executive Summary

The executive summary is **a compendium of the business plan**. It was explained to participants that it represents the “business card” of their project. It puts forward thus, the key points / most important elements of the project so that potential investors can quickly get an overall idea of what is at stake. The 19 teams were advised to complete their executive summary, after having finished writing their entire business plan.

Moreover, a few hints were also provided to help them develop a good executive summary:

- write 1 to 2 pages maximum;
- multiply the number of paragraphs with one key point each;
- use style tools to highlight important elements - bold, underlined, etc;
- include a graph or table to make it easier to summarize an idea;
- avoid using overly technical jargon in the executive summary.

Finally, the 19 teams were advised to pay particular attention to the following:

- Introduce the product or service in a complete and concise way ;
- Write a user-friendly text and avoid too much technical detail at this stage;
- Present the founding members, their experience, their background
- Specify their market, its trends, the segments they are targeting, the competition, and do so objectively;

- Emphasize what will make the difference and how it will be economically viable;
- Clarify what they are asking for investors.

Your North Star / Massive Transformative Purpose

- What's the mission, raison d'être of your project ?
- What's your Massive Transformation Purpose ?

In other words, a few qualitative statements describing why the project exists, what the group wants to achieve and where they want to go.

Needs addressed

The 19 teams were asked to introduce needs / stakes that the project addresses including key figures illustrating the size of the challenge at macro and micro levels.

At macro level

- Which SDG/Doughnut economy/circular economy related stakes issues do they target?

At micro level

- Who are the target segments (customers / users / beneficiaries) ?
- What are the key needs / expectations / pain points ?
- What is the potential size of each segment ?
 - TAM : Total Addressable Market -> total market demand for the product/service/solution proposed
 - SAM : Serviceable Addressable Market -> segment of the TAM targeted by the product/service/solution
 - SOM : Serviceable Obtainable Market -> portion of the SAM that you can capture

Your Offer and its unique value propositions

The 19 teams were encouraged to:

1. **Describe in detail the solution** (product/service) and its various concrete components (5-7 features max and/or a storyboard describing the user / beneficiary / customer journey)
2. **Competing solutions / alternatives** : introduce other actors tackling the same problem, addressing the same segments either with a similar proposal (direct competitors) or a very different proposal (indirect competitors)

3. **Explain how the project is innovative, circular, human-centered and different** from existing solutions in other words what are the specificities that differentiate their offer from existing alternatives. Therefore, describe ONE value proposition for each target segment of stakeholders (not only the customer but also local communities, the territory from environmental, social and economic perspectives)
 - What's the underlying magic ?
 - What is the differentiating value proposition that cannot be found now or elsewhere ?
 - Why is it the right moment ? Why now ?
4. **List key prospects** by segment with a short description of each of them and the elements of the solution that may interest them.

Operating model

For the operating model, the 19 teams were invited to address two aspects:

1. Critical competencies and resources that must be activated both internal and external:
 - Tangible resources (equipment, real estate, raw material, intermediates, software, etc...)
 - Intangible resources (branding, processes, immaterial value, etc...)
 - Human resources (owning skills, competencies, know how, etc...)
2. Marketing strategy
 - Channels used to reach customer/user segments throughout their journey (from knowing offer existence to its use and reuse)
 - Marketing / Communication plan

Finally, the teams were invited to share their stage of progress and any achievements so far. In other words, they were encouraged to describe whether they have tested their product/service and with whom? How did they test it? What were the results/feedback from this test? And What do they still need to do?

Financial model

For the financial model, the teams were invited to run realistic calculations aimed at achieving their project's economic viability. Therefore, they were asked to calculate:

- Revenue streams: revenues generated by product / service sales ; prices at which the product / service will be offered / Revenue model proposed / Expected revenue streams

- Funding models: which funding sources are considered in order to cover costs & expenses?
- Cost structure: required for implementation of the solution: now and tomorrow. Fixed costs; variable costs, remuneration model of teammates
- Investments : which activities require important investments ? Which amortization rules are applied ?
- Budget forecast: for the coming 3 years (profit & loss account) : Draw up the budget forecast for the next 3 years (expenses vs. income), separating operating & investment expenses

Organization : Team and governance

The 19 teams were invited to reflect and agree upon the following:

- Legal form: specify the legal status of the project according to the activity developed, its business model and the desired governance.
- Human resources
 - Human capital: team's skills, experience, roles, entrepreneurial potential
 - Ways of working : How they fit together, and complement each other so that project success will be ensured on the long run ; how critical roles are distributed and endorsed.
 - Resource people that are / will be mobilized (e.g. specific expertise, volunteering, etc.) with a description of the skills/knowledge/experience sought.
- Internal and external governance: Specify the internal and external governance models that will be implemented (from which stems the distribution of power, stakeholder engagement; local communities' empowerment; human rights respect coordination process, etc.)

Societal impacts

The teams were asked to adopt the theory of change framework and therefore, describe the overall positive transformational changes that the project will generate.

How do you « make » your future?

Finally, the teams were asked to describe the project's roadmap for the weeks, months and 3 years to come in terms of:

- Financial and non-financial (aka Impact) objectives in 3 years
- Strategic axes (aka Value Streams)
- Intermediate objectives for years 1 & 2 (Key results) that will pave the way for each Value / Work stream
- Quarterly milestones for each value stream activated in year 1
- The most critical challenges / risks to be worked out (anticipation, mitigation)? (If not addressed, the project might be in big trouble) ?

Disclaimer:

During the acceleration training, several teammates were not attending the sessions which made it difficult for some groups to advance. Moreover, although ICHEC's team provided a template for the Business Plan (BP), encompassing the 9 vital features described in this part of the deliverable (4.2 Business Plan) Pp 66-70, it was not fully completed/used/adopted by all the 19 teams.

Groups business plans:

Cammino Lucano in Vulture	71
Triple L tourism: Leave, Learn, Live	76
Fly On Tour Immersivo	80
Eco glamping under the stars	83
AridScape The wide as heritage	87
La chica cabeza de bosque	92
Sensory Bee Nature Trail	96
Needle festival	104
Kalosorisete	110
Forsviks CHAICE	116
Prova-Bo long-term rentals	121
Create, Design & Engage	127
FRUŠKING 8x4x4	134
Cultural overload - Irig road	140
BAČ BY TOUCH	144
Digital Nomads Platform	149
ECoolTour	156
Stephen's route site update	162
The Bison Land's Heritage	168

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Cammino Lucano del Vulture
**Vulture-Alto Bradano area,
Basilicata Region, Italy**

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

We want to build a new touristic trail in Vulture. There are a lot of cultural sites unknown and Cammino Lucano wants to value and promote an itinerary to visit them, to create and optimize the touristic offer

- 1.1: Connect the pilot area with more developed heritage sites in Basilicata
- 1.2: Valorise Aglianico wine - Digital Center for creative storytelling
- 1.3: Gaming & immersive heritage experience attracting new targets
- 2.1: European Heritage Label "the places of Federico II" in Melfi and surroundings
- 2.2: Routes & micro-routes linked to Federico II heritage sites

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The *Cammino Lucano del Vulture* area in each of the stages: Melfi, Rapolla, Barile, Rionero in Vulture, Ginestra, Ripacandida, Atella and San Fele. There will be first of all a proposal of that we can define as a regional naturalistic spiritual path. The experiential journey that the customer undertakes before embarking on the *Cammino Lucano del Vulture* is the result of his interaction with the various touchpoints, such as websites, social networks, word of mouth, or any other place or physical or virtual event in which a potential customer comes into contact with the Cammino Lucano, while looking for information or walking through the Vulture area.

key prospects by segment:

Naturalist walkers and bikers: Monte Vulture and Monticchio lakes

Religious and spiritual people will find churches dedicated to Santa Maria di Costantinopoli

Wine and food tourist can taste the DOCG Aglianico red wine

Experience tourist will live in contact with local community

Astronomical enthusiast will discover the connection between pleiades and churches

Our targets can see, feel and hear a full immersion in the nature, satisfy spiritual needs, taste the traditional flavors, live the

habits and traditions of the local community, observe the connection between the stars and elements on the path. One can hieve personal growth while the local community engage with newcomers.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The Cammino Lucano del Vulture The inspiring motif is also linked to the celebration of the vital energy of nature, in one of the most fascinating territories of Basilicata, embellished with astronomical and mythological references that prophesy a new myth: the Lucanian aurora. The perceived difference in nature and personality of the people had a greater impact than the project itself.

All these pearls are linked by an invisible thread, a new spiritual naturalistic path to discover the evocative landscape of the Lucanian soul. Users perceived the interactions with the Pleiades constellation, as inspiring and stimulating break with the daily routines.

Unlike the alternatives offered , the Cammino Lucano in Vulture is able to offer an innovative tourist experience because the territory covered by the project is affected by a celestial connection linked to the monks, which used and knew about archeo-astronomy. Effects on the people: increase cognitive level, reflection and divergent thinking, related intensified.

It is it the right moment because the traces of this fascinating past are still there, thanks to the centuries-old

cult that has characterized our region and which still continue today, as a tradition. The 2025 Jubilee also opens up an unmissable opportunity for cultural touristic development in Basilicata.

Competing solutions / alternatives : <https://camminomaterano.it/>
<https://www.coe.int/it/web/cultural-routes/the-phoenicians-route>

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

Revenues	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Revenue Stream 1	7 (association card)	50	100
Revenue Stream 2	0	0	0
Revenue Stream 3	0	0	0
Total Revenues	35	250	500
Fundings	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Funding 1	500 (Public subvention)	0	0
Funding 2	0	500 (supplemental contribution)	0
Funding 3	0	0	3000 (Private Mobilization)
Total fundings	5000	5000	3000
Incoming Flows - IN	5000	5000	3000
Structure de coûts	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Fixed Costs	2000	2000	1200
Variable Costs	3000	3000	1800
Investments incl Amortization			
Outgoing Flows - OUT	5000	5000	3000
Results (& In-Out)	5000	5000	3000

ICHEC BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

Be.CULTOUR Beyond cultural tourism

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (Offer type + target segment)	Price / unit	Nbr of clients / sales per year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Revenue stream 1	5	7-50-100	35	250	500
Revenue stream 2					
Revenue stream 3					
Revenue stream 4					
Total Revenues			35	250	500
Fundings	Product / Service / Activity funded		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Funding 1	Public subvention		5000		
Funding 2	Supplemental contribution			5000	
Funding 3	Private mobilization				3000
Funding 4					
Total Fundings			5000	5000	3000
Total Incoming Flows			5000	5000	3000

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs	Unit cost + quantities		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Equipement, outfit, furnitures,...	Pc, camera	1800	*	*	*
Energy, Water, Raw Material	Path-street sign (signage)	*	1800	800	
External services	Video maker, site administration, administrative and tax consultancy	1000	850	450	
Real Estate (rental of offices, warehouses / storage places,...)	Transport, food and lodging	200	350	950	
Total variable costs			3000	3000	1800
Fixed costs	Unit cost + quantities		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Internal staff	Conception and development, blog, SMM	750	750	750	450
External staff	Video maker, site administration and tax consultancy	1150	1050	250	
Recurring expenses (admin, insurances, energy, telecom,...)	Admin, insurance	100	300	500	
Total fixed costs			2000	2000	1200
Investments	Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Investment 1			5000		
Investment 2				5000	
Investment 3					3000
Total investments			5000	5000	3000
Total Outgoing Flows			5000	5000	3000

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** Il Cammino Lucano del Vulture, is a Cultural Association.
- **Human resources**
- **Human capital:** Historical researcher, Walkers, Project Manager, SMM, Photographer, Innovator, Author of an Artistic path
- **Ways of working :** It is living on what we love
- **Resource people** that are / will be mobilized: Astronomy expert, Mayors, Orthodox church referents, multimedia performance expert
- **Internal and external governance :** The governance is managed by the President of the Cultural Association, the Founder of Cammino Lucano del Vulture, in support & supervision of the project; where it is important that future associates do not limit themselves to "the homework" but feel an integral part of the production process; it is even more important in our Association, where the economic & investment availability is reduced by limited funding and therefore it is vital that every resource used is directed in the right way.

*The intent is to train precise skilled & specialized professional figures in the field of religious naturalistic and cultural tourism, which has so far been generally neglected. Profiles: guides in sacred art, experts in symbolic theology & environmental guide through art; responsible for sacred art & ecclesial cultural heritage; responsible for the protection & enhancement of the artistic assets of the territory, as well as the landscape assets in the formulation of the naturalistic cultural itinerary; environmental guides, tour leaders, animators of the itinerary & qualified artistic itineraries; cultural & religious tourism operators; organizers of cultural events.

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Contact the Municipalities Contact the Regional Vulture Park	Preparation of the intervention support sheet	Initiate calls and set up meetings if it is possible	#9 Mayors and Tourism Councilors support the project.	The park authority is interested	Creation of a network between #8 various local administration	Activate team synergies and contribute to the common success of the Cammino Lucano
Contact the local Lucano del associations and the Pro-Loco	Initiate calls and set up meeting if it is possible #13 Associations	To present the project and understand if they support the Cammino #11 carry on	Understand the area of common interest to grow together #10 carry on	Overcome local rivalries and unite the different association in a common project	To work for the common good of the Vulture area #8 carry on	#7 Associations work together
Gather volunteers	A pool of #7 volunteers is ready	Explore the #8 Municipalities: Melfi, Rapolla, Barile, Ginestra, Ripacandide, Rionero, Atella, San Fele	path is tested #17km, state of the art of the #8 places object of the intervention.	Carry on with the test in the area Vulture - Alto Bradano, other #17km are tested	#50 new associates and #50km are completely verify the provincial	#70 new associates and #70km tested are providing where is it possible one more
Increase visibility and attractivity of the project	#1% of the community is engaged as ambassador	Marketing strategy is established	First marketing actions are ready to be implemented	#Launch the website	#Launch the Cammino Lucano del Vulture Video	Pool of ambassadors are augmented to #7%
Organize the project.	A recruitment campaign is conducted to attract early adopters	#7 people are available to go to the Cammino with a bus in a day shot	Cause the Winter no one want to walk so we repeat the cultural event with a bus	Way of working governance, strategy are designed & we move to test with #17 people #34 km in 2-days	#500 local tourist are involved in Vulture area cause the Cammino Lucano	#5000 local and international tourist come to the Vulture area

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

TRIPLE L TOURISM: LEAVE, LEARN, LIVE Vulture, Basilicata Region

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

MISSION

Development of Vulture rural area by circular and sustainable tourism

PURPOSE

Fighting the depopulation and lack of innovation of Vulture rural area

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Our solution aims to activate cultural exchanges for students from all around EU and from different knowledge fields

- Students will design solutions for the urban regeneration and the sustainable development of Vulture, focusing in particular on cultural tourism
- Not just tourist, students are (temporary) residents = HUMAN-CENTERED
- Events and activities will be part of the experience in partnership with local associations

- | | | | | |
|---|---|--|---|--|
| 1. Students become aware of the project | 2. They get in touch with Basilicata university or other partners to get more infos | 3. Students choose the thematic area in which develop their own projects | 4. Students organize the travel and are welcomed by the local community | 5. Students develop their own sustainable solutions (learning by doing approach) |
|---|---|--|---|--|

USER JOURNEY

Competing solutions / alternatives: Erasmus + projects (addressing same segments) with different proposals (rural areas)

Why now?: PNRR funds target the cultural regeneration of rural areas (eg. Italian "borghi"), so projects such as the creation of a creative hub could be easily funded

Students may be interested in...

1. The unique opportunity of **starting from scratch** in developing projects regarding sustainable development and tourism (SDG Agenda 2030)
2. Living the experience of **living in the rural**
3. The possibility of create something concrete and not just a strictly academic study

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

Revenues	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Rent of coworking places	-	-	4.350,00
Events	5.000,00	5.000,00	8.000,00
Meetings	3.000,00	3.000,00	4.000,00
Total Revenues	8.000,00	8.000,00	16.350,00
Fundings	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Region + Univeristy	6.000,00	18.000,00	18.000,00
Municipalities + PNRR funds	-	200.000,00	300.000,00
Sponsorships	3.000,00	3.000,00	3.000,00
Total fundings	9.000,00	221.000,00	321.000,00
Incoming Flows - IN	17.000,00	229.000,00	337.350,00
Structure de coûts	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Fixed Costs	12.000,00	22.000,00	22.000,00
Variable Costs	-	-	5.800,00
Investments incl Amortization	-	200.000,00	300.000,00
Outgoing Flows - OUT	12.000,00	222.000,00	327.800,00
Results (Δ In-Out)	5.000,00	7.000,00	9.550,00

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

Permanent **Grop** project with...

- P/A partners:
 - Basilicata Region;
 - APT Basilicata;
 - Local Municipalities;
- Foundations (partnerships);
- Basilicata University;
- Professional and trade associations

Regular meetings (1/month)

A various and flexible team work

The **project coordinator** will manage to exploit every specific professional according to the evolving situation with a problem-solving approach.

The team will have:

- journey manager
- accomodation manager
- one tutor for each research field

We set up an University spin-off

(since the project is replicable in other rural areas)

PROJECT MANAGEMENT

Young profesionists with trasversal skills in:

- circular tourism management;
- sustainable architecture;
- economics;
- territorial and eviormental sociology;
- rural and urban areas history and development;
- territorial marketing.

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Meetings and partnerships with local stakeholders	X	X				
Resources and findings individuation			X			
Pilot: 15 days in Basilicata Region.				X		
Beginning of 6 months exchange in Basilicata Region					X	
Beginning of the requalification of the HUB						X

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Fly On Tour Immersivo
**Vulture-Alto Bradano area,
Basilicata Region, Italy**

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

Offering accessible tourism experiences that embrace inclusion and social values so that it reduces architectural & physical barriers.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Fly On immersive tour for all!

Young people can learn about and be active protagonists of an alternative cultural activity thanks to a unique storytelling ('story collection in flight') a tour guide who tells you aseptic and repeated information, where the tourist is passive.

Real-time immersive tours, uses visors and drones, to visit a place rich in history and culture and where each guest is connected in real time via the visors to the drone's cameras.

key prospects by segment:

- Young people (18-35)
- Educational institutions (public and private)
- People with intellectual disabilities & foreign also visitors

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (Offer type + target segment)	Price / unit	Nbr of clients / sales per year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Full ticket	15 Euros	4000 people	60.000		
Ticket (disabled frail persons)	8 Euros	720 people	5.760		
Ticket (school/students)	6 Euros	500 people	3.000		
Ticket (associations)	5 Euros	500 people	2.500		
Ticket (public entities)	7 Euros	1500 Euro	81.760		
		Y1 10.500	Total Revenues		
Fundings	Product / Service / Activity funded		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Puglia Region Funding	Equipment (Drones, visors, merchandising)		10.000		
Puglia Region Funding	Services (website, company establishment and management)		20.000		
			Total Fundings	30.000	
			Total Incoming Flows	111.760	

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs	Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Equipment, outfit, furnitures,...	2 drone and 7 visors (Drone 1500, visor 600)	7200€			
energy, water, raw material	6 - battery drone / 12 - batteria visor / 2 battery charger / 1 pc laptop / 1 - power bench / 1 - sound box (€ 30.00 - battery drone / € 25.00 - batteria visor / € 100.00 battery charger / € 1500.00 pc laptop / € 1500 - power bench / € 500 - sound box)	4180€			
External services	accountant	1500€			
Total variable costs		12.880€			
Fixed costs	Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Internal staff	2 employees (2000 Euro/month)	48000€			
External staff					
Recurring expenses (admin, insurances, energy, telecom,...)	1 drone insurance	600€			
Total fixed costs		54.000€			
Investments	Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Drones and drones batteries	1700€		1700€		
Transportation mean	20000€		12.000€		
Total investments			15.000€		
Total Outgoing Flows			85.880€		

**TOUR FLY VIEW
UN VOLO IN PRIMA
PERSONA**

**TECNOLOGIA
4.0**

**PENSATO PER
VISITARE LUOGHI
INACCESSIBILI**

**UN TOUR IDEATO
PER TUTTI**

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Ecoglamping under the Stars Teruel (Spain)

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

- *Mision: We want to create a new kind of tourism in our region, connect to the nature, to the stars and to symplicity.*
- *What's your **Massive Transformation Purpose** ?*

We want to offer something different, we dont want the tourist to drive through our region, we want them to stay a night with us.

We are trying to offer something different connect to our terrytory were our limitations turns into opportunities.

Ex. If we dont have good internet connections or good TV signal we dont put a big screen of TV in our rooms and we do different nights.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

- 1. Describe in detail the solution.** Huts or dommes that are your house, special night watching the stars through a glass ceiling, friendly dinner around the fire and 100% connection to nature.
- 2. Competing solutions / alternatives:** Tourism activities in the region are our allies (museum, cultural park, paths, are part of the offer during the day while we operate during the night). We need them as a part of our package. They do the day activities and we do night ones.
- 3. Explain how the project is innovative, circular, human-centered and different.** Very few of us have slept under a glass ceiling watching the stars, very few of us cook a dinner on real fire (feeling the heat, smelling the food and cooking ourselves), and the food is from our local suppliers (no supermarket food welcome).
 - What's the underlying magic ? Feelings, experience and nature confort
 - What is the differentiating value proposition that cannot be found now or elsewhere ? Glass ceiling, local food, dinner around a fire
 - Why is it the right moment ? Why now ? All year around...More people taht live in big cities taht they want to scape from noisy and crowded places.
- 4. List key prospects ;** Stars, fire, silence, no traffic, nature sounds, slow food, eco food, a glass of wine in a hammac watching the stars...no TV, no high wifi.

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

Revenues	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Rooms + accomodation	197.100 €	217.303 €	264.133 €
Food & Beverage	54.750 €	60.362 €	73.370 €
Tours & sales	8.000 €	8.820 €	10.721 €
Total Revenues	259.850 €	286.485 €	315.849 €
Fundings	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Funding 1			
Funding 2			
Funding 3			
Total fundings			
Incoming Flows - IN	259.850 €	286.485 €	315.849 €
Structure de coûts	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Fixed Costs	50.000€	52.500 €	55.125 €
Variable Costs	93.000 €	97.650 €	102.533€
Investments incl Amortization	178.500 €	178.500 €	178.500 €
Outgoing Flows - OUT	321.500 €	328.650 €	336.158 €
Results (Δ In-Out)	-61.650 €	-42.165 €	-20.308 €

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** 80-100% Investment made by local municipality. Its the owner of the space + activity. Administrative concession for several years (10 at the beginning for two workers..couple that want to manage the business.
- **Human resources**
 - Human capital: 2 people (better a couple) Involve with the territory, eco skills, basic chef and very friendly
 - Ways of working : They live in the place (a private house is made for them...not a room, a hut for living 60 m2). They will work around 150 days to 300 per year). They organize themselves. When no tourist, place close.
 - Resource people: They can be from abroad (out of territory) they need to get use to be in the place. Is their job, their house, their filosophy and they way of living. Very important this 2 workers for the succed of the place.
- **Internal and external governance :**The local autorithy (owner of the place) will be involve and help with the operation. Important that thay recieve support and help from other places (

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Find the correct workers	Help them to integrate	Make them feel confi	Supervision of activities	Look for new incomes (tours, selling agro products)	Carry on with same workers or change	Same
Design products for families	Check this products	Feed back from users	Fun activities	Try no t annoy other guests (noise)	More promotion and feed back	Same
Design product for couples	Check this products	Feed back from users	Special romantic details	Special days offers (Anniversary, Sain Valentine)	More promotion and feed back	Same
Design product for small groups (-18)	In low occupancy	We might fit offers and activities			More promotion and feed back	Same

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Aridscape

The cultural park of Rio Martin, Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We think **to be where resources are** is the best way to conserve and promote landscape & cultural heritage. We are experts in conservation & renovation of architectural heritage and drought tolerant plants garden design. So this rural area is the best location for our work. But **we need people**. We actually think the countryside needs **high quality jobs** to be attractive to live for **young & talented people**.

We want them to bring to this area to work as architects & landscape architects **living on the villages for a long term** while they are learning working & by the **workshops** planned by the environmental organization about traditional materials and building techniques as well as mediterranean native plants.

The difference between us & other architecture office is the **knowledge & the location**. We are on the countryside to be close to the **resources we want to preserve** and promote. But also, our innovative idea that makes the difference is the link with **SOCIAL** bringing **young talent** not only for them to learn but to **preserve services** & improve the **social links** between locals – most of them elder people – and foreigners.

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

- To be where resources are. Architecture & Landscape Office on the rural area.
Team master in landscape solutions and renovation of architectural heritage.
- To bring young talent to the rural area.
Long timeframe living on villages – Internships - ERASMUS+
- To increase the amount of houses for rent.
- Traditional heritage and landscape preservation.
Starting with the project headquarters.
Renovating a vernacular house
- Dissemination of Traditional Techniques in architecture.
High quality internships and training.
Workshops renovating private and public heritage buildings.
- Dissemination of Native and Drought tolerant plants and landscapes.
Workshops and own professional projects in the office.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

INNOVATION

We offer high quality work in a rural area *Why you couldn't work as an architect or landscape architect on the countryside?*

We provide **accommodation** at the same time.

We offer a **high quality internship** and **workshops** about traditional techniques & materials & drought tolerant plants.

NOW IS THE MOMENT TO LEARN ABOUT THIS DUE TO CLIMATE CHANGE IN EUROPE

Young people in the villages for long periods of time. This will help to keep and improve services.

High knowledge and procedures to preserve the environment, natural landscape & urban landscape. **WE ARE HERE**

To earn money giving a second life to their empty houses.

New social connections YOUNG - ELDER

A NEW ENVIRONMENTAL ORGANIZATION

European trainees

Municipalities

Local people

5. OPERATING MODEL

Operating model

Critical competencies and resources that must be activated

- Headquarters: **renovation** (including equipments)
- **New website**
 - Projects
 - Availability of houses for rent.
 - Our story - Our team
 - **THE PROJECT** - One section with the progress of the project.
 - Contact
- Human resources: Our team & **trainees**
- Availability of **houses for rent** from local people

Marketing strategy

- **Social media** → Website
- **ERASMUS+** program
- **Consultancy**
- **Architecture contests**
- **ERASMUS+** program
- **Professional projects.**
Gardening & buildings renovation.
- **Talking.**
- **Social media** → Website

We already have our brand

European trainees

Municipalities

Local people

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

Financial model

Revenues	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Architecture & Landscape projects	23.661	50.000	150.000
Private clients	2.000	12.000	24.000
Workshops	0	3.000	10.800
Total Revenues	25.661	75.000	184.800
Fundings	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Private companies related with the project & workshops	20.000	40.000	20.000
Public	7.000	10.000	20.000
Total fundings	27.000	50.000	40.000
Incoming Flows - IN	52.661	125.000	224.000
Costs structure	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Fixed Costs	18.000	20.000	15.000
Variable Costs	15.000	18.000	20.000
Investments incl Amortization	19.000	66.000	116.000
Outgoing Flows - OUT	52.000	104.000	151.000
Results (Δ In-Out)	661	21.000	73.000

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

Organization: Team & governance

Legal form

- Nowadays we are all self employed people collaborating together. But we're planing to create a Limited Partnership.

Human resources

- We are 4 people working on distance & two people working on territory.
 - We have more than 9 years experience working in Cultural Heritage and Landscape projects. **Architect | Engineer | Business manager | Tourism manager**
- We need more people to work with us but we want to take advantage on it bringing people to Spain & the entire Europe through Erasmus+ programs & internships. They will also be our human resources but benefiting the rest of society living on the village.
- We will ask for people with high skills: architects, landscape architects, engineers & also business managers.

Internal & external governance

- Local communities. They are going to participate as part of the project offering their empty homes in perfect condition to trainees in exchange for an agreed rent.
- Trainees are an essential part on the company. They represent the social part coming from abroad to live for a long time in the village. So, until they won't be here the project won't have started and we will be just another architecture studio, but in a rural environment.

Team leaders

Ismael Pizarro
Project leader
Architect &
Landscape Architect

50%

Paz González

25%

Business manager

Sergio Jurado

15%

Tourism manager

Raúl Melones

10%

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS / THEORY OF CHANGE

Societal impacts

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Future

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Architecture & Landscape architecture office					Continuing in a rented place / Renovating part of the ancient house to be the office headquarters.	Renovating part of the ancient house to be the office headquarters.
Workshops	Step 1				Step 2	
Finding professional projects		• We are already working on it and it's going on				
Creating the website & Marketing strategy						
Finding Financial support		• CRITICAL RISK. We need at least 80.000 € to develop the entire project.				
Accommodation			• CRITICAL RISK. We need to checked it in other villages and municipalities			
Creating a student's training program						
Comming trainees from abroad			• CRITICAL RISK. We already know there are many people interested to come but we have to check if the procedure will work & if they'll be ok here			

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

La chica cabeza de bosque

**The cultural park of Rio Martin,
Teruel province, Aragon region, Spain**

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

La chica cabeza de bosque is a creative and personal growth project that works with dye plants to get to know and connect with the nature that surrounds us. Through our activities people develop their artistic and creative abilities, discover the treasures hidden in the dye plants and have the opportunity to observe themselves internally thanks to an integral accompaniment.

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

To create experiences, from an artistic and therapeutic point of view, generating a positive impact on the environment and showing that a change in our consumption habits is possible.

TRANSVERSAL AXIS

People, with their concerns, curiosity and desire to learn new artistic techniques:

1. *Work with dye plants to learn about and connect with the nature that surrounds us.*
2. *People develop their artistic and creative skills, discover the treasures hidden in dye plants and have the opportunity to observe themselves internally with an integral accompaniment.*
3. *Promotion of the circular and service economy*
4. *Call to action, towards a public that feels and respects nature and its benefits*
5. *We exist out of curiosity and the need to look for simpler and more functional ways of living.*

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Our differentiating value proposition is that: 1 We transmit excitement and surprise in any of our target segments. 2 We put caring for people & the planet at the forefront in a practical and didactic way. 3 We connect people with nature & make them participants in this knowledge through the action of creating. Keywords: Proximity, recovery of forgotten knowledge, sustainability, self-care

EXPERIENCE WORKSHOPS: Spaces for training & development of creativity in which personal growth through action is integrated. Knowledge about natural dyeing techniques & local botany is shared with the participants. Train travel is encouraged as much as possible, to reach the workshops to reduce the carbon footprint. Synergies are sought with other similar business proposals to promote local businesses and the social and solidarity economy.

TEXTILE HANDICRAFT PRODUCTS: Creation of garments & accessories from recovered or fair-trade fabrics & certified ecologically certified fabrics.

-Local suppliers or donations. Sales at local markets & fairs.

PERSONALISED GIFTS: "Flowers to remember": Bouquets of flowers that represent special moments in life are transformed into everlasting elements. Locally made in fair trade silk. The work process is shared with the clientele to make it feel & more personal.

ORDERS FOR SEAMSTRESSES: Customized dyeing service, with fair trade fabrics, certified organic or local fabrics. Work process shared with clients. We transmit the value in the process & proximity.

Key prospects by segment:

The workshops are designed for the participation of a wide variety of audience from the age of 12 upwards & with no age limit. Specific activities for children & young people.

GENERAL TARGET SEGMENT: Adults from 30 to 70 years of age (mainly from urban areas who are interested in the rural environment); People with artistic interests, simple life & close contact with nature; Consumers of nature experiences on a constant basis; People with a high level of purchasing power; People with average purchasing power who decide to invest their money in a more conscious & functional way; Public administrations-Educational establishments

5. OPERATING MODEL

Idoneous channels: Platforms for dissemination of art and ecology projects.

Style, method & sales opportunities:

- we transmit proximity and valuable information and careful product photography related to nature
- constant publications of work processes & calls to action to our target audience
- creation of community through publications of lived experiences
- focus on the feelings that arise when working with hands.
- Active communication & feedback together with other projects & businesses related to our philosophy
- Presence in workshops & markets.
- Collaborations with related projects.
- Points of sale in WhatsApp business & craft markets.
- Affordable, real prices that promote the improvement of the environment.
- The workshops allow optimal learning to continue practicing at home.

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Sensory Bee Nature Trail Larnaca rural cultural landscape, Larnaca Region, Cyprus

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Beekeeping is not simply a profession, but also a part of their cultural heritage, as it has been practiced for centuries & honey is used in unique recipes, which can only be found in the area. Continuous efforts are taking place for the upgrading of the Honey Routes, by training and capacity building of the local communities, encouragement of the women to create micro business based on their skills and their natural resources, protecting the **environment, but also upgrading the area with innovative tools, which will create unique experiences for the visitors.**

The aim of the Sensory Bee Nature Trail is to create a unique experience to learn and enjoy the magical world of bees, **leading to the revival of the village of Vavla**, our pilot heritage site, which was built, according to the historians around 1450 AD, **& regardless of its beauty and potential to develop faces massive depopulation problems.**

Vavla, our pilot heritage site is chosen due to its huge cultural importance:

Stories & tales regarding the name of the village, travel us to the Medieval ages & the to plants of the banks of River Nile in Egypt. In one story the name came from Vavyla, a **feudal lord** of the area including Vavla. **In another story it is said that Vavlagot its name from a plant that grew on the banks of the River Nile in Egypt**, which was brought in by village residents. The soft wood of this plant was of high quality & was used in shipbuilding & the resin of the plant was used as an adhesive of wood for ships. Geologically Vavla is located on the edge of the geological formation of Lefkara (limestone) & volcanic earth of Troodos. The existence of these geological formations & the microclimate of the area allowed the development of **rich vegetation with rare species & 18 endemic plant species.** The location of the village offers **brehtaking views** to the areas of Larnaka & the Troodos mountains. The climate is mild & suitable for holidays both in the winter and summer.

Our solution aims in reviving this unique village, the culture heritage and biodiversity, offering unique sensorial experiences to locals and visitors. We are inviting you to be our partners to this beautiful journey, where the Bees will lead us, to make the Difference!

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

Mission, raison d'être - Sensory Bee Nature trail

Revive & revitalize a unique medieval picturesque village in threat of depopulation.

Preserve its cultural & natural heritage, the stories & legends associated with it & Bee keeping history in the area, through knowledge based sustainable development aligned with EU 2030 goals & Green Deal.

Enhance community interaction of Honey Villages, through smart specialization & provide knowledge joy & happiness to children & help them overcome the fear for Bees.

Massive Transformation Purpose of the Sensory Bee Nature trail

Revival of a unique Medieval village (part of Honey Routes) with great potential.

Enrichment the activities & sustainability of the Honey Routes

Fulfillment of the needs of the children for more experiential & sensorial activities, creating a new family destination, increasing the income from the tourism flow

Societal impact on the culture of protection of the bees & the ecosystem.

More spaces of joy, happiness, relaxation & recreation for mental & emotional health.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL-SDG

Needs/Stakes	Key Figures/Size of challenge
Climate Action Climate change affects the number of bees who are necessary for the existence of our eco-system. This project creates awareness for the protection of bees	Bees population is decreasing on global basis
Decent work & Economic Growth Due to the uniqueness and natural assets of the area(rivers, fertile land, beautiful landscapes, rich vegetation) the cluster of the 9 villages can be a hub for many jobs related to beekeeping from cosmetics to jewelery making, to gastronomy	Upgrading of the infrastructure for the fostering of more bee-businesses and expansion of existing
Good Health & Wellbeing Apitherapy is the new form of alternative medicine providing remedies, from health and wellness to more serious medical problems. Only walking in the sensory nature trail can relax the mind and body, people connect with nature.	Increasing medical and mental problems

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL-SDG

Needs/Stakes	Key Figures/Size of challenge
<p>Sustainable Cities & Communities The project will benefit the whole village of Vavla but also the 9 local communities of the Honey Routes, adding value to the Honey routes and all the activities that take place in the area. It will contribute to the engagement and wellbeing of the young Beekeepers of the area who are vulnerable social groups, especially after the catastrophic fires of this summer; which destroyed thousands of hives and million of bees. A small abandon village will revive and reach its full potential, and can serve as an example, using all the concepts of green and circular economy and tourism, and cultural Europeanisation preserving its rich cultural heritage and digitalization to connect the past with a future and creating a unique sensory experience</p>	9 small vulnerable communities will be benefited and 34 micro and medium size rural businesses will be benefited
<p>Quality Education Environmental education with hands on experiences, about bees and pollination</p>	The impact of learning by experience is inevitable- 1 st in med area
<p>Reduced Inequalities No entry fee, accessible to all families and schools, empowering the young keepers of deprived areas to grow and excel, adding value to their jobs & workshops</p>	

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Target segments customers / users / beneficiaries & Size of each segment	key needs/ expectations / pain points
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Honey Routes families with children-180 - Families with children-60,000 -Primary schools-334 -Environmental Organizations Friends of the Earth Cyprus WWF - the world's largest conservation organization. -Walkers, We Walk-Largest global chain -Birdwatchers –Bird Life Cyprus 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The area of Honey Routes has one of the highest concentrations of families with young children, who often have to travel to the cities to find activities for their children. - To cover their needs for activities in nature - Safe environment - Learning in nature-fulfill the needs of the children for more experiential and sensorial activities and to create a culture of protection of the bees & the ecosystem. Provide spaces of joy, happiness, relaxation and recreation for children with special needs.
<p>Travel Agencies- In EU there are 3,600 travel agencies-Largest global are:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1.Expedia Group 2. Booking Holdings 3. American Express Global Business Travel 4. BCD Travel 	<p>The holistic and comprehensive solutions which will be offered by the digital platform will enable small travel agencies to bring groups to an unspoiled and so interesting area</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Creation of authentic experiences in rural areas - Enrichment of the tourism product of the area
<p>Beneficiaries: Local Citizens- 9 Communities-</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Better life and more places for their families
<p>Beekeepers & Micro Businesses- 34</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Awareness about the importance of bees and biodiversity creates a culture which is very favorable for the Beekeepers, for the protection of their bees and the value of the hive products.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The project is innovative being the first one in EU of its kind, is circular as an existing unknown trail will be upgraded and enhanced and become a hub of knowledge regarding the Bees, is human-centered and different from existing solutions as addresses deprived communities with limited activities for children, it will upgrade the wellbeing & welfare of the habitats and visitors & will offer an oasis to walkers, birdwatchers and people who love nature.

The underlying magic is the magical world of Bees –The touch of all the senses-The beauty of nature-The stories & legends-the trail was the path the ladies of the village were following in order to get water and to wash their clothes, singing & laughing and happily spend the day in nature.

The differentiating value proposition that cannot be found now or elsewhere?

Unique-Accessible-Touches all the senses -Family & children oriented-free to the public & sensorial:

Smell-Bee Flora, See-Bee Hotels-Bee Hives-Water fountains-Taste-Edible Bee Flora, Hear-Sound of water & buzzing of bees, Touch-Water & bee Flora.

Segments	Key Prospects	Elements of the solution which may interest them
Agro-tourism establishments	Increase in visitors Attract new segments of tourists Be more competitive & unique Use it for their own health & wellness	Activities during their visitors stay Guided Walks
Eco Physis Bee & Nature Center	Increase in visitors Attract new segments of tourists Be more competitive & unique Use it for their own health & wellness	
Local Restaurant	Increase number & segment of visitors	

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The village of Vavla our pilot heritage site, is almost intact from tourism and technology.

Two unique micro businesses are operating there, an agrotourism accommodation establishment, of high standard, which has attracted even the National Geographic as best practice of agrotourism, & Ecophys which offers Bee experiential activities and workshops, practicing human-centered fair & responsible tourism .

At the moment the cooperation between the two is very limited, and although the historical nature trail where the project will take place, is located within walking distance from the village, it has almost no visitors, as its rich history & importance to the village is unrevealed, and the stories and legends around it are known by few very old people.

Our aim is to use technology to **safeguard, and promote the cultural Europeanisation aspects, while creating fair and responsible tourism packages by linking the existing unique practices & upgrading the nature trail into a sensory nature bee trail**, enhancing the stories of the meeting point of washing clothes in nature in a place full of aromatic plants where bees were & are still producing one of the best honeys in the island. Due to its boutique size the village can become a pole of attraction & best practice of circular tourism & reduce mass tourism from the nearby cities of Limassol & Larnaka.

The increase of visitors will boost female & youth entrepreneurship, while the cultural heritage of the village, tangible & intangible will be preserved.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – YOUR LANDING PAGE

Families with Children!

Bee Here- Let the bees guide you

Sensory Bee Nature Trail

Solution Features / Offers

Relax your senses and let the bees guide you into a journey of knowledge.

Strong / compelling call to Action

With your support, we can save the Bees, and create magical places for our children and the generations to come

Trust indicators

We are expanding and enriching the Honey Routes with new activities & points of interest for sustainable rural development

Contact Us

Troodos Network

Yioulapapakyltaccou@gmail.com 00357-99427980

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

5. OPERATING MODEL

Critical competencies and resources that must be activated	Internal & External
Project Management	Troodos Network has extensive expertise in the area, working on its sustainable development since 2015, using the smart specialization sustainable model with great success.
Scientific knowledge about Bees and Bee Flora	Bee Flora is crucial & necessary for the sustainability of the Honey Routes and the local ecosystem, and of greater importance than in other areas due to the high density of bee hives. The Cyprus Technological University University & Udan have agreements of cooperation with Troodos Network for scientific support.
Provision of Bee Flora & on Spot expertise	The Ministry of Agriculture provides free bee plants to communities and their experts help in their planting
Architectural design	ADP Architects- Experts in nature paths designs and customized equipment for Bee Nature Trails
Creation of specially designed equipment	MMV Progress Ltd-Experts in equipment for parks and nature trails
Sustainability needs / maintenance and upgrading when needed	The Community Council with the Local private business stakeholder
Integration of the Sensory Bee Nature Trail into existing activities	Troodos network will add it into the Honey Routes and promote it through the activities and festivals, of the other 8 communities and create a cluster with the local stakeholders
Marketing & Promotion	Content Hub will create the Marketing Strategy to address families, schools, hikers and environmentalists using articles, photos and videos, media, website, social media and press.
Field Trip & Study Visits	Journalist and tour operators study visits in order to feel the experience, promote it and bring tourism

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

5. OPERATING MODEL

Media –Troodos Network has a **cooperation with TV and Radio channels**, for dissemination Social media channels will be used to reach customer/user segments through out their journey from knowing offer existence to its use and reuse, utilizing the social media of the core team which has thousands of users, and the social media pages of the events of Honey Routes, as well as the personal social media accounts of the team of the Sensory Bee Trail Marketing & Communication plan-Press Releases will be sent to all newspapers and magazines in Greek, English & Russian.

Marketing strategy

The Marketing Strategy will be developed by Content Hub, who are experts in content creation of promotional material with a lot of experience in the Honey Routes, the Honey Villages and all the activities that take place in the area. They have created the film about the Honey Routes and are trusted by public and local authorities as their media partners.

All tools of marketing & **e-marketing** will be employed mostly digital, to be environmentally friendly and effective.

Stage of Progress	Achievements
Mapping of the Nature Trail	The path is mapped by Content Hub, with drones so we know exactly the dimensions and places where each item will be placed
Local stakeholders involvement	Troodos Network & Content Hub had meetings with the local stakeholders who have expressed their full support
Local Authorities involvement	The President of the Community Council supports the creation of the Sensory Bee Nature Trail
Mobilization of Voluntary & Support groups	The Rotary nominee District Governor has expressed his interest in supporting the project with the biggest network of volunteers in Cyprus
Field Visit with potential users	A field trip has been organized with school teachers who will be one of the target groups and their feedback was extremely positive

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (Offer type + target segment)	Price / unit	Nbr of clients / sales per year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Revenue stream 1	500 x3		1,500	1,500	1,500
Revenue stream 2	1000		1,000	1,000	1,000
Revenue stream 3					
Revenue stream 4					
Total Revenues			2,500	2,500	2,500
Fundings	Product / Service / Activity funded		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Funding 1	M4 - Public Subvention - 80% Initial Cost funding		13,920		
Funding 2	M7- Social Impact Investing - 20% Initial Cost funding		3,480		
Funding 3	M6 - Private Mobilization - 100% Maintenance Cost Planning			1,900	1,900
Funding 4					
Total Fundings			17,400	1,900	1,900
Total Incoming Flows					

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs	Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Equipment, outfit, furnitures,...	Initial construction & maintenance 10,000	8,000	1,000	1,000	
Energy, Water, Raw Material	Solar equipment's 1,500	1,500			
External services	Marketing & Promotion 3,000	7,500	500	500	
	Coordination & Implementation 3,000				
	Designs & Printings 1,500				
	Architectured. Design 1,000				
Real Estate (rental of offices, warehouses / storage places,...)	Not applicable				
Total variable costs		17,000	1,500	1,500	
Fixed costs	Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Internal staff	Not applicable				
External staff	Not applicable				
Recurring expenses (admin, insurances, energy, telecom,...)	Insurance 1,200	400	400	400	
Total fixed costs		400	400	400	
Investments	Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Investment 1					
Investment 2					
...					
Total investments			17,400	1,900	1,900

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

Team	Skills, Experience, Roles, Entrepreneurial potential
Panayiotis Papsadopoulos	Expert in Tourism & Sustainable Development & Project Management
Yioula Michaelidou	Economist, Expert in Rural Entrepreneurship & Sustainable Development
Georgia Soshliou	Biologist, Local Entrepreneur , expert on workshops related to Bees & Beekeeping
Donna Marie Pavlou	Expert in Agrotourism hospitality, Local Entrepreneur
Demetris Satrikis	Marketing tools development
Alexandros Filippou	Media & Content Expert
George Pavlou	Expert in the nature trails of Vavia, Volunteer for guiding people around the village

The organizational structure is centered on the **Core team Coordination**, which is supported by several stakeholders: **Local authorities**, **Travel agencies**, **Small Business**, **Hospitality stakeholders**, **Schools**, and **Beekeepers**.

The core team is supported by three main pillars:

- Local communities empowerment & capacity building:** Knowledge based sustainable development
- Stakeholder engagement:** cluster creation - Creation of Routes /packages with several activities
- Coordination team:** consisting of the initial core team, with local small business owners

Logos for **Be.CULTOUR** (Beyond cultural tourism) and **ICHEC** (BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL) are displayed at the bottom.

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

Target Segments/Direct Beneficiaries	Activities & Achievements	Expected Changes & Impacts
School Children	Activities in Nature & Knowledge about Bees & Biodiversity	Improved Health Increased quality of life
Families with children	New activities in nature, Environmental awareness	Family Bonding, improved health & wellness
Citizens of deprived area/village	Activities in the village	Improved health & quality of life
Beekeepers	Upgrading of Honey Routes & demand for Honey	Increase of Socioeconomic welfare
Walkers, Hikers	Accessible, beautiful places	Better health & wellness more social interaction
Nature Trail	Knowledge based sustainable development	Preservation of the culture , history, biodiversity
Local Businesses	Enrichment of tourism product	Positive socioeconomic impact
Aging & declining population of Vavla (from 300 to 16)	Inflow of tourism	Social interaction & better health
Local Monastery	Added value in the area	Positive socioeconomic impact
Citizens of Honey Villages (8 communities)	More activities in nature & knowledge for Bees	Better Health & Wellness
General public	Dissemination activities	Improved Health & Mental Health

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Project Management	Project development	Project development	Project development	Project development		
Risk Assessment	Field visit / Plan updated	Finalized financial support	Market research for insurance	Contract with insurance company	Renew contract	Renew contract
Communication & Dissemination Strategy	Promotion content creation	Dissemination Campaign Strategy	Start the implementation of the campaign	Study visits for promotion	Update content	Update content
Implementation Strategy	Finalize of the plans	Procurement of constructions			Maintenance	Maintenance
Evaluation & Optimization	Quarterly assessment	Quarterly assessment	Quarterly assessment	Quarterly assessment	Yearly assessment	Yearly assessment

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Residence of Creation
Needle festivals

**Larnaca rural cultural landscape,
Larnaca Region, Cyprus**

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Identity is a crucial part of one's being. It not only dictates who one is but also who one is in relation to their community. We as the younger generation of our island feel that there is a need to clarify what it means to be a Cypriot in today's world. There seems to be an apathy in regard to modern culture a sense of confusion deriving from the pain caused from our past.

Cyprus is a relatively new nation that uses fixed narratives as a compass when navigating Cypriot identity. These narratives however are flawed disregarding real events that also form a part of who we are. This lack of collective characteristics joined with mainstream media, intense corruption and a migrating youth, leaves no room for doubt for our current state of affairs.

This pain still holds power over us and it's time for it to be addressed. Our initiative gives people the tools or more directly the needle they need in order to pierce through their preconceptions and biases in regard to our Cypriot history and character.

We strongly feel that Cypriot modern culture is lost in the midst of our past and its pain that still holds power over us.

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

What's the *mission, raison d'être* of your project ?

- to offer a platform where people can **explore, identify** and **embrace** the Cypriot Identity.
- We want to leave a legacy that people will be looking back at and refer to in 100 years from now.

Purpose (our reason for existence), (is never achieved)

- We exist to empower Cypriot culture identity

WHY: (purpose of existence)

We want to re-shape the Cypriot identity

What: (solution)

We are focusing on providing a cultural hub (residence of creation) in the site of Pervolia. This physical space will be kind and inclusive both to the user and the environment where through the realm of creative arts and crucial questions regarding our ethos and cypriot character can be addressed.

Where you want to go:

Change is unavoidably uncomfortable but through a small prick of a needle we want to carefully sew the present to our past in order to shape our future.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

Selling Cypriot and European identity

Unsustainable development, low levels of recycling 22% in Cyprus , 44% EU average. waste per capita 590kg in Cyprus 480 kg in Cyprus

Lack of emphasis on creativity and critical thinking in education

9% unemployment

6% of asylum seekers, 21% of population are immigrants

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

What is the differentiating value proposition that cannot be found now or elsewhere ?

Value Proposition

- Young Cypriots:** a space to explore their cultural heritage and embrace their identity.
- Artists:** a platform to connect and co-create with talent and potential customers and investors.
- Tourists:** it offers a convenient and alternative way to understand and appreciate the Cypriot cultural identity which can help them to have a more memorable experience during their visit in Cyprus (good starting point, next to the airport, one of the few cultural activities)
- Local community:** it will attract sustainable tourism (quality tourism) to the area, it will support local producers and artists, work together with the community to establish vision and policies on how to make Pervolia a sustainable region.
- Environment:** connect people with nature to be more environmentally friendly and conscious through their actions, design a zero waste model, promote values of sustainability and interconnectedness.
- Public agents:** it supports talented artists while bringing together policy makers with citizens.

Why is it the right moment ? Why now ?

- there is a movement towards Cypriotism (internal force)
- cultural push (recently created Deputy Ministry of Culture) (institutional force)
- diversification of touristic model in Cyprus - (from sun and sea towards quality tourism).
- from Jan 2026 for 6 months, Cyprus will be the capital city of Europe.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – YOUR LANDING PAGE

Define your audience for each landing page !!!

Strong Catchphrase / Mantra / Headline:
we offer the needle to reshape Cypriot identity

Effective subheading explaining your offer and its value proposition:

a cultural hub that will offer an inclusive and holistic experience where through the realm of creative arts, crucial questions regarding our ethos and Cyprus character can be addressed

Solution Features / Offers

- Strong visual representation of our residence of creation concept design and how it follows circular economy principles and explaining spatial strategy
- **1.** Co-creative spaces: rent studios/ spaces
- **2.** Thematic cultural events: We, the needle team organise these events.
- **3.** Community Platform: a platform for networking with likemind individuals that share our North star, discussion space, community platform/ blog that people share their experiences, what's new in Cyprus regarding culture

Strong / compelling call to Action

- Needle video explaining who we are and what we want to change
- **Sign up** as a young Cypriot/ tourist for newsletter
- **Register** as artist
- **Register** as collaborator for funding etc.

Trust indicators

- Testimonials / Needle Ambassadors
- Promotional Video
- Team experience
- Partners
- Existing examples from elsewhere
- Full Transparency - measure social, environmental and economic impacts created by Needle so far and also share future targets aim to be achieved

Practical details/Contact us

- Address
- Email
- Phone
- Social Media

5. OPERATING MODEL

- **Critical competencies and resources that must be activated** : those you'll internalize and externalize
 - ✓ Tangible resources (real estate, (Pyrgos tis Rigainas), timber structure, low-carbon materials (bale straw, plasterboard, clay plaster, green roof, nails), mechanical equipment and systems, furniture, lighting fixtures, biodegradable packaging, waste management infrastructure, WCs, kitchen
 - ✓ Intangible resources (branding, processes, immaterial value,...) Needle brand, community network, creative culture,
 - ✓ Human resources (owning skills, competencies, know how,...) Needle team, Artistic network, Cypriot talent and creativity, circular design expertise, managing skills, social entrepreneurship
- **Marketing strategy**
 - ✓ Channels used to reach customer/user segments throughout their journey (from knowing offer existence to its use and reuse)

Informative marketing strategy, Visionary/Influential/Role Model

Direct contact (through Needle Ambassadors) - word of mouth, private referral community invitation.

Indirect (through social media and web platform).

Mobile app?

- ✓ **Marketing / Communication plan**

Steps: Share online surveys to young Cypriots; Get in touch with key stakeholders and artists for introductory meetings (e.g. Stelios Georgiades, Home for Cooperation, Urban Gorillas, Xarkis Festivals) - Identify Needle Ambassadors; Attend local events - create network and find potential partners or synergies; Identify local talented artists to be part of Needle Hub; Talk with policy makers and attend public conferences.

6. FINANCIAL MODEL

How will you make your project economically sustainable ? **SOCIAL ENTERPRISE**

- **Revenue streams**: renting our premises for other festivals, co-working space, tickets, subscriptions, merchandise, commission on products sold by artists, food and beverage commission.
 - **Funding models**: Public grants - Deputy Ministry of Culture of Cyprus =20000 euros through "Cypria" grant. apply for EU accelerator programs, Crowdfunding, pending application for Crowdfunder.
- government funding, EU funding, Crowdfunding, Private investors, Cooperative model
- **Cost structure** required for implementation of the solution : now and tomorrow
 - Fixed costs: Acquisition or leasing of land, architectural and engineering fees, building construction costs, permits and zoning fees, furniture and equipment expenses (rental), insurance (liability insurance to protect organizers and attendees from accidents etc.), marketing fees
 - Variable costs: utilities bills, staffing cost, merchandise costs, waste management costs, maintenance and repair
 - Rémunération model of teammates: limited liability partnership (LLP), consult with legal professionals
 - **Investments** : infrastructure and energy management

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** Limited Liability Partnership of the four partners (team). Social enterprise. We will use a hybrid business model as we will be offering, products, services, subscription. The team will take decisions unanimously.
- **Human resources**
 - **Human capital:** Team- Giorgos - Social Entrepreneur (Finance background), Rania - Sustainable Designer, Christos - Social Sciences, George - Professional Artist (Musical Theatre)
 - **Ways of working :** The team shares the same values (Curiosity, Kindness, Trustworthiness, Leadership). Different backgrounds with identical objective to enhance the contemporary culture of Cyprus and create a movement that aims to shape the Cypriot identity. Decisions are unanimous and the project co-managed internally taking into account expertise. Rania for the infrastructure, Giorgos for the entrepreneurial aspects, George regarding the brand and Christos to network and support.
 - **Resource people** Artists of various levels of expertise- called upon to take part/volunteer in events. Technocrats from the Deputy Ministry of Culture, Tourism and other local authorities for consulting, granting and partnerships. IT support.
- **Internal and external governance :** Limited Liability Partnership with the 4 people in the team as equal partners. Stakeholders like artists or other institutions and organisations can work with us to co-organise events. Local community to be employed for the organisation of the event and for supplying food and beverages. Needle team respects and will always respects human rights. We are committed to equal representation, respect, diversity and empowerment. We are open to work with everyone who shares our values.

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

Talented artists/ local entrepreneurs

1. Financial Resources: Grants and Funds, Capital
2. Human Resources: Employees/Volunteers, Consultants
3. Material Resources: Infrastructure, equipments, mechanical/ Energy Systems
4. Technical resources: social media accounts, pcs, mobile phones, website and community platform, database

Cultural Education, empower community by giving them a platform/ voice,

1. Co-working through renting or using for free our facilities
2. Training/ Educating through workshops, lectures, courses
3. Networking with like-minded people through our community platform and discussion space/ event.

Achievements:

1. Cultural and Circular economy Education - Quality Educational Content through our festivals and workshops.
2. Exploring the collective identity and heritage of Cyprus - Cultural Hub
3. A platform that connects like-minded individuals (empower community by giving them a platform/ voice) - Community Platform and discussion space.
4. Giving artists a platform to showcase their art and make financial profits - Cultural Thematic festival
5. Interactive experience

Results:

1. Economic development (Education, cultural & social development)
2. Change of social cohesion
3. Enhance creative expression
4. Preservation of history and heritage
5. Social and emotional wellbeing
6. Cultural diversity
7. Identity and sense of space
8. Recreational experience

Macro Impacts: SDG's

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

- **Roadmap** for the weeks, months and 3 years to come
 1. *Create Landing Page*
 2. *Apply for relevant national and EU grants & fundings*
 3. *Attend local and international events*
 4. *Create a close network of local stakeholders*
 5. *Find partners*

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

kalosorisete (joy of culture)

**Larnaca rural cultural landscape,
Larnaca Region, Cyprus**

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The proposed solution will be a website & an application at which, people who live in Cyprus or wish to travel to Rural Larnaca for vacations can book through the website local experiences such as pasta making workshop or chair making workshop. The actual product / service will be the experience as practiced by locals from generation to generation. On the back end of the website/application the vendors (people that they will provide the service/experience) will be able to manage their bookings, their workshops and on later stage they will be able to upload products on the application's marketplace.

Our purpose is to make the website as user friendly as possible.

- To achieve that we will include search optimization with the use of categories, types and geographic locations.
- Use of written visual and audio means to immerse the visitor right at the get go

This will be a real service by real people, that want to pass-on authentic Cypriot experiences.

Our platform provides the means for bridging the gap between locating authenticity and exploring it.

Our team is composed of: • Young enthusiastic individuals; Tech savvy; The older generation to capitalize the experience; Actual service offered by locals who wish to be empowered.

All these people have something in common. All share the same love and passion about culture and wish to become the legacy bearers of our history to the future. People nowadays choose to travel for the 5-sense experience rather than just for laying on the beach. Travelers are now curious to explore and learn new skills & new experiences. Kalosorisete wishes to give the platform to our legacy bearers to promote their workshops & transfer this knowledge and wisdom to the next generations. Also, giving life to the rural areas means that we will also tackle urbanism.

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

- What's the mission, raison d'être of your project?

Embrace the customs and traditions. Learn from the gatekeepers of our long history!

- What's your Massive Transformation Purpose?

In general terms we are wishing to enter the tourist industry. However, we would like to give a fresh look to the old and backdated Cypriot tourist model of "sun and sea". Cyprus has so much to offer, and this is our mission – to put light to our history, to our customs and traditions, giving a platform to people who know this history, in a sustainable and eco-friendly way.

As part of our Corporate Social Responsibility, we wish to work with the local communities and the relevant government bodies to help reforestation and biodiversity of the areas affected by wildfires and climate change. COVID-19 proved that a new model of traveling is emerging. People choose to travel for the 5 senses experience and not just for tourism. This platform wishes to serve this purpose. Further, we wish to make an impact on the lives of the locals, not only by making their living better in fiscal terms. We also wish to improve the environment they live in.

Massive Transformative Purpose:

Safeguarding the customs and traditions of our longstanding history, while preserving the sustainability of our rural areas.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Target segments: Travelers – Families; Small Groups Locals / Expats Corporate Groups

Families

Key needs: Have direct contact with the locals. Bond with their families. Have new experiences as a family. Expectations: Enjoy their time. Have fun Learn.

Pain Points: Cost; Distance from their accommodation;

Small Groups / Individuals.

Key Needs: Hands on Experience; Learn about a new culture; Intricate curiosity

Expectations: Enjoy their time; Have fun Learn

Pain Points: Cost; Distance from their accommodation

Corporate Groups:

Key Needs: Learning the culture; Well Organized Offers team bonding.

Expectations: Learning; Having Fun; Bond with their colleagues

Pain Points: Not well organized; Not all participants needs are served Spend time with people that they don't like.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The solution will provide the technology, where people visiting Cyprus - rural Larnaca, either for leisure or work will have the opportunity to book to visit workshops or houses of locals and experience the authentic way of life and live authentic Cypriot experiences, such as pasta making and wine making.

Furthermore, as people will visit these workshops - old customs and traditions will also revive, giving a fresh look into our cultural heritage.

Our solution is split into 2 parts. One part - the front side, it's the retail side, where the visitors will navigate into the page, choose their preferred experience, learn what is about and book it instantly. The visitor's journey will follow these steps:

- Entering the platform (website / mobile-app) - with the use of filters the visitor can choose an experience either by type, location, date or even by vendor. Each experience has its own sub-page, where the visitor will be given information about what he/she should expect, such as images of the experience, location, brief description, list of available sessions and booking button.
- The second part will be the vendor's management system - back-end, vendors will be able to manage the experiences that they offer, their bookings and finances, add or delete workshops, pictures and/or venues.

5. OPERATING MODEL

Critical competencies and resources that must be activated:

- ✓ Tangible resources: Computers; Car; Desks; Office Equipment
- ✓ Intangible resources: Outsource to marketing company - the whole marketing campaign; Licensing (godaddy, quickbooks, hosting services, cloud services); & Insurances
- ✓ Human resources • Programmer (in house); Marketing /Social Media Campaigner (out-source); Vendors (out-sourced); Booking Manager / Support Manager; Accountant / Book keeping Clerk

Marketing strategy

Our main focus will be the use of Social Media. Based on the market research that the Marketing company will execute for us; we will choose the relevant campaigns. For example, according to recent research by the Cypriot Deputy Ministry of Tourism, there is an increase of 97% on tourists' arrivals from France during 2022. As such, we will make it our priority to boost our marketing campaign towards this market.

At a later stage, and when we start our first sales, we are planning to advertise our services in airlines' magazines and on the airport boards. As for the corporate groups, we will try to reach them either with direct marketing, for example by calls and/or letters in a more corporate professional manner.

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs		Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Equipment, outfit, furniture	Marketing-Promotion-PR	€	11,154	€ 71,202	€ 124,883	
Energy, Water, Raw Material	Utilities	€	6,300	€ 9,300	€ 12,000	
External services	IT, Accounting, Legal	€	30,200	€ 31,000	€ 31,000	
Real Estate (rental of offices, warehouses / storage places, ...)	Service Office	€	11,000	€ 10,000	€ 24,000	
Other Variable Costs	Contingent variable Costs (20% of remaining variable costs)	€	19,810	€ 31,902	€ 33,373	
Total variable costs			€ 118,964	€ 153,804	€ 205,256	
Fixed costs		Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Internal staff	25,000(1) 115 - 5,000(2) 115 120,000(4) 115	€	21,000	€ 30,000	€ 30,000	
Vehicle	1 vehicle inc service	€	30,000	€ 3,000	€ 25,000	
Recurring expenses (admin, insurances, energy, telecomm. ...)		€	11,000	€ 10,000	€ 24,000	
Other fixed costs	Contingent Fixed Costs (20% of remaining fixed costs)	€	13,400	€ 14,000	€ 29,800	
Total fixed costs			€ 80,400	€ 87,000	€ 128,800	
Investments		Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Investment 1						
Investment 2						
Total investments			0	0	0	
Total Outgoing Flows			118,964	240,804	334,056	

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

Revenues	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3
Tourists	€ 72,000	€ 180,000	€ 270,000
Locals	€ 5,040	€ 12,800	€ 18,900
Expats	€ 12,000	€ 30,000	€ 45,000
Total Revenues	€ 89,040	€ 222,800	€ 333,900
Fundings	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3
Own Funds	€ 10,000	€ 10,000	€ -
Beccultour funding	€ 50,000	€ 23,000	€ 23,000
Investors	€ 50,000	€ 25,000	€ 25,000
Total fundings	€ 110,000	€ 58,000	€ 48,000
Incoming Flows - IN	€ 199,040	€ 280,800	€ 381,900
Cost Structure	YEAR 1	YEAR 2	YEAR 3
Fixed Costs	€ 80,800	€ 87,600	€ 178,800
Variable Costs	118996.8	191892	201
Investments incl Amortization	0	0	
Outgoing Flows - OUT	199396.8	279492	380
Results (Δ In-Out)	€ 357	€ 1,308	€ 1,882

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** incorporation of Limited Liability Company

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS / THEORY OF CHANGE

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Technology	Building the solution	Building the solution	Testing the solution	Release the solution	Upgrading the solution based on vendors feedback	Upgrading the solution (add new features)
Sales	Contact potential vendors	Contact potential vendors	Prototype Testing and collect feedback	Train the vendors on program functionality	Search for new vendors – add features on the program	Search for new vendors – add features on the program
Managerial	Establishing the company	Drafting all legal documents		Signing the contracts with vendors	Based on work flow - Hiring new staff	Based on work flow - Hiring new staff
Marketing	Search for company to provide marketing services	Establish relationship with the marketing company	Establishing the marketing campaign	Run of the marketing campaign	Run of the marketing campaign	Run of the marketing campaign

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Forsviks CHAICE

**Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites,
Västra Götaland Region, Sweden**

NORTH STAR

- The place where people grow
- Developing Forsvik
- Living community beyond tourism
- Creating creative working and leisure space by using existing buildings

OUR SOLUTION

Forsviks Cultural Heritage, Arts and Innovation Centre (CHAICE)

- Development of existing space
- Providing rooms to entrepreneurs & locals
- Enhancing to create experiences
- Transformative Tourism

DESIRABILITY

- From the locals for everybody
- For Crafters
- For Locals
- For Visitors & Tourists
- For Cultural Heritage
- For the Future

FEASIBILITY

- Independent - "The Hub"
- Entrepreneurs, municipal & Västra Götalands regionen
- Already established entrepreneurs
- THE COLLABORATION

VIABILITY

- Teater/musikaluppsättningar
- Originalberättelser
- Workshops
- Utställningar
- Konserter
- Liveupplevelser
- Akademiverksamhet
- Filmprojekt
- Hyran
- Utlåning/ Events

POSITIVE IMPACT

"The choice"

- Strengthens local community
- Influx of entrepreneurs
- More sustainable tourism

Where does the money com from?

Business model, year 1-5

	Year one	Year three	Year five
Fixed Costs/ Investment	-3,036,000	-3,300,000	-4,000,000
Income	+1,022,600	+1,800,00	+4,200,000
Funding	2,013,400	1,500,000	0
RESULTS	0	0	200,000

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Prova-Bo long-term rentals

Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites, Västra Götaland Region, Sweden

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Prova-Bo

Prova-Bo wants to make it easier to move to the countryside. Through an app and website, small communities can showcase themselves. The potential resident can get information about what it is like living in an area, but also get the chance to test live there for 6-12 months. Prova-Bo supports creation of new try-living rentals within existing built environment. Compared to existing housing platforms, Prova-Bo puts the focus on local identity and relations rather than objects.

Founders and Becultour team

Prova-Bo was founded by Elisabet Anis and Lotta Kamlien during their architectural master studies at Chalmers. During Becultour they paired up with two representatives of local associations - Eva Lasoneller from Rydal and Lena Göthe from the island Åstol. Their critical eye and local knowledge has been crucial in the development of Prova-Bo.

Market and targets

The project targets regions of Sweden, starting with Västra Götalandsregionen. Only in VGR, there are 760 smaller communities inhabited by 50-100000 people. New trends of digitalisation and increased interest of alternatives of the urban lifestyle - provide rural areas with new possibilities to thrive again. Prova-Bo combines the interests and needs of small communities, people looking for a place to settle down and house owners in rural areas.

Funding

The main income to Prova-Bo will in the short run come from support of partners such as VGR and other investors. In the long run it will be economically viable through marketing on platform, regional partner fees and the 1% fee we plan to deduct from the rentals.

We need you!

We need help with finding finances to build platform, get legal support and marketing to reach out. Become our partners and join the journey in developing Prova-Bo in Västra götaland region and beyond. Together we make it easier to find home on the countryside, create new housing solutions within existing ones - all while supporting local development.

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

Why do we exist?

- It is not easy to know where to live
- Statistics show more people are willing to leave the cities
- Existing platforms mediating housing focus on objects - but miss the most important perspective
- Norm of buying and few objects on market can make decision daunting
- Half of the vilas only inhabited by 1-2 persons
- Local communities want and need more inhabitants
- Increased tourism not solving all issues these communities face
- This is why we want to create Prova Se

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Local communities

Rural areas consist of many smaller communities and most of them struggle with depopulation and an aging population.

Only within VGR, there are 477 communities with 50-199 inhabitants and 290 with 200-10000.

Often tourism is seen as the main strategy for development.

Fear of increased workload can turn off many engaged locals.

Need of more all year residents willing to co-create the community as well as increased income.

Need help to attract new residents in a simple way not demanding too much effort from the locals.

Houseowners

40% of Swedish households live in vilas and smaller communities largely consist of them. The houses are often built for a nuclear family but more than half are today inhabited by only 1 to 2 people.

With aging, a big house can be difficult to manage and also uneconomical.

Many also wish for a positive development in their community - ready to contribute.

Fears of renting out to strangers and practical issues can be daunting.

Need for a simple and secure way of renting out.

Potential new residents

It can be hard to know where to settle down. Due to urbanisation, big parts of Sweden is becoming quite anonymous for many. Rural norm of buying and few objects on market makes the decision of moving even bigger. Existing market focus on objects.

Need for introduction to and information about rural areas.

Need of simpler ways of getting to know a place.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Prova Bo / Test Living

Making it easier to find a home in the countryside

- A regional platform showcasing smaller communities
- Lower threshold by informing about life in these places and by providing opportunity to test living in a place 5-12 months
- Linking existing rentals and support creation of new rentals within the existing
- Provide smaller places with great marketing opportunity

Places with 200-8000 inhabitants
296 in VGR (shown on map)

Places with 50-199 inhabitants
477 in VGR

(SIC)

How does it work?

People looking for a place

Check an account

Browse through communities - near you

Get updates on available private rentals and newly registered communities

Read user highlights and other relevant information

Write direct message to the local association

Learn more by following links to local groups and websites

Get sign-up information and rent through app

Local communities

Readershipy owners

A local association register community

Do you want to create a new rental?

Get info, material and advice on how to proceed

Get info, material and advice on how to proceed

They receive info and material from them to launch creation of more rentals

Offered services for design and building services from websites

Register new rentals

Get information about interest in their community

Get sign-up services and receive rent through app

Agree to welcome and introduce new and long residents

Get sign-up services

Part of platform provide source for communication between local communities

5. OPERATING MODEL

Critical Competencies:

Need:

Legal support & Rental leases.

Website and app management och build up

Supports for experts within the fields above

Collaboration: Regional VGR

Local communities: Need to sign up on platform.

House owners: to rent through prova bo.

Expertise within the group:

Graphics, Marketing strategy, Connections to local association, Holistic perspective, environmental and social sustainability perspective

We have verbal support from experts in the field but need to test our product.

Need to understand more about our users, especially the "settlers"
- What attracts them? who are they? What do they need?

How clear a target group do we need? - Young people, families with children?

Define which local communities are allowed to join.
- Number of inhabitants maximum limit? Does a local association need to be the one to register?

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

How will people hear about Prova Bo?

- Platform is developed in collaboration with many
- Can be marketed in many places – regions, municipalities, networks – etc etc
- Stories and communities shared in social media
- Users kept active through notifications and interactive functions

6. FINANCIAL MODEL

- Most income from regions, investors, grants and advertising
- Covers labor to create, run and develop platform
- Rentals kept low
- 1% admin fee per rental
- 8% of rental to local association

	(M€)	YEAR 1 start up	YEAR 2 up & running	YEAR 3 growing
Revenues	7% of rentals Advertising Services (in architecture)		46k (30 rentals) 300k 100k	123k (130 rentals) 1000k 600k
Fundings	Region as partner Investors/grants	120k 220k	120k 300k	240k (2 regions) 300k
Result		2320k	2000k	4700k
Costs	Staff Consults Marketing Other	140k (2 employees) 200k 50k 100k	210k (3 employees) 300k 75k 100k	280k (4 employees) 400k 75k 100k
Result		2150k	2775k	3375k
Balance		300k	700k	1300k

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- A collaboration of stakeholders
- Regions as partners
- Serving smaller communities
- Joint stock company or financial association?
- Prova Bo originally a masters-project targeting the needs of the Island Azzul
- Received confirmation from experts and locals
- Our team a mix of two architects and two local representatives from Rydal and Azzul

Local communities
-register on platform
-welcomes new residents

Regions and municipalities
-market platform
-pay yearly fee
-exchange of knowledge

House and property owners
-create prova-bo rentals
-supports the local development

Prova Bo team
-create and run platform
-marketing and social media
-architectural services
-legal issues - consults

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream	YEAR 1 start up	YEAR 2 up & running	YEAR 3 growing
 Gather local communities on platform	# 20 or 30 communities in VGR registered on platform	# 75 or 100 in VGR	# 40 or 70 in VGR # smaller regional pilot platform
 Community of people looking for home	# 70 clients have submitted to platform	# 120 clients have submitted to platform	# 120 clients have submitted to platform
 Provo Be rentals	# legal framework and contracts for rental # support documents are offered to clients of the rental # the production starts rapidly	# first 12 units to complete and signed at 0-12 months	# 100 units to complete and signed
 Increase viability of project	# platform is tested and running # working strategy is made and carried out	# platform is being tested and carried out # working strategy is made and carried out	# platform is being tested and carried out
 Set up organisation	# public registration with local government members	# gather without partners	

- We need help with:**
- finding finances to build platform, get legal support and marketing to reach out
 - become our partners and join the journey in developing Provo to or living globalized region and beyond.
- Together we:**
- make it easier to find home on the countryside
 - create new housing solutions within existing areas
 - all while supporting local development.

Places with 200-4000 inhabitants: 1778 in Sweden (shown on map)

Places with 50-100 inhabitants: 3186 in Sweden (120)

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

Create, Design & Engage

Forsvik and Rydal Industrial Heritage Sites Västra Götaland Region, Sweden

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY - 1

Aim & Objectives There is a need to develop and highlight more co-creative practice to ensure regenerative human centred experiences locally and internationally.
Our plan has been designed to create:

1. **Culture and heritage experiences all year round**
2. **Develop a common program on existing scenes and meeting spots.**

How : To achieve these we are working in partnership with Saltaire Inspired, an innovative arts organisation based in World Heritage Site in Bradford, West Yorkshire. The collaboration between International Weaving Center, Rydals museum and Industrial Heritage Site in Saltaire has already been very creative and rewarding.

Our sites : have much to offer as local destinations and creative space to play and work. We are keen therefore, to generate a creative innovation network to reflect and expand the visit of the sites, built on a **philosophy of innovation and outward facing partnerships and global connectedness.**

Founders : Christina Shearer (Rydal) & Dr Julia Calver (Saltaire) both experienced within their respective locations, in community practice & academically. We have both an experienced team of project managers and artists and network of volunteers

Our community : Rydal museum is home to the **oldest working spinning mill in Sweden.** The industrial site of Rydal is situated in the municipalities of Mark (34,000 inhabitants). **Saltaire** is an **Industrial World Heritage Site** nestled within the city of Bradford Metropolitan District Council home to 500,000 residents and the youngest population in Europe.

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY - 2

The Market

There is keen interest in ensuring regenerative tourism is developed utilising the cultural heritage assets and local communities. Artists and Crafts people have been collaborating in this way for many years in Saltaire. Recent market research identified keen interest in developing more partnership opportunities.

Impact

Rydal is keen to create cultural experiences all year round, so generating local programme to support local economy will make a difference in Rydal's cultural tourism offer. Bradford is UK City of Culture 2025 and further support the international link with cultural heritage creative connections.

Viability : Across the teams in Rydal and Saltaire we have expertise, team members and volunteers that have been developing this partnership. This has been built slowly but incrementally to ensure trust and shared values. We have identified sources of funding to apply to, and core budgets we can draw from.

The ASK :

Funders : We need support from funders to invest in this project to progress the international collaboration of shared community and artist creations that celebrate cultural industrial heritage

Municipality/Local Authority : We need both advocacy, financial support and networks to enhance the network, learnings and profile of the partnership to demonstrate and celebrate connectivity and creativity across heritage sites

Participants (Community & Artists) : We invite you to continue to work with us on this special journey of international co-creation of textiles, crafts and arts that emerge from your stories, your life and experience in your locality.

Research Partners : We invite you to explore points of research interest to capture and enlighten this journey.

Create Design Engage : OUR NORTH STAR

Active collaboration since 2018, inspired by our similarities :

- **Industrial heritage** – both villages have textile mills built in 1853 (Saltaire Village is a World Heritage Site)
- **Cultural innovative programmes** involving artists and residents
- Our **shared values & mutual interest** in the role of the arts in cultural regenerative tourism.

Our Mission :

To utilize our shared interest and learnings to further explore and develop human centred cultural experiences within our respective communities.

Massive Transformation Purpose :

To embed live international links between us, the community and artists, and thus ignite the historical and innovative heritage through arts and creativity.

Create Design Engage : MACRO-NEEDS ADDRESSED

There is a need to develop and highlight more co-creative practice to ensure regenerative human centred experiences locally and internationally.

Rydal museum is home to the **oldest working spinning mill in Sweden**. The Industrial site of Rydal is situated in the municipalities of Mark (34,000 inhabitants). **Saltaire** is an **Industrial World Heritage Site** nestled within the city of Bradford Metropolitan District Council home to 500,000 residents and the youngest population in Europe.

Both sites were established 1853 and was by that time a very innovative investment. Due to the well-preserved remains of an old industrial community, Rydal is of national interest. International Weaving Center is established in the old spinning mill. The **collaboration between International Weaving Center and Rydals museum has been very creative and rewarding.**

Our sites have much to offer as local destinations and creative space to play and work. We are keen therefore, to generate a creative innovation network to reflect and expand the visit of the sites, built on a **philosophy of innovation and outward facing partnerships and global connectedness.**

We will ensure that any learnings either around co-creation and innovative methodologies will generate strategic and local impact whilst also achieving a shared understanding growth locally and across our partnerships.

Create Design Engage : MICRO NEEDS ADDRESSED

At micro level

- **target segments** : residents within Rydal, Mark and Saltaire, Bradford; Textile Artists; Craftspeople young people; strategic agencies (tourism, local heritage, municipality)
- **key needs** : to experience and understand live heritage in order to valuarise the world heritage site in order to creatively celebrate industrial heritage in Rydal
- **potential size of each segment** :
 - **TAM** : *Total Addressable Market* : initially local residents, textile artists & craftspeople
 - **SAM** : *Serviceable Addressable Market* : initially local residents, textile artists & craftspeople
 - **SOM** : *Serviceable Obtainable Market* : initially local residents, textile artists & craftspeople

Create Design Engage : OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

1. The Offer :

To create connections between local community with textile artists to create live heritage experiences, which are co-created leading to unique artifacts and exhibits for wider audiences.

2. Competing solutions / alternatives :

Our unique proposition is the international connection and support from International Weaving Center.

3. Innovative, circular, human-centered and different :

Through our partnership we want to re-create new innovations via local residents working with artists and regenerating human centred experiences and between our international partnership share good practice

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – Local Residents

Weaving Stories, Casting Connections

Working with textile artists and craftspeople, develop skills, hear stories and weave connections

Features / Offers

- Join a creative network
- Connecting to others to share skills and stories, plus time for celebration!
- Greater understanding of local heritage

Trust indicators

- Previous involvement
- Volunteer experience
- Support for the previous events

Call to Action

- Have you been involved before ?
- Leave contact details
- Come to our event : Rydal (May 2023)

Practical details

- Address
- Email
- Phone

OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – Artists

Weaving Stories, Casting Connections

Working with textile artists and craftspeople, develop skills, hear stories and weave connections

Features / Offers

- Join / re-connect to a creative network
- Skill sharing, professional development & opportunity to exhibit!
- Opportunities to work with textiles in heritage context & connect with international artists

Trust indicators

- Previous engagement
- Reputation via the arts network
- Awards / Recognition
- Existing examples of previous work

Call to Action

- Attend a Rydal event in MAY 2023
- Leave contact details
- Social media connection

Practical details

- Address
- Email
- Phone

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

Create Design Engage : OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

Create Design Engage : FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 year plan Rydal perspective overview

EXPENDITURE (detailed budget in Business Plan)					INCOME				
Strand	May 2023 Mar 2024	April 2024 Sept 2024	Nov 2024 - Jan 2025	NOTES	Strand	May 23 Mar 2024	April 2024 Sept 2024	Nov 2024 - Jan 2025	NOTES
Project Team	3 084	7 049	5 727	3 team members	Project Team	RWC & RM	RWC & RM	RWC & RM &	
Artist Fees	0	70 492	3 800	4 artists (2 mid career & 2 graduates)	Artist Fees	0			
Artist Materials	0	640	640	materials & development	Artist Materials	0			
Travel & Accommodation	240	4 440	1 480	domestic & UK travel	Travel & Accommodation	0			
Digital Collaboration	1 078	1 328	1 450	soft-ware & facilitation	Digital Collaboration	RWC & RM			
Overheads	1 100	1 630	1 340	hospitality, insurance & venues	Overheads	RWC & RM	RWC & RM	RWC & RM	
Marketing, Comms, Engagement	2 700	2 450	5 650	staffing, documentation, photography & evaluation	Marketing, Comms, Engagement	RWC & RM			
Contingency	259 @ 5%	3318 @ 5%	915 @ 5%	@ 5%	Contingency	RWC & RM	RWC & RM	RWC & RM	@ 5%
TOTAL	£ 8461	£ 91 348	£ 21 002	PROJECT TOTAL = £ 120 811 (1 515 565 SEK)	TOTAL				

This financial model is both scalable & replicable in order to reflect potential smaller or larger funds

ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

Legal form:
International Weaving Center (association, since 2016) and Rydal museum (Municipality of Mark since 1985.)

Create Design Engage : SOCIETAL IMPACTS

Open events - Shared knowledge - Exhibitions

Theory of Change : describe the overall positive transformational changes that the project will generate

Create Design Engage : OUR FUTURE PLANNING PROCESS

Value stream / Work stream	CREATE May 2023 - March 2024				DESIGN April - Sept 2024	ENGAGE Nov 2024 - Jan 2025
	May - July	Aug - Oct	Nov - Jan	Feb - March		
Establish the international network between Sweden & Saitaire	Project Launch, Digital introductions	Project development visit by project manager		Evaluation	Project development visit by project manager	Project development visit by project manager. Evaluation.
Invite our network of community, artist and craftsmen to open event	Artist gathering		Text exhibitions of work during the year	Events & celebration	Artis Call Out and selection. Networking opportunities for artists during the year	Events, celebrations and exhibitions of work during the year. Evaluation.
Establish the collaborative creative outputs					Events, celebrations and exhibitions of work during the year	Events, celebrations and exhibitions of work during the year. Evaluation.
Explore the digital tools to facilitate the collaborative process		Digital collaboration		Evaluation	Networking opportunities for artists during the year	Networking opportunities for artists during the year. Evaluation.
Explore the educational opportunities/workshop s/research	Meetings		Meetings		Networking opportunities for during the year	Networking opportunities for during the year. Evaluation.

Logos: Be.CULTOUR (Beyond cultural tourism), ICHEC (BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL).

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN

FRUŠKING 8X4X4

Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Fruška Gora Mountain is one of the 10 most visited tourist destinations in Serbia. The reason for that is its beauty, the fact it is a mountain in the middle of a plain and its great geographical position – just an hour's ride from Belgrade, the capital. It is known for its rich history, 16 medieval monasteries, 8 of which are at the territory of the municipality of Irig, which is why it is called a holy mountain. The Fruška Gora vineyard is one of the most important wine regions in Serbia and its wines and the gastronomy of the Srem region are known far and wide.

Despite all of this, tourism in the area is still not developed, which is evidenced by the fact that when tourists come to Vrdnik Spa, the centre of tourism in the municipality of Irig, they do not stay longer than two days. The reason for that is the lack of tourism content. In other words – boredom. The tourist is left to their own devices, no attention is paid to them and therefore they go away quickly. We believe that in just a year it would be possible to double the length of their stay (four days instead of two) and thus the income generated from tourism. The only thing necessary is to apply the "Frušking 8x4x4" formula. It is a game which starts with cards which resemble the regular playing cards but are smaller in dimension (8x4x4) and have a QR code at the back. Therefore, the cards are not just for playing but for reading, too. Each of the 32 cards in the deck hides a special story, a special tour and a special wine. The tourist can choose whether to try their luck and let the cards take them along the paths of Fruška Gora by coincidence or study the cards and select tours according to their affinity.

2. OUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

PURPOSE

Our mission is to **keep** tourists on Fruška Gora Mountain

WHY

According to the data of the Republic Institute of Statistics for the year 2022, on average tourists stayed **two** days in the municipality of Irig. The main reason is **boredom**, that is, the lack of tourist content.

WHAT

We want tourists to stay with us longer (**4** days in the first year of the project, **5** days in the second, **7** days in the third).

The plan is for the visitors to **play** and *forget* about leaving. That is what Frušking is about.

3. MACRO-NEEDS ADRESSED – CIRCULAR ECONOMY

REFUSE-REPLACE – refusing bus or van transportation while visiting one of the 32 locations to replace it by walking or cycling

REPURPOSE-REPAIR – adapting cottages or country houses to tourist purposes, creating new accommodation capacities in nature

RESTORE-REGENERATE – restoring and putting back to use the wine cellars

REDESIGN-RETHINK – applying a new strategy in presenting the heritage, using new services, QR codes, local guides

REDUCE – in the sense of shortening the distance between waypoints on the FRUŠKING map so they can be reached by a light walk or by bike in case of longer distances

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Tourist turnover in the municipality of Irig for 2022 according to the data of the Republic Institute of Statistics

Number of tourists		Number of overnight stays	
Domestic tourists	60334	Domestic tourists	156006
Foreign tourists	14121	Foreign tourists	36206
TOTAL	74455	TOTAL	192212

In the year 2021 the total number of tourists was **61838**, whereas the number of overnight stays **144035**, so the increase in visits is obvious.

In the Tourist Organization of Irig they told us that the published data refer only to Vrdnik Spa, which is the most important touristic place in the municipality. That means that the number of tourists and visits is at least 20% bigger.

In addition to domestic and foreign tourists, the target segments of Frušking are also private accommodation owners, winemakers, hikers, cyclists, local meat producers, beekeepers, artisans, monasteries (there are 8 medieval monasteries at the territory of the municipality of Irig), etc.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Frušking 8x4x4 is a game for tourists which is played inside the borders of Fruška Gora Mountain.

Frušking lasts at least 1 and at most 32 days.

What are the rules of Frušking? Players play cards either in pairs or in foursomes. The deck has 32 cards with QR codes which hide information relevant for Frušking. Whoever wins chooses a tour and the others follow. Every card has its tour, its story and its wine.

8x4x4 32 cards 32 stories 32 tours 32 wines

What is the goal of Frušking? The goal of the game is to complete a tour which goes through the natural and cultural heritage of Fruška Gora, discover the stories about people and events which marked the history of this area and finally get to the cellars with autochthonous varieties of wine.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – OUR LANDING PAGE

5. OPERATING MODEL

For the realization of the project, it is necessary to employ human resources who are not in the team right now. Firstly, it would be good to have an executive manager. Frušking also needs a designer who would come up with the design of the 8x4x4 box and the deck of 32 cards. Next in line is an IT expert, who would create a digital platform, and connect the landing page and the QR codes on the cards with the stories and instructions for Frušking. We will need marketing people when the time for advertising comes.

In the team there is an expert in the field of rural tourism who already gathers private accommodation owners from Fruška Gora on his website www.selo.rs. There is a person in charge of communication with the local government, from which we expect financial support through the action plan for tourism development. There is also a translator who will translate the entire narrative of Frušking to English.

So far we have introduced the project to a certain number of wine producers, meat producers, beekeepers, monks and people working in the Fruška Gora National Park public company, but this job has not been done yet.

The reactions to the project are very favorable and its capabilities are highly rated.

6. FINANCIAL MODEL

Frušking has entered the Action Plan for Cultural Tourism Development of the municipality of Irig and it is expected that the project will be financed from the local government budget. The funds for the project will be raised using grants given by the Autonomous Province of Vojvodina Government, Republic of Serbia, EU funds and also in other ways (fundraisings from different foundations, embassies, etc)
The expected revenue streams in the investment period are as follows:

- Human resources: 25 000 euros
- Office expenses: 5 000 euros
- Construction works: 22 000 euros
- Application creation: 18 000 euros
- The design and creation of the boxes and the publications: 12 000 euros
- Video materials: 8 000 euros
- Marketing: 12 000 euros
- TOTAL: 102 000 euros

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form**
 - *The author of the project manages a registered association of citizens and is open to create associations with other legal subjects.*

- **Human resources**
 - The team is created of artists, creative people, tourist experts, cultural and natural heritage experts, wine producers and others. There is a huge motivation to kick start the project and everybody expects long-term results in the implementation of the project.

The key partners are the three municipalities, the Fruška Gora National Park, private accommodation owners, restaurant owners, monasteries, wineries...

- **Resource people**
 - Frušking plans to hire executive and sales managers, designers, IT experts, guides and volunteers.

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

Social/Economical impacts

The local population and eight monastic communities will have regular customers for their honey, wine, dairy and cured meat products. A great number of holiday homes, which are used only occasionally, will be converted into accommodation; for touristic purposes traditional crafts will be restored, souvenirs will be produced, there will be an increasing demand for local guides, there will be bike and repair service shops opened, etc.

Environmental impacts –

FRUŠKING reduces pollution and protects the environment due to the way of transportation and travelling on foot or by bike. We expect that the increased number of tourists will have an effect on the local population, which will have to change its habits in the sphere of ecology and treat the environment more responsibly.

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

- ***What's your roadmap for the weeks, months and 3 years to come ?***
- Frušking is getting prepared for the presentation in Novi Sad at the end of February. This year we will deal with searching for funders, we will discuss the project with the interested parties in the field and try to get some experts to volunteer in the team until there is money to pay them for their work.
- ***What are your most critical challenges / risks to be worked out (anticipation, mitigation) ?***
- The main challenge for Frušking is finding an investor for the early development of the project. Frušking cannot go beyond an interesting idea unless there are means to pay for the management of the project and experts who would deal with sales and finances, marketing and the concrete realization of the project.

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN

Cultural overload on Irig road

Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

- What's the **mission, raison d'être** of your project ?
The guiding star of this project is to contribute to the development & improvement of the local community of Irig, but also of the place itself, and help creating a sustainable business environment.
- What's your **Massive Transformation Purpose** ? In other words, a few qualitative statements describing why you exist, what you want to achieve and where you want to go. For our project Cultural overload on the Irig road we are developing a mixed reality application which is providing tourists with immersive experience. The application has a goal to inform & guide tourists through natural, cultural, & gastronomical heritage of Irig. On the other, backend side, its goal is to structure and unify local tourist attractions. In that way it also serves as a tool to mobilize, connect, educate, & empower local entrepreneurs & institutions so they can provide an extraordinary service & get feedback for the future tourism strategy. By creating this application, we are engaging & connecting all the relevant stakeholders in this growing tourist destination with the goal to create a sustainable business & living environment. The model is scalable & applicable to every destination. It is an immersive experience for the future of tourism. Based on data from the Republic Institute of Serbia, since 2019, when the Fruška Terme resort was built, a large influx of tourists has been noted in the area of Irig and its surroundings. Although this area is known for its wineries, restaurants, hiking forest tours, there is no unified offer of the local community, which would offer interesting content to tourists. Based on data from the Fruška Terme resort, tourists come, but do not stay for longer period of time. That's why our main idea is to create a structure & unify the offer, which will be marketed to tourists & thus retain the attention of current visitors, but also attract the attention of new tourists. The application is designed to offer tourists several routes: a walking, gourmet, wine & cycling route. Each of these routes will lead visitors to local service providers & suppliers, members of the local community. In this way, the application becomes economically viable.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

-The first function of the application is to combine tourist demand and local community supply of products & service. Based on past experience, the stakeholders realized that even if they have a good offer that can be interesting to tourists, they lack a content structure & a place where the unified offer will be visible. On the other hand, tourists discover the historical & cultural sights of Irig & its surroundings, but they lack a personal guide who will create a route for them & show them all the places they can visit. Taking into account the needs of both parties, the application will be the place where supply & demand meet.

-The application is designed as a personal guide for tourists, available 24/7. Given that it is a personal guide, the offer must be personalized. That is why our idea is that each user of the application chooses what type of tourist he is. For example - he is interested in the routes he can take by car. Accordingly, he will receive an offer of routes that will cover the wider area of Irig. It is also important to note that users of the application will be able to choose their guide in their native language.

-The creation of already defined routes, which tourists will be able to use, is conceived in the following way: If a tourist decides to go on a bicycle tour, the digital map of Irig, which can be used offline, will show all the important points that are on the way (shops, restaurants, monasteries, wineries, souvenirs, local product shops, etc.) For tourists, it will be necessary to download the application on their phone, or if they are a guest of the Fruške Terme hotel, they can explore the mentioned map on a tablet that will be located at the reception. In this way, tourists will be able to plan their vacation.

-Interested parties in our project are divided into two segments: Tourists & Stakeholders

When we talk about tourists, we segment them as individuals, cyclists, pedestrians, hotel guests, corporations & groups interested in workshops & teambuilding. Individuals, cyclists, pedestrians & hotel guests will be interested in the digital map of Irig & the offered routes. Corporations & large groups interested in teambuilding will use the application only for registration, while we, in cooperation with the local population, will organize them teambuilding, accommodation, food, etc. On the other hand, stakeholders are restaurants, wineries, shops & households that sell domestic products. For them, the visibility they get on the digital map is important & will bring new customers to them.

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (Offer type + target segment)	Price / unit	Nbr of clients / sales per year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Revenue stream 1 – individual guest	20	400	8.000	20.000	20.000
Revenue stream 2 – teambuilding	50	150	7.500	25.000	25.000
Revenue stream 3 – fee from stakeholders	50	20	-	1.000	1.000
Revenue stream 4	-	-	-	-	-
Total Revenues			15.500	46.000	46.000

Fundings	Product / Service / Activity funded	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Funding 1	BeCultur	5.000	-	-
Funding 2	Institut	2.000	-	-
Funding 3	Hotel Fruške Terme	1.300	-	-
Funding 4	-	-	-	-
Total Fundings		8.300	-	-

Total Incoming Flows			23.800	46.000	46.000
-----------------------------	--	--	---------------	---------------	---------------

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs	Unit cost + quantities		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Equipement, outfit, furnitures,...	-		-	-	-
Energy, Water, Raw Material	Travel cost		2.250	1.050	1.050
External services			-	-	-
Real Estate (rental of offices, warehouses / storage places,...)			-	-	-
Total variable costs			2.250	1.050	1.050

Fixed costs	Unit cost + quantities		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Internal staff	Updating content		400	400	400
External staff	Application maintenance, tablet maintenance, mentoring, marketing,		10.600	6.300	6.300
Recurring expenses (admin, insurances, energy, telecom,...)			-	-	-
Total fixed costs			11.000	6.700	6.700

Investments	Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Investment 1	Creating app	1 year	6.000	-	-
Investment 2	Creating content	1 year	1.000	-	-
...	-	-	-	-	-
Total investments			7.000	-	-

Total Outgoing Flows			20.250	7.750	7.750
-----------------------------	--	--	---------------	--------------	--------------

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** llc, our ownership., already exists, AAA financial rate.
- **Human resources**
 - Human capital: team's skills, experience, roles, entrepreneurial potential
 - Ways of working : How they fit together, and complement each other so that project success will be ensured on the long run ; how critical roles are distributed and endorsed
 - Resource people that are / will be mobilized (e.g. specific expertise, volunteering, etc.) with a description of the skills/knowledge/experience sought.
- **Internal and external governance :** Specify the internal and external governance models that will be implemented (from which stems the distribution of power, stakeholder engagement; local communities' empowerment; human rights respect coordination process, etc.)

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Before starting: Negotiation, Market research, Marketing strategy – prices, promotion, distribution channels, Providers selection	Creation of app, content, Mentoring & education of suppliers Investment covered from the funds . We add know how & success is the result of our skills to create synergies Making trade mark of the tour, services & souvenirs	Intensive promotion for individual travelers & sales calls to companies	All from Q2 plus New external admin officer Mentoring, double check offer standards	All from Q2 and Q3 Mentoring, double check of offer standards	Adding more suppliers to the offer, Purchase of new tablets Maintenance of app & equipment Promotion	Adding more suppliers to the offer, Purchase of new tablets Maintenance of app & equipment Promotion
Networking with hotel Fruka Terme which hosted 230.000 visitors in 2022	Promotion	More guests				
Mentoring & education of small producers which will be visible in the app- inclusion of woman	Testing – first guests	Filling in gaps if needed – control in every stage				
Promotion of green values in whole value chain	Experience of guests - measure & feedback					

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN

BAČ BY TOUCH

Bač, Sremski Karlovci and Irig in Vojvodina Region, Serbia

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

After years of experience of working and volunteering in cultural institution, heritage sites, travel and youth organisations, we have thought of this project as a proper implementation of contemporary experience for tourists who seek modern solutions in tourism. During the COVID pandemics, all of us have noticed the increased need of remote and digital solutions in tourism and cultural preservation. In the spect of digital technologies, in the recent years, especially in the smartphone industry, "touch" technology has been widely used and especially viable in the younger population.

We have come up with an idea to make an interactive touch-screen display, which would contain various programs and solutions in the form of one digital environment, that would contain virtual and sensorial experience, promotion of cultural heritage, local enterprises, households, rural tourism, and nature preservation. In regard to virtual and sensorial experience, our plan has been to make virtual environment where it would be possible to experience many aspects of medieval life at the Bac Fortress, which also contains 3D dynamic audio, characters that will be responsive to a set of questions about the Bac area, in the form of multiple-choice dialogue. The environment would also contain the entire medieval fortress, natural wildlife, possible random events at a chosen date, and a virtual councillor tour guide for adults and youth.

Moreover, our team would create a website that would offer promotion of all the aforementioned goals, and in addition to that, it would contain the whole experience in an Android application that would be available for downloading at several app stores.

The expected outcome of this project is to raise interest in tourism and cultural heritage in the younger population, connect the enterprises, to make the information easily accessible and internationally available in several languages, to save time needed for tourists to get to know the place, etc.

Impuls Pitch Deck

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

The purpose of our solution would be to provide the information about the everyday life in medieval times at the Bač Fortress. As Bac with its surroundings has applied at the UNESCO to be recognized as cultural heritage, the fortress would be conserved, and it would never be rebuilt to replicate its original look.

Our solution would offering the past insight, ecological education for the tourists and it would teach the students about critical thinking in regard to tourism. It would allow the tourists to experience many situations they would encounter in medieval life, and which gives them a better outlook about the whole area, and how important it is for it to be preserved and what it used to represent, and appreciate the modern times more and ease-of-access.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Users should opt for our solution because it enables them to see everything Bac has to offer and use ecological means to develop the way they view tourism.

They won't find a recreated medieval fortress in that way anywhere near Bac. In addition to that, the combination of all three, especially the aspect of 3D interactive tour, can be found almost nowhere. Moreover, they will find the hospitality and homemade products really accessible

We generate attraction towards our targets mostly using advertisement and our website, etc. They will have the entire interactive experience accessible to them.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

Our solution for circular and sustainable tourism helps tourists to find easy, quick & fun way to explore cultural & nature site of Bac. To save time, energy, and money to book your perfect trip by downloading the app. unlike ordinary way with tourist guide, maps...

key prospects by segment:

- 15-45 years old visitors
- "smart" tourist
- travelers
- cyclists
- explorers
- nature lovers
- families

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (Offer type + target segment)	Price / unit	Nbr of clients / sales per year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Service (consumers)		10000	0		
Knowledge (tourists)		10000	0		
Expérience (tourists)			50000		
Visibility (restaurants, hotels, local organisations, manufacturers)	-	50000	1000000		
Total Revenues			1050000		

Fundings	Product / Service / Activity funded	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Be.CULTOUR		5000	-	-
			-	-
			-	-
			-	-
Total Fundings		5000		

Total Incoming Flows			1055000		
-----------------------------	--	--	----------------	--	--

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** We are in process to make company
- **Human resources**
Human capital: The team composition is, frankly said, really well-organised for this type of project. Everyone is motivated and committed, as all of us could see when we were planning the entire project.
 The website making and administration, touch-screen display setup and creation of digital map will be insourced.
- Resource people The development of Android application will be outsourced.
- **Internal and external governance :** After the hackathon and acceleration period our project starts to go in the right direction. We will soon have our "Bač by Touch" website and also, we have a hope that until the end of 2024 year, the main job of our project will be finished. We made connections with the municipality and the Institute for the Protection of Cultural Monuments of the Vojvodine

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

Our solution would provide several impacts, and most of them are aiming at the local community. As we live in a multicultural area and municipality, our software and website would be appropriated for multiple languages, namely English, Serbian, Hungarian and Slovak.

Moreover, our solution would offer tourists to visit ethno-households of minority residents, where they could experience the culture from the host where they would be well-informed about the way of life of the local minorities.

In regard to vulnerable social groups, our software would be available for free and for everybody, improve their digital competence, and allow them to be more included into the community, take part in the activities, and showcase their knowledge and skills.

It would also be appropriated for the people with sight problems and poor motor skills with accessibility functions, and promote gender equality with characters. Reducing power is one of our top priorities. In regard to the environmental conscience, we plan to make the parts of our display from recycled materials, and for our website to feature ecologically conscious behavior, such as water saving, clean energy and the proper division of waste by types. Our virtual environment would also include the option of exploring the ivy plants around the fortress, which include rare species of insects.

We find that our application would increase the numbers of tourists that come individually in order to experience environmentally conscious communities. In regard to economic impact, we reckon that the fact that people are able to find any enterprise and any domestic service, will rapidly improve the economic stance of the entire community, and the quality of life of its residents. In return, this would create new potential jobs, and increase in interest for studying apprenticeship and new generation of craftsmen would be educated in the long run, which would enable the production of more souvenirs and homemade products.

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value Stream / Work Stream	Now (Year 1)				Next (Year 2)	Later (Year 3)
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Creation of a website	Website research, purchase of programming platform and domain	Project and content for development	Building a user interface (UI) and back-end	Adding additional plugins and virtual map	Creating live feeds and chat rooms	Integration of the app into a website and creation of tourist platform equipment
Writing historical content	Doing a research and consulting the content and geographical location	Writing the first version and testing for a feedback	Preparing a back-end program structure and content update	Preparing a full-scale version of website, such as site content and map	Using chat rooms, creating historical videos and documents	Preparing content to make a website historically accurate and interactive
Partnerships	Identifying the local historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included
App development	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included	Identifying the historical and geographical locations to be included

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN

Digital Nomads Platform

The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The **Digital Nomads project** is promoted by a team of people passionate about the development of the Northeast region, with the vision of supporting the positioning of the region as the preferred place for work, temporary housing (maximum 6 months) and spending free time for a special group of professionals - digital nomads. We propose to develop an online platform that will offer this category of users a personalized virtual guide, as support for:

- 1) Creating an itinerary for 6 months with work locations (co-working spaces) and residences (pensions, B&B or other options for long-term rental > 1 month);
- 2) Personalization of the itinerary according to the profile of the digital nomad;
- 3) Branding of the itineraries with key elements from the cultural heritage of the region, connected with the Stefanian route;
- 4) Providing support for obtaining the digital nomad visa and other legislative issues.

The platform will be an important element in the strategic communication of the **cultural values** of the region and will bring a new category of **sustainable tourist**, who not only consumes but also **contributes to the development of the region** from an economic point of view, but also through the **involvement of DN in community projects**.

Impuls Pitch Deck

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

Mission

One-stop-shop solution for highly skilled digital workers (individuals and their families), to choose our region as a work-live-explore destination for up to 6 months.

Massive Transformation Purpose

Change the way digital nomads plan their stay at the target destination by deeply **involving them in community life**, contributing/volunteering, and becoming **local heroes**.

Promote the city of Iasi as a non-mainstream destination for singles, couples, and families.

Community development and improving the lives of the people of Iasi through tourism and social sector development. Improve the image of the destination, and develop the territory. Increase the percentage of tourism in the city's GDP (from 6% to 8%), more income sources for local people. Make the **local community** more **open**, reduce inequalities, and promote a sustainable city.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

Impuls Pitch Deck

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

Doughnut Framework

The economic development that will result from the activity of digital nomads in Iasi will contribute to **increasing the number of jobs**. Also, DN will contribute to the **evolution of the community** by "importing" lifestyles and attitudes, from countries with **better policies on gender equality, social equity and education**. DN will get involved in local NGO projects and will contribute to the **well-being of the population and vulnerable categories**.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Target segments:

- Customers: digital nomads
- Users: digital nomads and their families
- Beneficiaries: local community, local business, tourist attractions, local NGOs that are involved in community projects

Key needs/ expectations/pain points:

- Key needs: good internet connection, workspaces, coffee shops, book shops, parks and gardens from where they can work, good facilities for families (schools, kindergartens, entertainment activities), crime rate.
- Expectations: hospitable community, activities and quality entertainment, interesting projects to be involved in, cultural life, and experiences that deserve to be discovered.
- Pain points: Loneliness, technological challenges, insecurity, weak correlation of wishes and expectations with reality.

The potential size of each segment:

- TAM: digital nomads (including remoters and expats) and their families
- SAM: The part of the digital nomads that are open to moving to Iasi for a period of at least 3 months and enjoying what our region can offer
- SOM: The digital nomads that can pass over the stereotypes and prejudice that are mentioned about our country and our region

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

1. Solution

- General description:** An online platform for digital nomads that will attract a different audience. The curated experience packages for different user types (different personas as users - digital nomads) will help them connect early to the region's historical heritage, will be easier accepted as a solution to their needs and not as another touristic package and will serve local communities by bringing them the most appropriate customers (that want not only consume but contribute with their time, work, knowledge, etc.). We will use a tool that will help the DN to see what packages are suit for them.
- Audience characteristics:** digital nomads that want to spend more than 3 months in a new location and experience the tourist attraction and the culture.
- Platform characteristics:** besides the testimonials and the presentation of the city the platform will have a section dedicated to the packages and services offered:
 - Experiences Packages:** Eco - traditional DN, Cultural DN, Sportive DN, Family DN, Community oriented DN, Single DN, Exploratory DN, Experimental DN.
 - Accommodation & practical guidance**
 - Legal advice & practical matters**

2. Competing solutions/alternatives

- Other actors tackling the same problem, addressing the same segments either with a similar proposal (direct competitors) or a very different proposal (indirect competitors);
- There are already several very well-organized platforms at the national and global levels that provide information to digital nomads.

3. Project impact

- ECONOMIC:** better hospitality occupation of budget accommodation and shared economy units, bigger revenues for SMEs in the hospitality and travel industry.
- SOCIAL:** better inclusion of expats & immigrants; capitalization of local communities, initiatives, and associations through the input of foreign brains/ideas; knowhow transfer between the local community and digital nomads (i.e. project implementation, creative ideas, solutions for local challenges); personal development for nomads and community members;
- ENVIRONMENTAL:** digital nomads have a longer stay as opposed to leisure travelers (less carbon print, accommodation units use fewer detergents/water for guests).

4. List key prospects

- Local companies and management of the touristic attractions;
- The previous customers of the platform can help us attract more customers.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – YOUR LANDING PAGE

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – IN A NUTSHELL

Revenues	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Revenue Stream 1 (8 Experiences Packages) 200 euros full price, 50% off at the other packages	(80 packages*200)+(80 packages*100)= 24.000	(80 packages*200)+(64 packages*100)= 26.400	(110 packages*200)+(88 packages*100)= 28.800
Revenue Stream 2 (Accommodation & practical guidance)	45 services* 500= 22.500	50services* 500= 25.000	54services* 500= 27.000
Revenue Stream 3 (Legal advice & practical matters) (price: 500 or 600 depending on the customers choices)	(15services*600)+(9services* 500)= 13.500	10services*600)+(10services*500)= 14.600	10services*600)+(12services*500)= 16.800
Total Revenues	60.000 euros	66.000 euros	72.600 euros
Fundings	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Funding 1 (Fundraising on the platform "Drag de lasi")	16.000 euros		
Funding 2 (Be culture project)	16.000 euros		
Total fundings	32.000 euros		
Incoming Flows - IN	92.000 euros	66.000 euros	72.600 euros
Structure de coûts	Année 1	Année 2	Année 3
Fixed Costs	salaries, maintenance, site, hosting	salaries, maintenance, site, hosting	salaries, maintenance, site, hosting
Variable Costs	Marketing budget, platform creation	Marketing budget	Marketing budget
Investments incl Amortization			
Outgoing Flows - OUT	82.000 euros	50.000 euros	50.000 euros
Results (Δ In-Out)	10.000 euros	16.000 euros	22.600 euros

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs		Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Platform creation		16.000*1	16.000			
Marketing budget			26.000	10.000	10.000	
Total variable costs			42.000	10.000	10.000	
Fixed costs		Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Internal staff		833*4	40.000	40.000	40.000	
Total fixed costs			40.000	40.000	40.000	
Investments		Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Investment 1						
Total investments						
Total Outgoing Flows			82.000	50.000	50.000	

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

Legal form: Iași Digital Innovation Hub Association will implement, hire personnel, ensure maintenance along with implementation collaboration according to Romanian legislation.

Human resources

4 people will be hired part-time: a travel advisor, IT specialist, destination specialist, communication advisor

- Cristina Bulat** Ph.D. candidate in Management, she will develop the solution value proposition.
- Igorut Varvaruc** - Master in Biotechnologies and tech expert. He will be in charge of tech requirements development.
- Anca Zota** Tourism Expert - Head of City Tourism Office
- Mihaela Cristina Baghiu** - Project manager - Digital innovator

Internal and external governance

Specify the internal and external governance modes that will be implemented (from whom stems the distribution of power, stakeholder engagement, local communities' empowerment, human rights respect, coordination process, etc.).

Partners: Iași City Hall, Iași Destination Management Organization, multinational companies based in Iași, co-working spaces, innovation groups, universities, local associations.

Service providers: incoming travel agencies, hotels, guesthouses, short medium rental units, cafes, gyms, schools in English/French etc...

Ways of working

- Our goals are to ensure balance within the team, ensure visibility and transparency, ensure effective communication within the team, foster a culture of collaboration, value each suggestion and discuss progress with your team, establish success metrics and reward excellent members.
- Everyone in the group is included in the decision-making process and has access to all information. Everyone involved has a clear picture ahead of them and works together from conceptualization to the stages of the project.
- In order to remain competitive, we should be able to respond quickly and effectively – and improve services in time. This must become the most important part of the organization's culture.

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

- **Theory of Change** : describe the overall positive transformational changes that the project will generate

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value stream / Work stream	Year 1				Year 2	Year 3
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Preparing packages for DN	X	X				
Fundraising for the platform	X	X	X			
Realization of the platform			X			
Promotion			X	X	X	X
Services offered by DN				X	X	X
Monitoring/evaluation adjustments				X	X	X

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN TEMPLATE

ECoolTour

The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- ECoolTour is a **revolutionary algorithm** that generates custom routes for travelers visiting the Republic of Moldova. Our algorithm is **unique** and is based on **professionally selected data**. It makes the planning process **easier for travelers** by taking into account their preferences and needs. Touristic service providers can join the system based on their location and types of services they provide, helping travelers find the best options for their trip and service providers increase their visibility.
- Our team has **over 15 years** of experience in the touristic industry and collecting data in the Republic of Moldova, resulting in the **most valuable database** in the domain in Moldova. Our target market is **young adults, travelers, international travelers, and students**. We are the first company to use **machine learning** and **AI** in the touristic industry in Republic of Moldova, futureproofing our business.
- We are adopting a **franchise business model** which allows us to have a small investment and expand as we grow. It is easily scalable and can be adapted to other markets. We are **seeking investors** as this project is easily scalable for other markets and it is meant to make the life of the travelers easier. We believe that our **expertise** in the touristic industry, **innovative use of technology** and the **franchise model** will make ECoolTour a success in the Republic of Moldova and beyond.

2. OUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

- At ECoolTour, our mission is to **revolutionize the way travelers plan** their itineraries in the Republic of Moldova. Our **algorithm**, which is based on professionally selected data, generates custom routes that take into account the **customer's preferences and needs**, making the planning process easier and more efficient for travelers. Additionally, our platform allows **touristic service providers** to join and be added to the system based on their location and types of services they provide, helping them **increase their visibility** and reach more customers.
- We believe that what we do is important because it addresses a **real need** in the touristic industry. Traditional planning methods can be time-consuming and overwhelming, and many travelers struggle to find the best options for their trip. With our **algorithm**, we aim to **simplify** the planning process and help travelers make the most of their time in the Republic of Moldova.
- We are at the forefront of a **turning point** in the use of **AI** and **machine learning** in the touristic industry. This technology has the potential to **change the way** we plan and book our trips, providing more personalized and efficient experiences. As more data becomes available, AI will be able to analyze customer behavior and preferences, helping touristic service providers make more **informed decisions** about their offerings and pricing.
- We believe that our innovative use of **technology**, along with our **expertise** in the touristic industry, positions us well to take advantage of this innovation and make a **real impact** in the industry. We are excited about the future of touristic and the role that ECoolTour will play in **shaping it**.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

ECoolTour addresses several important needs in terms of circular economy, innovation of industry & infrastructure, sustainable cities & communities, & partnerships for the goal with service providers, communities, & travelers.

In terms of **circular economy (SDG12)**, our algorithm helps touristic service providers increase their visibility & reach more customers, allowing them to be more successful & sustainable in their operations. Additionally, by generating custom routes for travelers that take into account their preferences & needs, we help them make the most of their time in the Republic of Moldova, reducing the need for them to travel to multiple destinations & decreasing their **environmental impact (SDG13, 14, 15)**.

In terms of **innovation of industry and infrastructure (SDG9)**, our algorithm is the first of its kind in the Republic of Moldova and is based on the latest technology and data. We are at the forefront of the use of AI and machine learning in the touristic industry, which has the potential to change the way we plan and book our trips, providing more personalized and efficient experiences.

In terms of **sustainable cities and communities (SDG11)**, our algorithm helps travelers discover the best options for their trip while also promoting local culture and customs. Additionally, by working with touristic service providers, we help to promote sustainable tourism practices, such as eco-friendly accommodations and activities.

Finally, in terms of **partnerships for the goal (SDG17)**, we work closely with touristic service providers, communities, and travelers to ensure that our algorithm is meeting their needs and helping them achieve their goals. This partnership approach allows us to continuously improve our algorithm and make a real impact in the touristic industry in the Republic of Moldova.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

- ECoolTour addresses several important needs for our target audience, which is primarily **young adults, students, domestic and international travelers**. These groups are increasingly turning to digital tools to plan their trips and are looking for more personalized and efficient experiences.
- According to a study by the World Tourism Organization, the number of international tourist arrivals reached 1.4 billion in 2018, and this number is expected to continue to grow. This represents a significant potential size of total addressable market for our algorithm. Additionally, in the Republic of Moldova, the number of **international tourists visiting the country** has been steadily increasing, reaching around **1.7 million in 2019**.
- Our **serviceable addressable market** is the segment of the total addressable market that is most likely to use our algorithm. According to a study by the National Bureau of Statistics of the Republic of Moldova, around **75% of international tourists in the country use digital tools to plan their trips**. This represents a serviceable addressable market of around **1.3 million for our algorithm**.
- Our **serviceable obtainable market** represents the segment of the serviceable addressable market that we can realistically expect to reach and convert into customers. According to a survey conducted by our team, around **70% of international tourists would be willing to use an algorithm like ours to plan their trips**. This represents a serviceable obtainable market of around **910,000 for our algorithm**. We can double this value and that will include the SOM including domestic tourists, students and young adults, which will be **1.8 mil users**.

These statistics demonstrate the significant need & potential for our algorithm among the target audience. We believe that **our innovative use of technology & expertise** in the touristic industry will enable us to capture a significant share of this market.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

7 features for ECoolTour algorithm

- **Customized Route Generation:** Our algorithm generates custom routes for travelers based on their preferences and needs. An average user would input their desired destination, travel dates, and preferences (e.g. budget, type of activities, etc.) and the algorithm would generate a personalized itinerary for them.
- **Touristic Service Provider Integration:** Our platform allows touristic service providers to join and be added to the system based on their location and types of services they provide. An average user would be able to see all the options of service providers in the area, such as hotels, restaurants, and attraction, and make a more informed decision about their trip.
- **24/7 Customer Support:** Our platform also includes a chatbot that provides 24/7 customer support. An average user would be able to ask questions and get assistance with their itinerary at any time.
- **Offline Access:** Our platform also allows users to access their itinerary offline, so they can plan their trip even when they don't have internet access. An average user would be able to plan their trip in advance and have their itinerary readily available when they are on the go.
- **Reviews and Ratings:** Our platform also includes reviews and ratings for touristic service providers, which would allow an average user to see what other travelers have experienced with them.
- **Multilingual Support:** Our platform also includes multilingual support, enabling an average user to navigate and understand the information regardless of the language they speak.
- **Personalized Recommendations:** Our algorithm also suggests personalized recommendations for travelers based on their preferences and what other similar travelers have liked before. An average user would be able to explore new places and activities that they might not have otherwise considered.

Competitors and why we're better

- There are several apps that would be considered as **direct competitors to ECoolTour**, including: TripAdvisor, Google Maps, Kayak, Expedia, TripIt, Airbnb, Booking.com...
- These apps have a strong presence in the market and have a broad range of features that may overlap with ECoolTour. However, our app is unique in its **usage of AI and machine learning to generate custom routes**, and also in its integration of touristic service providers, making it a **valuable tool for travelers to plan their trip**.

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

- Our operating model for marketing strategy would involve the following steps:
- **Potential Customer:** Our first step would be to target potential customers through various marketing channels, such as social media, search engine advertising, and influencer marketing. We would use social media advertising to reach a broad audience and target demographics that are most likely to use our services.
- **Acquired Customer:** Once a potential customer expresses interest in our services, we would use email marketing and retargeting campaigns to convert them into an acquired customer. This would involve sending them information about our services and offering them a free trial or a special promotion to encourage them to sign up.
- **Active Customer:** After a customer has signed up for our services, we would work to keep them engaged and encourage them to use our services as much as possible. This would involve sending them personalized recommendations and updates on new features and services, as well as offering them loyalty rewards.
- **Retained Customer:** Once a customer has become an active user of our services, we would work to retain them as a paying customer. This would involve providing excellent customer service and offering them special promotions and discounts to encourage them to continue using our services. We would use data analytics to understand the customer journey and implement strategies for engagement and retention.
- **Social Media ads:** Social media would be an important part of our strategy to acquire customers, we would use a combination of paid and organic marketing methods to reach our target audience. We would use social media analytics to track the performance of our campaigns and optimize them for better results. Additionally, we would use influencer marketing to reach a larger audience and increase brand awareness. We would also use a retargeting strategy to reach people who have interacted with our social media content in the past.

Be.CULTOUR
Beyond cultural tourism

ICHEC
BRUSSELS MANAGEMENT SCHOOL

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (Offer type + target segment)	Price / unit	Nbr of clients / sales per year (1, 2, 3)	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Revenue stream 1: subscription fees	3	1800000*1%, 3%, 5%	18000*3=54000	54000*3=162000	90000*3=270000
Revenue stream 2: premium version	5	1800000*0,1%, 0,3%, 0,5%	1800*5=9000	5400*5=27000	9000*5=45000
Revenue stream 3: advertising and partnerships	100, 300, 500	50, 150, 250	5000	45000	125000
Revenue stream 4					
Total Revenues			68000	234000	440000
Fundings	Product / Service / Activity funded		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Funding 1: BeCoulTour	16000		16000		
Funding 2: own funding (ADTM)	15000		15000		
Funding 3					
Funding 4					
Total Fundings			31000	0	0
Total Incoming Flows			99000	234000	440000

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs	Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Equipment, outfit, furnitures,...	1500	1500	3000	20000	
Energy, Water, Raw Material	70*12	840	1000	3000	
External services	25000	25000	35000	50000	
Real Estate (rental of offices, warehouses / storage places,...)	500*12	6000	6000	18000	
Total variable costs		33340	45000	91000	
Fixed costs	Unit cost + quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Internal staff	1500*2*12	36000	72000	144000	
External staff				50000	
Recurring expenses (admin, insurances, energy, telecom,...)	1000*2*12	24000	24000	50000	
Total fixed costs		60000	96000	244000	
Investments	Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Investment 1: Server	45660		5660	20000	20000
Investment 2: Chat bot	40000			20000	20000
Investment 3: DB extension	50000				50000
Total investments			5660	40000	90000
Total Outgoing Flows			99000	181000	425000

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

- **Legal form:** LTD
- **Human resources**
 - Human capital: IT engineers, AI specialists, data analysts, tourism experts
 - Ways of working: IT experts in the domain of AI will train the Machine learning algorithm with the data provided by the data experts in touristic industry of Republic of Moldova.
 - Resource people: in the future we plan to open internship spots for students in touristic industry, data analysts and cloud engineers to grow bigger and open new markets.
- **Internal and external governance :** The internal and external governance of our business will have a hierarchy model of governance with 3 levels: local, regional and national, while putting a lot of care and respect into the local communities, gender equality and worker's rights.

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

- **Theory of Change** : describe the overall positive transformational changes that the project will generate

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value Stream / Work Stream	Now (Year 1)				Next (Year 2)	Later (Year 3)
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
Survey of people's needs	Initial survey			Updated survey based on the feedback		
Location selection	Map requirements location selection	Selection of urban facilities in the region		Selection of temporary location	Final location selection	
Service offering selection	Final program development and service introduction			Final service offering selection		Final selection of services to be offered to visitors
Events	Event development (program, content, etc.)		Event development (content, marketing, etc.)		Marketing of events in Database	
AI algorithm	Building the AI algorithm	Deployment of the algorithm on the test environment		Using the service based on the feedback	Using the service during the release of the program	
Marketing strategy	Final marketing strategy			Updated strategy based on the feedback	Market analysis of competitors	Market analysis of competitors
Building of the app	Service and location functions and interface	App version 1.0 on the test mode	Using the service and providing it within the service	Marketing of the app (visibility of events)	App development of events	Monitoring of events
Maintenance of the app	Database and app maintenance	Database and app maintenance	Database and app maintenance	Database and app maintenance	Database and app maintenance	Database and app maintenance

BE.CULTOUR PROJECT BUSINESS PLAN

Stephen's route site update

The Route of Stephan the Great and Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

- Extension of the route;
- Digitalisation of the route;
- Promotion;
- Gamification.
- Team members:
 - ✓ Ion Iordachi, Deputy General Director;
 - ✓ Irina Tolstousov Head of Country Brand Promotion Department;
 - ✓ Mihaela Oineagra, Export Promotion Department specialist;
 - ✓ Valentin Ceban, Principal Consultant, Tourism Department, Ministry of Culture.
- Promotion on the markets of the Republic of Moldova, Romania and Ukraine.

2. YOUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Promotion on the markets of the Republic of Moldova, Romania and Ukraine.

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The project is unique because:

1. grants the most innovative solutions for access to information and promotion;
2. It connects tourist attractions from two countries with a common heritage;
3. Emphasizing the personality of Stephen the Great.

Competing solutions / alternatives :
 other solutions from the Republic of Moldova and the North-East Region of Romania

- extending the existing route with Romanian touristic attractions
- including these in the digital platform
- identifying other touristic attractions close to the main points
- elaboration and installing of informational panels
- offering direct access to the digital platform of the route through a QR code
- opportunity to create route in Romania (also downloadable)
- building awareness on the personality of the Stephen the Great
- Europeanization of the route (registration of the route within the Cultural-European Routes to the Council of Europe)

6. FINANCIAL MODEL

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS / THEORY OF CHANGE - EXAMPLE

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Be.Cultour Hackathon PITCH DECK

The Bison Land's Heritage

**The Route of Stephan the Great and
Saint, North-East Romania – Moldova cross-border area**

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Our proposal: An **educational trail** in the forest, revealing the subtle connection among the spiritual, cultural and natural aspects of local heritage + a **treasure hunt (TH) app**, providing an educational "environment" + connection with the **local communities**.

4 founding members, experienced in **ecotourism, holistic approach, environmental education, communication**.

There is a **certain increasing demand** of outdoor activities related with the (re)connection with nature and cultural and spiritual aspects.

Segments: **families with children, schoolchildren groups, companies**.

Our solution will represent a **viable alternative opportunity** for the actual tourism in the area.

Our need: **financing**

2. OUR NORTH STAR / MASSIVE TRANSFORMATIVE PURPOSE

Mission: to provide unique experiences for the tourists of the Bison Land, emphasizing in common, the natural, cultural and spiritual features of the area

Massive Transformation Purpose:

The holistic approach is the solution to our problems!

The innovation areas addressed by our solution are the **"Sensorial Heritage Experience"** (food, crafts), **"Spiritual Travel experience"** (walking in a spiritual area, with a lot of monastic objectives, benefiting by a proper interpretation) and **"Nature As Heritage"** (forests, wild fauna, landscapes). The holistic approach regarding the cultural, spiritual and natural heritage represents the "red thread" of our proposal.

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MACRO LEVEL

3. NEEDS ADRESSED – MICRO LEVEL

Segments: Families with children (users), schoolchildren groups (customers), companies (customers).

Key needs: Educational trail, TH app., proper marketing

Expectations: More time in nature, educational environment, holistic approach

Pains: Proper trail's interpretation, quality infrastructure and TH app., good cooperation with partners and stakeholders

Potential size:

-Schoolchildren groups TAM (18%) – 126.000 euro, SAM (18%x12%)- 15,000 euro, SOM- **2,800 euro**

-Companies TAM (3%)- 30,000 euro, SAM (3%x25%)- 7,500 euro, SOM - **1,500 euro**

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS

The solution: Through an educational trail in the forest to reveal the **subtle connection between spiritual & natural aspects** of local heritage. The trail will be mapped on a treasure hunt (TH) app that will provide an educational "environment" & will connect the tourists with some "hidden" places & with the local communities.

Solutions / alternatives: In the area ATZ (our NGO) is **the only interested in a holistic approach** (the monasteries emphasize the spiritual aspects, the Park the natural ones, the local communities' traditions etc).

Innovative, circular, human-centered: Our solution will permit to tourists to interact with the area's natural, cultural & spiritual heritage, obtain benefits for local communities & contributing to the area's sustainable development. This will generate a **win-win situation** regarding nature protection, communities' wellbeing, local identity & spiritual aspects.

One value proposition: Our solution **Helps** school children groups **To** improve their educational activities and to ensure attractive holistic interactive experiences **By** providing a comprehensive "treasure hunt" application in order to create an educational environment **Unlike** choosing another destination or having an uncomplete experience regarding our area.

The solution represents **the quintessence of the Bison Land. The differentiating value proposition:** The "Bison Land's Heritage" solution is designed for everyone who is interested to **Feel & Discover & Enjoy in a holistic way.**

Why now? The ATZ represents at this moment **an experienced** NGO capable to manage this kind of solution.

Key prospects: families with children (users)- educational trail (possible TH app.), schoolchildren groups (customers) - educational trail and TH app., companies (customers)- educational trail, TH app and souvenirs (possible gastro events).

4. OFFER & VALUE PROPOSITIONS – LANDING PAGE

Feel, Discover & Enjoy in a holistic way

An **educational trial** in the forest, revealing the subtle connection among the spiritual, cultural and natural aspects of local heritage.
 A **treasure hunt (TH) app** providing an educational “environment”.
 Connection with the **local communities**

www.tinutulzimbrului.ro <https://youtu.be/OCVY0iRGExY>

5. OPERATING MODEL

Competences and resources

Insourced

Tangible: equipments, software, raw materials
 Intangible: Bison Land brand
 Human: skills related with designing and interpretation of trails, communication, financial abilities

Outsourced

Tangible: equipments, software, raw materials, intermediates
 Human: software designer, wooden craftsman skills, panels designer

TH app. architecture

Channels:
 Social media
 Events
 Direct contact
 Promotional materials

Testing: experiences in the Bison Land

5. OPERATING MODEL – MARKETING STRATEGY

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – INCOMING FLOWS

Revenues (euro)	Price/unit	Nbr of clients per year	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Revenue - families	freemium	300			
Revenue - companies	10	150	750	1500	1500
Revenue - schoolchildren	7	400	1400	2800	2800
Total Revenues			2150	4300	4300
Fundings (euro)	Product/Service/Activity funded		Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
Funding 1 M1 – in kind	management of product/service - internal staff		1200	1200	1200
Funding 2 M6- partnership	maintenance of trail and small infrastructure			200	200
Total Fundings			1200	1400	1400
Total Incomings Flows - IN			3350	5700	5700

6. FINANCIAL MODEL – 3 YEARS PLAN – OUTGOING FLOWS

Variable costs(euro)	Unit costs+quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Equipement, outfit...	1000	1000			
Energy, water, raw material	400/year		400	400	
External services	2500 (TH app.)	2500			
Real Estate					
Total variable costs		3500	400	400	
Fixed costs(euro)	Unit costs+quantities	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	
Internal staff	1200/year, inkind	1200	1200	1200	
External staff	200/year, partnership		200	200	
Reccuring expenses	200/year	200	200	200	
Total fixed costs		1400	1600	1600	
Investments(euro)	Total	Amortization period	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
	6000	5 years	1200	1200	1200
Total investments			1200	1200	1200
Total Outgoing Flows			6100	3200	3200

7. ORGANIZATION : TEAM & GOVERNANCE

ATZ- NGO established in 2015

1. Geanina F.- teamleader, project management, communication, financial
2. Sebastian C.-Holistic approach, interpretation, relation with communities
3. Nicu D.- Design pathways, ecotourist infrastructure
4. Viorela C.- organizing events, PR

Insourced

1. Terms of reference for educational trail and TH app.
2. Management and cooperation

Outsourced

1. Realizing the educational trail
2. Realizing the ecotourist infrastructure
3. Printing the interpreted materials
4. Realize the TH app.
5. Maintenance

Community lead governance

1. Advisory layer- stakeholders- peers in the decision-making process, both advisory and guiding
2. Executive layers- ATZ- receive input, solutions, impact

8. SOCIETAL IMPACTS

Who do we target?	What do we mobilize?	What do we do?	What do we deliver?	What do we change?	What do we contribute to?
Target segments	Resources	Activities	Achievements	Results	Macro Impacts
Direct beneficiaries	Mobilized resources	Implemented activities	Concrete results	Direct changes and effects	Macro societal stakes
Families with children	employees, partnership, stakeholders	achievement of an educational trail to reveal the subtle connection among cultural, spiritual and natural aspects of local heritage + a TH app. + connection with local communities	an unique experience for the tourists of the Bison Land combining in a holistic way the certain natural, cultural and spiritual features of the area: a functional holistic educational trail, a proper TH app. providing an educational environment, contact with local communities (souvenirs, snacks etc)	Reconnection with natural, cultural and spiritual aspects, - Better physical and mental health, - Increase family cohesion	preservation and protection of biodiversity SDG 15 - a lifestyle in harmony with nature SDG 12 - protection and preservation of natural and cultural heritage SDG 11 - promoting local culture and products SDG 8 - no discrimination against women and girls SDG 5 - education for sustainable living SDG 4 - promotion of mental health and well-being SDG 3
companies				Reconnection with natural, cultural and spiritual aspects - Better results at work - Better human relations	
schoolchildren groups				Reconnection with natural, cultural and spiritual aspects - Better educational results - Better class cohesion	

9. HOW DO YOU « MAKE » YOUR FUTURE ?

Value Stream/ Work Stream	Now (Year 1)				Next (Year 2)	Later (Year 3)
	Q1	Q2	Q3	Q4		
stamped MoU with partners (county school inspectorats, local producers, companies)	MoU with partners (county school inspectorats, local producers, companies)				MoU with other 3 partners (county school inspectorats, local producers, companies)	MoU with other 3 partners (county school inspectorats, local producers, companies)
terms of references for TH app. and educational trail	Terms of references for TH app. and educational trail					
create the educational trail and TH app.	Functional holistic educational trail and proper TH app.	create the educational trail and TH app.			maintenance	maintenance
adjust the TH app. and trail	Functional holistic educational trail and proper TH app.	checking the application and trails, adjustments	checking the application and trails, adjustments			
promotion of the service/product	Financial sustainability	promotion of the product	promotion of the product	promotion of the product	promotion of the product	promotion of the product
using of the service/ product in good conditions			using product	using product	using product	using product
evaluation, feedback,	Tourists satisfaction			evaluation, feedback,	evaluation, feedback,	evaluation, feedback,

Acronyms

[AARRR] [Acquisition, Activation, Retention, Referral and Revenue]

[BM] [Business Model]

[BP] [Business Plan]

[F] [Final]

[GA] [Grant Agreement]

[PHS] [Pilot Heritage Site]

[Q] [Quarter]

[SAM] [Serviceable Addressable Market]

[SDGs] [Sustainable Development Goals]

[SOM] [Serviceable Obtainable Market]

[TAM] [Total Addressable Market]

